

Angular momentum and dark matter in void dwarf galaxies

A Thesis

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Dedicated to my parents.

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Declaration

This thesis is a presentation of my original research work. Wherever contributions of others are involved, every effort is made to indicate this clearly, with due reference to the literature, and acknowledgement of collaborative research and discussions.

The work was done under the guidance of Jayaram N. Chengalur, at the National Centre for Radio Astrophysics, Tata Institute of Fundamental Research, Pune.

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In my capacity as supervisor of the candidate's thesis, I certify that the above statements are true to the best of my knowledge.

(Jayaram N. Chengalur)

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Abstract

We use neutral hydrogen (HI) emission to probe various processes that shape the structure and dynamics of dwarf galaxies. In particular, we use HI observations of a sample composed primarily of dwarf irregulars in voids to determine the kinematics, which in turn is used to measure the angular momentum and dark matter halo properties of the galaxies and the dependence of these parameters on the galaxy environment. We investigate the systematics involved in the derivation of rotation curves and their effect on inferred dark matter density profiles. We study the baryonic/gas specific angular momentum of a diverse sample of galaxies to develop a holistic understanding of the formation and evolution of the gas disks.

We present HI images as well as kinematical data for 24 galaxies residing in the Lynx–Cancer void. These were obtained as part of a systematic survey of the most gas rich dwarf galaxies residing in this void. This survey has led to discovery of several interesting systems that show signs of interaction and gas accretion. We have selected a sub-sample 11 galaxies for which rotation curves can be reliably derived. We derive their rotation curves by using 2–D and 3–D tilted ring fitting routines, and the derived curves generally overlap within the error bars, except in the central regions where, as expected, the 3D routines give steeper curves.

We construct mass models of eight gas rich dwarf galaxies that lie in the Lynx–Cancer void and we find that both the isothermal and NFW halos are a good description of dark matter distribution of galaxies in terms of the fit-quality (i.e. χ_{red}^2). From NFW fits to the dark matter halo profile, we find that the concentration parameters of haloes of void dwarf galaxies are similar to those of dwarf galaxies in normal density regions. We measure the slope of the central dark matter density profiles, obtained by converting

the rotation curves derived using 3-D and 2-D tilted ring fitting routines, into mass densities. We find that the average slope ($\alpha = -1.39 \pm 0.19$), obtained from 3-D fitting is within the range expected for Λ CDM haloes. On the other hand, the average slope ($\alpha = -0.49 \pm 0.24$) measured using the 2-D approach is closer to what would be expected for an isothermal profile. This suggests that systematic effects in the velocity field analysis have a significant effect on the slope of the central dark matter density profiles.

We present measurements of the baryonic mass (M_b) and specific angular momentum (j_b) of 11 void dwarf galaxies. We find that the dwarf galaxies residing in voids and average density environments have similar specific angular momentum. However, all dwarf galaxies have significantly higher j_b than expected from the relation obtained for larger spiral galaxies. This increase in specific angular momentum sets in at a baryonic mass threshold of $10^{9.1} M_\odot$. Interestingly, this mass threshold is very similar to the mass threshold below which galaxy discs start to become systematically thicker. We examine the possibility that both these effects, viz. the thickening of disks and the increase in specific angular momentum are results of feedback from star formation. Such feedback would preferentially remove the low angular momentum gas from the central parts of dwarfs (thus increasing the specific angular momentum of the system) and also inject mechanical energy into the system, leading to thicker discs. We find however, that the amount of observed star formation in our sample galaxies is insufficient to produce the observed increase in j_b . We suggest that other mechanisms, such as for example, cold mode accretion of high specific angular momentum gas, may also be playing a role

To further understand the role of angular momentum in disc galaxies, we study the relationship between the HI specific angular momentum (j_g) and the HI mass (M_g) for a sample of galaxies with well measured HI rotation curves that span a range of morphology. We find that all the galaxies ranging from dwarfs to late-type spiral galaxies ($10^7 - 10^{10.5} M_\odot$) follow an unbroken power law for the $j_g - M_g$ relation with a slope of 0.87 ± 0.05 . This is in contrast to the $j_b - M_b$ relation, which has a break at $10^{9.1} M_\odot$. We

show that this break arises because of the change in gas to stellar mass ratio with mass as well as the different slopes of the stellar and gas j - M relations. Our sample includes two HI-bearing ultra diffuse galaxies, and we find that their angular momentum follows the same relation as other galaxies. The only discrepant galaxies in our sample are early-type galaxies with large rotating HI disks, these are found to have significantly higher angular momentum than expected from the power law relation. The HI disks of all these early-type galaxies are misaligned or counter-rotating with respect to the stellar disks, consistent with the gas being recently acquired. Our observations are in reasonable agreement with models which assume that evolutionary processes maintain HI disks in a marginally stable state and also support simulations which suggest that late stage wet mergers, as well as cold flows play a dominant role in determining the kinematics of the baryonic component of disk galaxies.

Publications related to thesis

1. **Sushma Kurapati**, Jayaram N. Chengalur, Simon Pustilnik, Peter Kamphuis *Angular momentum of dwarf galaxies*, 2018, MNRAS **479**, 228.
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Other publications

1. J. N. H. S. Aditya, Nissim Kanekar, **Sushma Kurapati** *A Giant Metrewave Radio Telescope search for associated HI 21cm absorption in high-redshift flat-spectrum sources*, 2016, MNRAS **455**, 4000.
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3. **Sushma Kurapati**, Arunima Banerjee, Jayaram Chengalur, Dmitry Makarov, Svyatoslav Borisov, Anton Afanasiev and Aleksandra Antipova *Mass modelling of a superthin galaxy, FGC 1540*, 2018, MNRAS **479**, 5686.
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GLOSSARY

1

Introduction

Galaxies are gravitationally bound collections of stars, gas, dust, and dark matter. Galaxies have a range of shapes, colors, and other characteristics. Astronomers developed galaxy classification systems based on their visual appearance to further understand these objects. [Hubble \(1936\)](#) divided galaxies into spirals (disks with spiral structure), ellipticals (smooth ellipses), lenticulars, and irregulars. There were further subdivisions in each of these categories depending on how tightly wound the spiral arms were, the roundness of ellipse, and if the galaxy had a bar, among other characteristics. This morphological classification scheme is usually referred to as a tuning fork diagram, which is shown in [Figure 1.1](#). Elliptical galaxies form the “handle” of the tuning fork diagram. They are arranged in an increasing order of ellipticity from left to right. Spiral galaxies without bars are on one prong of the fork and with the bars are on the other. Lenticular or S0 galaxies are at the junction of prongs and the handle. These S0 galaxies have a disc but show no or faint spiral arms, and have colours similar to the ellipticals. The galaxies with a large bulge compared to its disk such as E, S0, are called as early-type galaxies while the spiral galaxies with lower bulge fractions are called as late-type galaxies.

Galaxies of different Hubble types differ not only in their morphologies, but also by other properties such as color, stellar mass, gas content, and star formation rate, etc. Studies using SDSS based samples have shown that galaxies have a bi-modal distribution in colour as a function of stellar mass ([Baldry et al., 2004](#)). In such a plot the galaxy population is broadly divided into two groups, viz., “blue cloud” and “red sequence”. The transition region between the two groups is referred to as

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the green valley. Red sequence galaxies usually have early type morphologies, higher stellar masses, with little or no star formation, and have older stellar populations. Galaxies in “blue cloud” are the galaxies that mostly have late-type morphologies and are actively forming stars. Green valley galaxies are thought to be galaxies transitioning from blue cloud to red sequence with intermediate morphologies and star formation rates. This colour bimodality shows that the morphology is closely related to other properties of the galaxy. Understanding the evolutionary processes that determine the correlations between different galaxy parameters has long been a major field of research in astronomy.

In this thesis, we are mainly interested in dwarf irregular galaxies. Dwarf galaxies are significantly smaller than Milky Way. There are many definitions for dwarf galaxies, most of which are based on the optical luminosity. Here we generally follow [Tammann \(1994\)](#) in defining dwarf galaxies as those with their blue magnitude greater than -17 mag. The dwarfs with irregular shapes and spheroidal shapes are termed as dwarf irregular (dIrr) and dwarf spheroidal (dSph) galaxies respectively. Dwarf spheroidal galaxies have very little gas, negligible amount of on-going star formation, and mostly have older stellar population. On the other hand, dwarf irregular galaxies are gas-rich galaxies with ongoing star formation. Dwarf galaxies are the most abundant galaxy type in the local universe.

We use neutral hydrogen (HI) emission to probe various processes that shape the structure and dynamics of galaxies. We use both qualitative studies of HI morphologies and quantitative studies of parameters such as angular momentum and dark matter halo properties to understand galaxy structure and to make inferences about its evolution. We use HI to assess the kinematics, which in turn will help us in the derivation of angular momentum and dark matter halo properties of galaxies and their dependence, if any, on the galaxy environment. In this chapter, we provide the essential background required for a better understanding of the work presented in the subsequent chapters.

1.1 Galaxies in the cosmological context

1.1.1 The large scale distribution of galaxies

The standard cosmological picture emerging from various observations (e.g. Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) radiation and its fluctuations, expansion history mea-

Figure 1.1: Hubble tuning fork diagram for galaxy classification with the figures from Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS). This figure is taken from [Masters et al. \(2019\)](#)

surements using supernovae Ia, large scale structure power spectra measured through spectroscopic surveys, etc) is the Λ Cold Dark Matter (Λ CDM) model. The formation and evolution of the large scale structure of the Universe is well described within the Λ CDM paradigm. This model predicts that large scale structure of the universe is formed through hierarchical clustering, where small scale structures merge under the influence of gravity to form progressively larger structures. High density regions contract, and finally collapse, accreting material from their surroundings while emptying the under-dense regions further. In this scenario, the matter distribution on mega-parsec scales forms a web like pattern, which is called the “cosmic web” ([Bond et al., 1996](#)). This structure was first recognized by [de Lapparent et al. \(1986\)](#), and is confirmed by modern redshift surveys such as 2dFGRS ([Colless et al., 2003](#)), Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) ([Tegmark et al., 2004](#)), and the 2MASS redshift survey ([Huchra et al., 2005](#)). Current high resolution N-body simulations also reproduce the cosmic web quite accurately ([Springel, 2005](#)).

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1.1.2 Galaxy formation

In the standard picture of galaxy formation, baryons follow the distribution of the dark matter, because of coupling via gravity (see e.g. [Benson, 2010](#)). However unlike dark matter, gas can lose its energy and cool down by radiation. This results in baryons falling towards the center of the dark matter halo ([White and Rees, 1978](#); [Fall and Efstathiou, 1980](#)). The gas finally collapses into dense molecular clouds and start forming stars. The influence of dark matter haloes, interaction with the circumgalactic medium, and the feedback mechanisms between baryonic components regulate the gas content and galaxy evolution.

1.1.3 Accretion of gas

How galaxies get their gas is one of the key questions in understanding galaxy formation and evolution. The accretion of gas from the low density intergalactic medium (IGM) into the overdense dark matter haloes is necessary for galaxy formation. Further, accretion must occur through the life of a galaxy for it to sustain their star formation over cosmological times without depleting their observed gas mass ([Larson, 1972](#); [Fox and Davé, 2017](#)). In the classical theory of galaxy formation ([Rees and Ostriker, 1977](#); [Silk, 1977](#)), gas is shock heated once it enters the dark matter halo before it cools down and settles onto a disk ([White and Rees, 1978](#)). This mode of accretion is termed ‘hot-mode’ ($T \sim 10^6$ K) accretion. Recent simulations have highlighted the importance of second mode, the ‘cold-mode’ ($T = 10^4 - 10^5$ K) accretion, where cold gas flows along filaments directly into the disk and they make specific predictions about its dependence on galaxy mass, environment, and redshift ([Kereš et al., 2005](#); [Dekel et al., 2009a,b](#); [Kereš et al., 2009](#)). Simulations show that ‘cold mode’ accretion dominates in galaxies with baryonic mass less than $10^{10.3} M_{\odot}$ at $z=0$, where the gas is never heated and falls down to the centre of the halo in free fall time.

1.2 Role of environment on galaxy evolution

The Cosmic Web is made up of interconnected filaments, walls, and nodes (galaxy clusters) which enclose vast low density regions. Matter flows out of the least dense regions (or voids) into walls, along filaments, then to clusters and super-clusters found at the intersection of the filaments. A large fraction of the volume of the universe is

1.2 Role of environment on galaxy evolution

occupied by voids while most of the galaxies reside in groups, clusters, and the filaments connecting these massive structures. The galaxies broadly form and evolve in these four types of environments inside the cosmic web.

The formation and evolution of a galaxy is strongly related to its surrounding environment. One of the clearest indicators for an environmental dependence of galaxy evolution is the ‘density-morphology relation’, red, gas-poor, early-type galaxies are more common in high density environments such as galaxy clusters, whereas blue, gas-rich, late type galaxies dominate the field population (Dressler, 1980). Similarly, at intermediate redshifts, the fraction of blue star forming galaxies in clusters is higher than that in local clusters (the ‘Butcher-Oemler effect’; Butcher and Oemler (1978)). These effects suggest that galaxies in high density environments tend to quickly lose their gas, and stop forming the stars and become red, while the galaxies in low density regions tend to accrete fresh gas and keep forming stars, giving them their blue appearance. Various mechanisms have been proposed as responsible for the transformation of star forming late type galaxies into passive early type galaxies in clusters. For example, ram pressure that arises due to the fast motion of galaxies through a hot intra-cluster medium (ICM) is expected to compress or completely remove the interstellar medium (ISM) from galaxies (Ram pressure stripping; Gunn and Gott (1972); Quilis et al. (2000); Tonnesen et al. (2007)). Galaxy strangulation/starvation, where the weakly bound diffuse hot halo gas from the galaxy is stripped, will quench the star formation once the gas supply is exhausted (Larson et al., 1980). Alternatively, tidal interactions between neighbouring galaxies (e.g. galaxy harassment; Moore et al. (1996)) lead to the transformation of disk galaxies to ellipticals. Studies of galaxy clusters and groups have also provided evidence that galaxy transformation occurs not just in dense cluster cores, but also at lower densities such as cluster outskirts or galaxy groups. The infalling galaxies undergo ‘preprocessing’ before their arrival in the galaxy cluster, or are transformed entirely in the group environment (Fujita, 2004; Bahé et al., 2013).

In the other extreme, voids provide us with environments that are largely unaffected by the complexities and processes modifying the galaxies in groups and clusters. They are extremely underdense regions spanning tens of megaparsecs. These voids are not empty, but contain a sizeable galaxy population. Observational studies of void galaxies find that galaxies in voids are bluer, have higher specific star formation rates, and are of later types than galaxies residing in average density environments (e.g. Rojas et al.,

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2004, 2005; Patiri et al., 2006; von Benda-Beckmann and Müller, 2008; Hoyle et al., 2012; Kreckel et al., 2012; Moorman et al., 2016) suggesting that they are less evolved compared to the similar mass galaxies in high density regions. This arises naturally in hierarchical structure formation models, since small galaxies progressively merge to form larger galaxies and galaxies embedded in voids represent less evolved systems (Goldberg and Vogeley, 2004). Hence, voids provide us with a unique opportunity to study the evolutionary processes that are relevant at high redshifts and study galaxies at the earlier stages of their evolution. Further, voids are ideal places to search for cold gas accretion, since it is expected to be important in low density regions at redshift(z) ≈ 0 (Kereš et al., 2009).

Studies of the properties of the void galaxies can provide strong constraints for distinguishing the intrinsic (e.g. when the galaxy is first assembled) and external processes that drive galaxy evolution. Dwarf galaxies are particularly interesting for this study as their shallow gravitational potential makes them more vulnerable to the surroundings compared to the massive galaxies. In this thesis, we select dwarf galaxies from a nearby 'Lynx–Cancer' void. We use neutral hydrogen, which often extends well beyond stellar disk to trace galaxy interactions and to study kinematics of galaxies.

1.3 Neutral hydrogen

Hydrogen is the most abundant element of the universe and it constitutes about 75% by mass of all the observable matter in the universe. In its atomic state, it can emit a photon at 21 cm. This radiation is produced during the hyperfine transition of the hydrogen atom from the triplet state to the singlet state. Although this is a highly forbidden transition, it is easily observable due to the large amount of neutral hydrogen in the universe. This 21 cm line has been used extensively to map the neutral hydrogen (HI) distribution in galaxies. HI observations directly trace the gas reservoir that drives and regulates star formation. HI observations also provide important information on the kinematics of galaxies since the HI often extends well beyond the stellar disk. The HI disk is fragile, more susceptible to external forces (e.g. tidal interactions, ram pressure stripping, and gas accretion), and can exhibit a disturbed morphology for a long period of time after such events. Hence, it is an ideal tool to probe galaxy interactions with the environment.

Bosma (1978, 1981a,b) found that the HI rotation curves of spiral galaxies were fairly flat at the outskirts for most of the galaxies which became the major evidence for the existence of dark matter in galaxies. The HI kinematics in combination with the multi-wavelength data can be used to infer the luminous and dark matter distribution of galaxies and to understand the dynamical structure of galaxies.

In this thesis, we use high resolution HI observations from various radio interferometers such as Giant Metrewave Radio Telescope (GMRT), Very Large Array (VLA), and the Westerbork Synthesis Radio Telescope (WSRT) to study the detailed structure of the HI component of a sample of dwarf irregular galaxies residing in a void. Further, these high resolution HI observations allow us to derive high quality rotation curves, which can be used for the determination of dark matter distribution and angular momentum of gas rich disk galaxies.

1.4 Kinematics

The rotation curve is the variation of the rotation velocity with radius. Rotation curves are usually derived from the star or gas velocities at different radii. The emission lines from the optical spectra such as $H\alpha$ of the ionized gas can be used to derive the rotation curves. Similarly, HI 21 cm radio observations can also be used to derive the rotation curves. The optical rotation curves provide more details on the dynamics of the inner part of galaxies due to their high resolution while the rotation curves derived from HI observations are more extended. Thus, the HI rotation curves which probe the mass distribution to much larger radii, are essential for the study of angular momentum and dark matter properties of galaxies.

1.4.1 Tilted ring model

The kinematics of gas rich disc galaxies have traditionally been modelled using the “Tilted Ring Model” (Rogstad et al., 1974). In this model, we assume that the gas flows at a constant speed at a specific distance from the kinematic centre. A rotating disk galaxy can then be described by a set of concentric rings, each of which is assumed to be in a circular motion. Each ring is characterized by centre, systematic velocity (V_{sys}), rotation velocity (V_{rot}), position angle of the major axis (PA), and inclination

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Figure 1.2: Schematic diagram showing tilted ring model. Diagram taken from [Rogstad et al. \(1974\)](#)

angle (i). The line of sight velocity at any (x,y) position on a ring with radius R is given by

$$V(x, y) = V_{sys} + V_{rot}\sin(i)\cos(\theta) + V_{exp}\sin(i)\cos(\theta) \quad (1.1)$$

where θ is the position angle with respect to the receding major axis measured in the plane of galaxy and V_{exp} is the expansion velocity. θ is related to the actual PA in the plane of the sky as follows:

$$\cos\theta = \frac{-(x - x_o)\sin(PA) + (y - y_o)\cos(PA)}{R} \quad (1.2)$$

$$\sin\theta = \frac{-(x - x_o)\cos(PA) + (y - y_o)\sin(PA)}{R\cos(i)} \quad (1.3)$$

The free parameters for each ring would be its centre, the rotation velocity, inclination angle, and position angle of the major axis. For a regular disk, one would expect that the parameters such as centre, inclination, and position angle may not change much with radius and V_{exp} is usually set to zero for well-behaved galaxies. This modelling yields the “rotation curve”. This tilted ring model has been implemented in the GIPSY task ROTCUR ([van der Hulst et al., 1992](#)), which works on a 2D velocity field. Most of the earlier modelling software available for determining rotation curves work on 2D velocity fields determined from the 3D data cube (i.e with RA, DEC and velocity as axes). Velocity fields determined in this way could suffer from

systematic problems, such as a flattening of the velocity gradient in the central part of the galaxy because of the finite resolution of the observations (the so called “beam smearing” problem). Beam smearing tends to smooth out the velocity gradients in the central regions of galaxies. If this effect is not corrected for, the derived rotation curves will be shallow and lead to systematic errors in derived dark matter distribution. These problems become more pronounced as the number of resolution elements across the galaxy decreases and the inclination of the galaxy disc increases. There are now packages available (e.g., TIRIFIC, [Józsa et al. \(2007\)](#); 3d-BAROLO [Di Teodoro and Fraternali \(2015\)](#)) that determine the rotation curve by directly fitting to the 3-D data cube and include corrections for effects such as beam smearing. In our thesis, we have used both of the 2-D and 3-D approaches to derive the rotation curves and characterize the systematic differences between these two approaches. We use the rotation curves to measure the dark matter radial distribution as well as angular momentum of galaxies.

1.5 Dark matter

Early observations of HI rotation curves have shown that most of the spiral galaxies have flat rotation curves (e.g. [Bosma, 1978](#)). Since the visible matter in the galaxy is concentrated near the centre, this flatness of the rotation curves indicates a discrepancy between the amount of the mass inferred from observed rotation curves and the visible mass in the form of gas and stars. The commonly used hypothesis to explain this mass discrepancy is to assume a halo of unseen dark matter, which interacts with ordinary baryonic matter only gravitationally.

1.5.1 Cusp-core problem

The observed constant velocity at the outskirts of the galaxy disk implies that the dark matter density in the outer parts of a galaxy should have a density profile $\rho \sim r^{-2}$, which closely resembles an isothermal sphere. The rotation velocity associated with the dark matter often rises linearly with the radius, which indicates a central core in the dark matter distribution. In this thesis, we use pseudo isothermal halo to represent the cored model.

The standard Λ Cold Dark Matter (Λ CDM) simulations predict that the dark matter halo has a cuspy density profile with the density distribution in the inner regions

Figure 1.3: Schematic diagram showing the cusp-core problem.

following a power law $\rho \sim r^\alpha$ with slope $\alpha = -1$ (Navarro et al., 1996; Navarro and Steinmetz, 1997). This cusp model ($\alpha = -1$) has a steeply rising rotation curve as the square root of radius while the core model ($\alpha = 0$) rotation curve rises linearly. A schematic diagram elucidating this problem is shown in Figure 1.3.

We can test these models by observed kinematics of galaxies. It is difficult to test such models on spiral galaxies because gravitational force in the central parts of these galaxies has significant contributions both from gas and stars and the exact contribution of the stellar disk depends on unknown mass to light ratio. It is hence difficult to disentangle the dynamical contributions of dark and visible matter, and unambiguously determine the distribution of dark matter in the brighter galaxies. On the other hand, dwarf galaxies have little, or no bulge, and their stellar populations are dynamically unimportant. They are usually dominated by dark matter even in their central regions, making the mass modeling more certain than in spiral galaxies. Hence, dwarf galaxies are considered to be ideal laboratories to study the distribution of dark matter in the inner parts of galaxies.

Observations of dwarf galaxies and low surface brightness galaxies, where the dark matter dominates indicate the presence of a flat (~ -0.2) dark matter density core which is inconsistent with the expected cusps (e.g. Oh et al., 2015; de Blok et al., 2001; de Blok and Bosma, 2002b; Oh et al., 2011a). Some observational studies (Simon et al., 2005; Adams et al., 2014) find intermediate slopes, i.e. steeper than would be expected from a constant density core, but still significantly shallower than the slopes predicted by

simulations. This difference between observations and simulations is known as “cusp–core problem”.

Various solutions have been proposed to solve this problem, which are either related to the simulations or the systematics in observations. Some authors propose that dark matter could be warm or weakly self-interacting which would erase the cusps arising in pure Λ CDM cosmology (e.g. [Spergel and Steinhardt, 2000](#); [Rocha et al., 2013](#); [Elbert et al., 2015](#); [Kaplinghat et al., 2016](#); [Schneider et al., 2017](#)) while others invoke baryonic processes to generate cores from originally cuspy distribution (see e.g. [Pontzen and Governato, 2012](#); [Governato et al., 2012](#); [Pontzen and Governato, 2014](#); [Read et al., 2016a](#)). There is also a possibility that systematics in observations could give a false impression of cores. These category of solutions suggest that there are residual systematic problems in determining and modelling the rotation curves of galaxies, and these problems could result in a misidentification of cusps as cores (e.g. [van den Bosch et al., 2000](#); [Swaters et al., 2003](#); [Hayashi et al., 2004](#); [Oman et al., 2017](#); [Pineda et al., 2017](#)). These residual systematic effects include smoothing of the rotation curve because of the finite resolution of the observations ([van den Bosch et al. 2000](#)), incorrectly measured inclination angles ([Rhee et al., 2004](#); [Read et al., 2016b](#)), improperly modelled pressure support (e.g. [Pineda et al., 2017](#); [Rhee et al., 2004](#); [Valenzuela et al., 2007](#)) or unmodelled non-circular motions (e.g. [Oman et al., 2017](#); [Rhee et al., 2004](#); [Valenzuela et al., 2007](#)). All of these can lower the inner rotation velocities and mask the cuspy distributions. In this thesis, we investigate the systematics involved in the derivation of rotation curves and their effect on the mass models. We derive the rotation curves by using both the 3D and 2D tilted ring fitting routines. We compare the properties of dark matter halos that were obtained using the rotation curves from both approaches.

1.6 Angular momentum

The mass (M) and angular momentum (J) of galaxies are proposed to be the most important ingredients in their formation history and their evolution. They are conserved in isolated systems and are key to other properties. M and J are not independent (since J scales with mass), hence the standard method to study their relationship is to use the angular momentum per unit mass or the specific angular momentum (j) which is defined as $j = J/M$. The relation between the specific angular momentum and mass

1. INTRODUCTION

is considered as one of the fundamental scaling relations for galaxies (e.g. [Fall and Efstathiou, 1980](#); [Fall, 1983](#)).

Angular momentum remains constant unless acted by an external torque. In the standard scenario of cosmological galaxy formation, galactic haloes acquire their angular momentum through tidal torquing between neighboring protogalaxies in the primordial universe. These models predict that the specific angular momentum of the dark matter halo (j_H) = $k(\lambda) M_H^{2/3}$, where λ , the spin parameter of the halo, is approximately independent of mass ([Peebles, 1969](#)). However, this prediction is for the dark matter halo, whereas the observations are limited to the quantities pertaining to the baryonic components of the galaxies. According to these models, the dark matter halo and its gas component are expected to have similar specific angular momentum initially since the baryons and dark matter were well mixed and they must have experienced same tidal torques. Hence, if the specific angular momentum of baryons is conserved throughout the formation of galaxies, then a similar relation should apply to baryons.

Hydrodynamical simulations have for a long time suffered from catastrophic loss of angular momentum producing galaxies with too little angular momentum that were too small and bulge-dominated. This is a consequence of the hierarchical formation of galaxies which causes baryons to lose a large fraction of their angular momentum to the dark matter (e.g. [Navarro and Benz, 1991](#)). This is called as “Angular momentum catastrophe”. In recent simulations, with a higher resolution and inclusion of realistic feedback prescriptions that remove the low angular momentum from galaxy centers allowed formation of centrifugally supported disks with high specific angular momentum ([Governato et al., 2010](#); [Agertz et al., 2011](#); [Guedes et al., 2011](#); [Marinacci et al., 2014](#); [Brook et al., 2011](#)).

On the observational side, [Takase and Kinoshita \(1967\)](#); [Freeman \(1970\)](#) investigated the relationship between the total stellar angular momentum J_* and stellar mass M_* , and found them to follow a power law $J_* \propto M_*^{7/4}$. [Fall \(1983\)](#) studied the distribution of galaxies in the stellar specific angular momentum (j_*) and stellar mass (M_*) plane. They use the stellar masses derived from total luminosities and approximate the j_* by the product of length scale and rotation velocity to study the relationship between the j_* and M_* of 44 spiral and 44 elliptical galaxies. They show that j_* has a power law dependence on M_* : $j_* = q M_*^\alpha$, with $\alpha \approx 2/3$, which is in agreement with the scaling of dark matter haloes in Λ CDM cosmology. They also found that the spiral and elliptical

galaxies lie along parallel tracks, with elliptical galaxies having 5 times lower specific angular momentum as compared to spiral galaxies. This work was further expanded by [Romanowsky and Fall \(2012\)](#) and [Fall and Romanowsky \(2013\)](#) in which they revisit the $j_* - M_*$ relation using a broader morphology range of 67 spiral (Sa-Sm) and 40 elliptical (E7-S0) galaxies. They show that for a fixed mass, j_* is a function of Hubble type and can be used as a classification scheme for galaxies. These studies estimated j_* using the velocity width measurements and assume a specific form of rotation curve.

High resolution observations with optical integral field spectroscopy (IFS) and/or radio interferometers will allow one to obtain spectra at each pixel and the angular momentum can then be integrated pixel by pixel across the galactic disk. [Obreschkow and Glazebrook \(2014\)](#) were the first to consider the gas (atomic and molecular) contribution to angular momentum in addition to the stellar contribution. They present high precision measurements of baryonic specific angular momentum using 16 spiral galaxies from The HI Nearby Galaxy Survey (THINGS; [Walter et al. \(2008\)](#); [Leroy et al. \(2008\)](#)) survey, where they estimate J by integrating dJ over spatially and kinematically resolved galaxies. They have quantified the morphology via the bulge fraction (β) and they find a tight correlation between baryonic specific angular momentum (j_b), baryonic mass (M_b), and bulge fraction. They find that galaxies with the same bulge fraction have $\alpha \approx 1$, while they reproduce the $\alpha \approx 2/3$ trend if galaxies with different bulge fractions are lumped together ([Romanowsky and Fall, 2012](#)). These studies were extended to gas-rich dwarf galaxies ($10^7 - 10^9 M_\odot$). [Butler et al. \(2017\)](#) use 14 dwarf galaxies from LITTLE THINGS ([Hunter et al., 2012](#)) and find that they have systematically higher j_b compared to the $j_b \propto M_b^{2/3}$ observed for spiral galaxies with different bulge fractions. Similarly, [Chowdhury and Chengalur \(2017\)](#) measure j_b and M_b for 5 gas-rich dwarf galaxies and find that they have a higher baryon specific angular momentum compared to an extrapolation of the trends seen for higher mass bulge-less spirals.

In this thesis, we use interferometric HI observations to study the relation between the baryonic specific angular momentum and mass, as well as the gas specific angular momentum (j_g) and gas mass (M_g). We also study the baryonic j - M correlation for dwarf galaxies and in particular compare the baryonic specific angular momentum of dwarf galaxies residing in Lynx cancer void, UM cluster, and field. Studies of the environmental dependence are particularly interesting because different environmental

1. INTRODUCTION

processes (e.g. accretion, stripping, and merging) can redistribute the angular momentum of baryons during the evolution of a galaxy. We also measure the angular momentum of ultra-diffuse galaxies (UDGs) to test their formation scenarios since some formation models suggest that their large sizes can be due to their high spin parameters (Amorisco and Loeb, 2016). Finally, we study the gas j - M correlation for a diverse sample of gas-rich galaxies including HI-bearing ultra-diffuse galaxies (HUDs), normal dwarf galaxies, spiral galaxies, and S0 galaxies. Studying angular momentum of a diverse sample of galaxies as well as galaxies residing in different environments together will allow us to understand the effect of nature and nurture on baryonic angular momentum.

1.7 This thesis

The main scientific goal of this thesis is to understand the structure and dynamics of galaxies by using both qualitative studies of HI morphologies and quantitative studies of parameters such as angular momentum and dark matter halo properties. We use high resolution H I observations of galaxies residing in a void to understand environmental processes that are driving the galaxy evolution. We use HI kinematics to derive their rotation curves and thereby estimate their angular momentum and dark matter distribution. We compare the properties of these galaxies from these extreme environments to a control sub-sample of dwarfs in average density environments. In particular, we study the baryonic/gas specific angular momentum of galaxies residing in different environments and the j - M correlation of a diverse sample of galaxies to develop a holistic understanding of the role of angular momentum in galaxy formation and evolution. Further, we investigate the systematics involved in the derivation of rotation curves and their effect on inferred dark matter density profiles.

The outline of the remainder of the thesis is as follows. In chapter 2 we present the HI observations of 25 void dwarf galaxies and describe their HI morphologies. We also present rotation curves for a subset of 11 well-behaved galaxies using 2D and 3D approaches. We also highlight key results on the individually interesting systems. In chapter 3, we construct mass models of eight gas-rich dwarf galaxies that lie in the Lynx-Cancer void and compare the dark matter halo properties of void dwarf galaxies to those of dwarf galaxies in normal density regions. We present the measurements of

the slope of the central dark matter density profiles, obtained by converting the rotation curves derived using 3-D and 2-D tilted ring fitting routines, into mass densities. In the following two chapters, chapters 4 and 5, we study the baryonic/ gas specific angular momentum and mass relations. In chapter 4, we present the measurements of baryonic mass and baryonic specific angular momentum of 11 void dwarf galaxies. We discuss the specific angular momentum and mass relation for dwarf galaxies and compare them with the larger spiral galaxies. In chapter 5, we determine the empirical relation between gas specific angular momentum and gas mass for the galaxies ranging from dwarfs to late-type spiral galaxies. We also present the gas specific angular momentum of HI bearing ultra-diffuse galaxies and lenticular galaxies. We conclude this thesis by summarizing the main results in chapter 6.

1. INTRODUCTION

2

Void galaxies

2.1 Introduction

Voids are underdense regions of the universe that are largely devoid of galaxies and fill a large fraction of the universe volume. In the standard Λ Cold Dark Matter (Λ CDM) cosmology, structure in the universe was formed through hierarchical merging where the small scale structures merge to form progressively larger ones. In such a scenario, galaxies in the currently underdense regions are expected to be less evolved since they typically form at later times than those in the dense regions (e.g. [Aragon-Calvo and Szalay, 2013](#)). Hence, voids provide us with a unique opportunity to study galaxies at an earlier stage of their evolution. The galaxies residing in low density of void regions are expected to evolve in relative solitude and thereby retain important clues regarding their formation and evolution.

The structure formation in voids is similar to structure formation of a low density universe ([Goldberg and Vogeley, 2004](#)). They have a substructure consisting of subvoids, walls, filaments, and nodes at the intersection of filaments (e.g. [Aragon-Calvo and Szalay, 2013](#)). Numerical simulations suggest that the galaxies in voids may preferentially lie within these filamentary void substructures ([Aragon-Calvo and Szalay, 2013](#); [Sheth and van de Weygaert, 2004](#); [van de Weygaert and Platen, 2011](#); [Rieder et al., 2013](#)). Hence, they are interesting places to see if the intricate substructure expected from hierarchical formation process can be traced observationally. Voids are also ideal for studies of gas accretion since their inherent isolation will allow us to distinguish the effect of galaxy mergers from other forms of gas accretion. In particular,

2. VOID GALAXIES

‘cold accretion’ of gas along cosmic filaments is predicted to play an important role in low mass dark matter halos prevalent during the earlier stages of galaxy growth at high redshifts and at $z=0$ in low density regions (Kereš et al., 2005). Thus, the void dwarf galaxies that are both low mass and earlier in their evolution, are ideal targets to search for cold gas accretion.

The standard Λ CDM cosmology predicts a large population of low mass haloes inside the voids. In contrast to this expectation, dwarf galaxies follow the same large scale distribution as the bright galaxies. This discrepancy is called as “the void phenomenon” (Peebles, 2001; Hoft et al., 2006; Peebles and Nusser, 2010; Papastergis et al., 2015). Various processes have been proposed to explain the missing dwarfs within the context of galaxy formation theories, which include environmental properties of dark matter halos, baryonic deficiency, etc. For example, Tinker and Conroy (2009) suggested that there is a critical mass threshold below which void galaxies can not form enough stars and hence are dark. This problem would be resolved if the small haloes in voids are baryon deficient. However, Hoft and Gottlöber (2010) used hydrodynamical cosmological simulations and found that the baryonic deficiency is independent of environment. This discrepancy still remains a puzzle.

In addition, galaxy clustering was found to be a strong function of environment (Abbas and Sheth, 2007; Pujol et al., 2017; Paranjape et al., 2018). The small scale clustering of galaxies in voids is not found to differ from clustering of galaxies in average density environments (Szomoru et al., 1996). Abbas and Sheth (2007) found that galaxies in the least dense regions are more clustered than at moderate underdensities, but galaxies in moderate underdensities are less clustered than those at moderate overdensities. It would hence be interesting to compare the small scale clustering of HI selected galaxies in voids with that of galaxies in average density regions.

Observationally, several studies have shown that void galaxies are statistically smaller, bluer, later type, with higher specific star formation rates than galaxies in walls that surround empty regions (Rojas et al., 2004, 2005; Patiri et al., 2006; von Benda-Beckmann and Müller, 2008; Hoyle et al., 2012; Moorman et al., 2016; Grogin and Geller, 1999; Ricciardelli et al., 2014; Moorman et al., 2014, 2015). However, controversy persists in the literature as to whether the void galaxies have different intrinsic properties compared to similar galaxies in average density regions. For example, Park et al. (2007) suggested this difference was almost entirely due to the dependence of

morphology and luminosity on environment (see also [Patiri et al., 2006](#)). Late type galaxies which are more dominant in low density regions will have bluer colours and have higher star formation rates compared to those of early type galaxies. Indeed at a fixed luminosity (brighter than $M_r -16.5$) and morphology, the void galaxies were found to have statistically indistinguishable colours and star formation rates as those of galaxies residing in dense regions ([Kreckel et al., 2012](#)). On the other hand, [von Benda-Beckmann and Müller \(2008\)](#) indicate that the faintest void galaxies are intrinsically bluer and have higher star formation rates at a fixed morphology and luminosity. [Moorman et al. \(2016\)](#) found that dwarf galaxies have stronger trends with environment. They found that the fainter dwarfs in voids have higher specific star formation rate (sSFR) than their average density counterparts, while the more luminous galaxies are statistically indistinguishable from similar galaxies in the field. They suggest that voids provide a nurturing environment for dwarfs.

Gas is a crucial factor for understanding the influence of the void environment on the galaxy star formation history. [Huchtmeier et al. \(1997\)](#) found that the gas content of dwarf galaxies in voids increases the further into the void that they were located. Similarly, [Pustilnik and Martin \(2016\)](#) show that the low luminosity galaxies in voids are systematically more gas-rich than those in higher density regions. On the other hand, HI observations from the Void Galaxy Survey (VGS; [Kreckel et al. \(2012\)](#)) show that the HI gas content of void galaxies is statistically indistinguishable from galaxies in filaments and walls, for relatively brighter galaxies ($M_r < -16$). They have seen evidence for both ongoing assembly through the gas dynamics between interacting systems and significant gas accretion seen in extended gas disks and kinematic misalignments ([Kreckel et al., 2012, 2011a](#); [Beygu et al., 2013](#)). They identify 18 HI rich neighboring galaxies and suggest that small scale clustering in the void is similar to that in higher density regions.

HI studies of fainter dwarfs are particularly interesting since they were found to have higher sSFR than their average density counterparts. Moreover, extremely low metallicity dwarf galaxies have been discovered in voids, suggesting that voids are suitable for the study of unevolved dwarf galaxies (e.g. [Pustilnik et al., 2006](#); [Pustilnik and Tepliakova, 2011](#)). There is a tendency for dwarf galaxies to dominate as one goes towards the centre of the cosmic voids ([Hoyle et al., 2012](#)). Hence, studying faint dwarf galaxies in voids will allow us to understand the objects in deep voids. Dwarf galaxies

2. VOID GALAXIES

are ideal candidates for the study of environmental influences on galaxy formation and evolution since they are more fragile with respect to external disturbances.

2.2 Lynx-Cancer void

Our primary sample is drawn from the Lynx-Cancer void galaxy sample of [Pustilnik and Tepliakova \(2011\)](#). The Lynx-Cancer void is a nearby void, lying at a distance of only ~ 18 Mpc ([Pustilnik and Tepliakova, 2011](#)). The proximity of this void allows one to study the properties of faint dwarf galaxies populating the void, unlike more distant voids, where typically only the brighter dwarfs have been studied. The Lynx-Cancer void galaxy sample ([Pustilnik and Martin, 2016](#); [Pustilnik and Tepliakova, 2011](#); [Pustilnik et al., 2011, 2016](#); [Perepelitsyna et al., 2014](#)) consists of a total of 104 galaxies and is believed to be close to complete for absolute B-band magnitude ($M_B < -14$ mag ([Pustilnik and Tepliakova, 2011](#)).

The galaxies in the Lynx-Cancer void tend to have low metallicities compared to the galaxies in average density regions. Besides, this void contains a substantial fraction of faint dwarfs ($M_B > -13.5$) that have extremely high gas mass fractions and very low metallicities. Single dish HI data for these galaxies has been presented in [Pustilnik and Martin \(2016\)](#), and has been used to show that void dwarf galaxies are systematically more gas rich (as measured in terms of the ratio of HI mass to blue luminosity) than comparable luminosity galaxies lying in groups or regions of moderate density.

High resolution HI observations for a subset of these galaxies were carried out using the GMRT. We have interferometric images available for 24 galaxies, consisting of the upper quartile of gas rich galaxies (i.e. galaxies with $M_{HI}/L_B > 1.9$) based on our GMRT observations or older VLA and the WSRT observations. These high resolution HI observations have led to the discovery of several interesting systems. These include two systems (J0736+21 and U3672) that are triplets of extremely gas-rich faint dwarf galaxies with approximately linear alignment ([Chengalur and Pustilnik, 2013](#); [Chengalur et al., 2017](#)) and an interacting pair of metal poor galaxies (UGC4722) joined by a blue plume ([Chengalur et al., 2015](#)).

2.2 Lynx-Cancer void

Table 2.1: Parameters for our sample of void galaxies and their companions.

S.No	Name	RA (J2000)	Dec (J2000)	$M_{\text{HI}}/L_{\text{B}}$ (M_{\odot}/L_{\odot})	F_{HI} (Jy.km/s)	V_{sys} (km/s)	M_{B}	Telescope	Notes
1	J0626+24	06 26 20.97	+24 39 20.0	3.20	7.04	1473	-15.64	GMRT	
2	J0629+2334	06 29 58.23	+23 34 28.5	3.69	10.4	1452	-15.89	GMRT	
3	UGC3501	06 38 38.40	+49 15 30.0	2.62	3.6	449	-13.32	GMRT	
4	KKH38	06 47 54.88	+47 30 50.0	6.25	6.50	451	-12.98	GMRT	
5	UGC3672	07 06 27.56	+30 19 19.4	3.15	11.94	976	-15.54	GMRT	triplet
6	UGC3817	07 22 44.48	+45 06 30.7	2.50	10.20	437	-14.44	WSRT	
7	J0723+3621	07 23 01.42	+36 21 17.1	2.93	3.74	917	-14.19	GMRT	triplet
	J0723+3622 ^a	07 23 13.46	+36 22 13.0	11.89	1.59	970	-11.95		
	J0723+3624 ^b	07 23 20.57	+36 24 40.8	28.30	0.48	938	-9.75		
8	J0737+4724	07 37 28.47	+47 24 32.8	1.58	1.04	476	-12.50	GMRT	O/H =7.26
9	UGC3966	07 41 26.00	+40 06 44.0	4.17	25.10	351	-14.58	VLA	
10	DDO47	07 41 55.00	+16 48 02.0	7.73	64.00	272	-14.78	VLA	
	KK65 ^b	07 42 32.00	+16 33 40.0	0.53	2.5	278	-14.15	VLA	
11	UGC4115	07 57 01.80	+14 23 27.0	2.47	21.60	341	-14.75	VLA	
12	UGC4148	08 00 23.68	+42 11 37.0	2.98	12.50	716	-15.18	GMRT	
13	J0852+1350	08 52 33.75	+13 50 28.3	2.75	2.30	1511	-14.55	GMRT	
14	UGC4704	08 59 00.28	+39 12 35.7	2.56	22.40	596	-15.66	GMRT	
15	J0908+0517	09 08 36.54	+05 17 26.8	2.98	3.07	598	-12.99	GMRT	
16	J0926+3343	09 26 09.45	+33 43 04.1	3.23	2.71	536	-12.90	GMRT	O/H=7.12
17	J0929+2502	09 29 00.10	+25 02 57.0	2.38	0.36	1661	-13.16	GMRT	O/H 7.20
18	J0929+1155	09 29 51.83	+11 55 35.7	3.27	3.11	1614	-14.69	GMRT	
19	J0943+3326	09 43 32.35	+33 26 57.6	6.46	0.53	514	-10.40	VLA	O/H=7.02
	UGC5186 ^b	09 42 58.66	+33 15 56.1	0.5	1.4	551	-14.23		
20	MRK407	09 47 58.45	+39 05 10.1	4.90	2.06	1479	-13.82	GMRT	
	J0947+3908 ^b	09 47 50.25	+39 08 31.7	3.92	5.00	1553	-14.90	GMRT	
21	UGC5288	09 51 17.20	+07 49 38.0	1.96	25.30	556	-15.61	VLA	
22	J0956+2716	09 56 33.65	+27 16 59.3	1.90	1.43	1074	-13.20	GMRT	
	IC2520 ^b	09 56 20.40	+27 13 39.0	0.43	6.04	1243	-17.32		
23	UGC5340	09 56 45.70	+28 49 35.0	2.86	26.70	502	-15.90	VLA	triplet
	DDO68C ^a	09 56 41.07	+29 00 50.7	1.00	0.73	506	-13.12		
24	UGC4722C	09 00 26.11	+25 38 21.4	4.30	4.30	1837	-15.19	GMRT	merger

Notes: ^a interacting companion; ^b non-interacting companion.

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2.3 Data analysis

All the galaxies were analyzed in classic AIPS following the standard procedure for spectral line interferometric imaging at the GMRT (see e.g. Chengalur et al. (2017); Patra et al. (2016)). All the calibration and data reduction were carried out using standard tasks in the Astronomical Imaging Processing System (AIPS; Wells (1985)). The data were flagged and calibrated manually for the galaxies observed with the VLA. While, for the galaxies observed with the GMRT, flagging and calibration were done using the stand-alone pipeline "flagcal" (Prasad and Chengalur, 2012; Chengalur, 2013). In some cases, some slight additional flagging was required after passing the data through the pipeline which was done manually in AIPS. All the subsequent analysis was done using various tasks in AIPS. The GMRT does not do online doppler tracking. Hence, the CVEL task was run on all the calibrated data sets in order to correct for the Doppler shift due to earth's motion. A few galaxies were observed over multiple sessions, these were combined using the task DBCON, before imaging. The calibrated visibilities were converted to images using the task IMAGR. A trial data cube was made in order to identify the line free channels. Following this, a continuum image was made using the line-free channels and the corresponding clean components subtracted from the UV data by using the task UVSUB. Any residual continuum was subtracted in the image plane using the task IMAGR.

The hybrid configuration of the GMRT (Swarup et al., 1991) allows us to make both high and low angular resolution images from a single observation. Hence, for the galaxies observed with the GMRT, data cubes were made at various (u,v) ranges, viz. 0-5 k λ , 0-10 k λ , 0-20 k λ and 0-30 k λ corresponding to $\sim 40''$, $25''$, $15''$ and $10''$. Single resolution data cubes were made for the galaxies observed with the VLA, where the resolution of the cube depends on the array configuration of the VLA used for the observations. The data cubes were made using the task IMAGR. Moment maps were made from the data cubes using the task MOMNT. The MOMNT task can be used to create a mask to blank the images at a given cutoff level. This mask was created by convolving the original cube with a Gaussian smoothing kernel which has a dimension of roughly the clean beam size. A Hanning smoothing kernel with a width of 3 velocity channels was also applied, after which pixels below 2σ (where the σ corresponds to the rms in original unsmoothed data cube) were blanked out. Spectra were made by using

task 'BLSUM' in AIPS. Integrated flux for each galaxy was measured by using SoFiA software. The interferometric fluxes are broadly consistent with the single dish fluxes, with the interferometric fluxes in general tending to be less than the single dish fluxes, (but mostly within approximately 2σ of the combined errors). For a couple of cases, e.g. KKH38 and J0943+332, the interferometric fluxes are significantly smaller than the single dish fluxes. The reason for this is not clear. Further investigation is required to resolve the discrepancies.

2.4 HI morphologies

We show the total intensity maps and velocity fields for the target galaxies in figures 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 2.6, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10, and 2.11. We have detected HI in all the 24 targeted galaxies. The parameters of these 24 galaxies and their companions are listed in Table 2.1. The columns are as follows: (1) S.No. (2) galaxy name, (3) RA in hours, minutes, seconds, (4) declination in degrees, minutes, seconds, (5) mass to light ratio, (6) flux from the single dish observations in Jy km s^{-1} , (7) absolute B-band magnitude (8) telescope used for the HI observations, and (9) notes on the galaxy, We have noted the metallicity O/H values for metal poor galaxies and we have also noted when the galaxy is in a triplet or is a merger remnant.

Many of the observed target galaxies (such as J0626+24, J0630+23, UGC3501, KKH38, UGC3817, J0737+4724, U3966, UGC4115, UGC4148, UGC4704, J0926+3343, J0929+1155) have regular disk-like rotation and smooth velocity fields. However, a fraction of them also show disturbed gas morphology and kinematics. Some of the galaxies have HI rings (e.g. J0630+23, UGC5288) and extended discs (e.g. UGC5288, DDO47, J0929+1155, and UGC4148). Three of these galaxies (J0723+3621, UGC3672, UGC5340) are in triplets and one of them (UGC4722) is a merger remnant. Five of these galaxies have a non-interacting companion. Total intensity maps and velocity fields for the companion galaxies are shown in in figure 2.12.

2.4.1 Notes on individual systems

J0723+3621 is a triplet of extremely gas-rich galaxies located near the centre of void. The triplet members J0723+3621 ($M_B = -14.2$), J0723+3622 ($M_B = -11.9$), and J0723+3624 ($M_B = -9.7$) have HI mass to blue luminosity ($M(\text{HI})/L_B$) ratios of \sim

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(a) Left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $16.09'' \times 13.53''$ on the PanSTARRS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy J0626+24. The HI contours start at a column density $1.0 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Right: velocity field for the galaxy J0626+24. Velocity contours run from 1430 to 1550 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 10 km s^{-1} .

(b) Left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $23.40'' \times 16.74''$ on the PanSTARRS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy J0630+23. The HI contours start at a column density $5.0 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Right: velocity field for the galaxy J0630+23. Velocity contours run from 1380 to 1510 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 10 km s^{-1} .

Figure 2.1: Moment maps of the galaxies, J0626+24 and J0630+23

(a) Left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $7.45'' \times 10.22''$ on the MZLS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy UGC3501. The HI contours start at a column density $2.9 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Right: velocity field for the galaxy UGC3501. Velocity contours run from 424 to 468 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 4 km s^{-1} .

(b) Left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $43.92'' \times 32.4''$ on the DECaLS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy KKH38. The HI contours start at a column density $1.5 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Right: velocity field for the galaxy KKH38. Velocity contours run from 425 to 480 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 5 km s^{-1} .

Figure 2.2: Moment maps of the galaxies, UGC 3501 and KKH38.

2. VOID GALAXIES

(a) Left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $41.04'' \times 40.32''$ on the DECaLS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy UGC3672. The HI contours start at a column density $1.4 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Right: velocity field for the galaxy UGC3672. Velocity contours run from 985 to 1085 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 10 km s^{-1} .

(b) Left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $26.21'' \times 20.05''$ on the MZLS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy UGC3817. The HI contours start at a column density $4.3 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Right: velocity field for the galaxy UGC 3817. Velocity contours run from 420 to 455 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 5 km s^{-1} .

Figure 2.3: Moment maps of the galaxies, UGC3672 and UGC3817.

(a) Left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $40.32'' \times 39.24''$ on the PanSTARRS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy J0723+3621. The HI contours start at a column density $1.4 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Right: velocity field for the galaxy J0723+3621. Velocity contours run from 865 to 990 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 5 km s^{-1} .

(b) Left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $9.36'' \times 7.92''$ on the SDSS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy J0737+4724. The HI contours start at a column density $3.0 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Right: velocity field for the galaxy J0737+4724. Velocity contours run from 455 to 490 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 5 km s^{-1} .

Figure 2.4: Moment maps of the galaxies, J0723+3621 and J0737+4724.

2. VOID GALAXIES

(a) Left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $17.74'' \times 15.94''$ on the MZLS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy UGC3966. The HI contours start at a column density $7.9 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Right: velocity field for the galaxy UGC3966. Velocity contours run from 325 to 395 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 5 km s^{-1} .

(b) Left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $39.24'' \times 36.36''$ on the SDSS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy DDO47. The HI contours start at a column density $1.5 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Right: velocity field for the galaxy DDO47. Velocity contours run from 240 to 310 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 5 km s^{-1} .

Figure 2.5: Moment maps of the galaxies, UGC3966 and DDO47.

(a) Left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $14.76'' \times 14.04''$ on the SDSS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy UGC4115. The HI contours start at a column density $1.0 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Right: velocity field for the galaxy UGC4115. Velocity contours run from 290 to 390 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 10 km s^{-1} .

(b) Left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $12.96'' \times 7.92''$ on the SDSS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy UGC4148. The HI contours start at a column density $2.2 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Right: velocity field for the galaxy UGC4148. Velocity contours run from 700 to 820 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 10 km s^{-1} .

Figure 2.6: Moment maps of the galaxies, UGC4115 and UGC4148.

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(a) Left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $42.84'' \times 37.08''$ on the SDSS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy J0852+1350. The HI contours start at a column density $1.4 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Right: velocity field for the galaxy J0852+1350. Velocity contours run from 1528 to 1568 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 5 km s^{-1} .

(b) Left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $8.46'' \times 7.45''$ on the MZLS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy UGC4704. The HI contours start at a column density $3.5 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Right: velocity field for the galaxy UGC4704. Velocity contours run from 540 to 652 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 7 km s^{-1} .

Figure 2.7: Moment maps of the galaxies, J0852+1350 and UGC4704.

(a) Left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $41.4'' \times 37.4''$ on the SDSS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy J0908+0517. The HI contours start at a column density $1.5 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Right: velocity field for the galaxy J0908+0517. Velocity contours run from 594 to 600 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 2 km s^{-1} .

(b) Left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $20.52'' \times 12.96''$ on the SDSS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy J0926+3343. The HI contours start at a column density $8.4 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Right: velocity field for the galaxy J0926+3343. Velocity contours run from 505 to 565 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 5 km s^{-1} .

Figure 2.8: Moment maps of the galaxies, J0908+0517 and J0926+3343.

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(a) Left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $23.5'' \times 16.6''$ on the PanSTARRS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy J0929+2502. The HI contours start at a column density $5.8 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Right: velocity field for the galaxy J0929+2502. Velocity contours run from 1654 to 1682 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 3 km s^{-1} .

(b) Left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $17.64'' \times 16.56''$ on the PanSTARRS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy J0929+1155. The HI contours start at a column density $7.7 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Right: velocity field for the galaxy J0929+1155. Velocity contours run from 1560 to 1680 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 10 km s^{-1} .

Figure 2.9: Moment maps of the galaxies, J0929+2502 and J0929+1155.

(a) Left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $51.84'' \times 38.52''$ on the PanSTARRS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy J0943+3326. The HI contours start at a column density $1.1 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Right: velocity field for the galaxy J0943+3326. Velocity contours run from 513 to 517 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 1 km s^{-1} .

(b) Left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $10.47'' \times 7.7''$ on the DECaLS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy MRK407. The HI contours start at a column density $2.8 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Right: velocity field for the galaxy MRK407. Velocity contours run from 1500 to 1675 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 15 km s^{-1} .

Figure 2.10: Moment maps of the galaxies, J0943+3326 and MRK407.

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(a) Left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission at a resolution $18.72'' \times 16.92''$ on the DECaLS optical image of the galaxy UGC5288. The HI contours start at a column density $7.15 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. Right: velocity field for the galaxy UGC5288. Velocity contours run from 516 to 596 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 8 km s^{-1} .

(b) Left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission at a resolution $26.21'' \times 20.05''$ on the SDSS optical image of the galaxy J0956+2713. The HI contours start at a column density $4.3 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. Right: velocity field for the galaxy J0956+2713. Velocity contours run from 1025 to 1225 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 10 km s^{-1} .

(c) Left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission at a resolution $16.5'' \times 16.2''$ on the DECaLS optical image of the galaxy UGC5340. The HI contours start at a column density $8.4 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. Right: velocity field for the galaxy UGC5340. Velocity contours run from 460 to 540 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 5 km s^{-1} .

Figure 2.11: Moment maps of the galaxies, U5288, J0956+2716 and UGC5340.

2.9, 10, and 25 respectively. The faintest member is one of the most gas-rich galaxies known. Galaxies, J0723+3621 and J0723+3622 are connected by HI bridge while the faintest one, J0723+3624 is not interacting with them. They lie in approximately linear alignment within 25 kpc and a radial velocity interval of $\sim 55 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (Chengalur and Pustilnik, 2013).

UGC5340, a very metal poor galaxy is again a triplet in which two more massive components are already merged. The third, much fainter component is at distance of $\sim 42 \text{ kpc}$ with the same systemic velocity is connected to the primary galaxy by a low surface brightness HI bridge (Ekta et al., 2008; Cannon et al., 2014).

UGC3672 consists of an approximately linearly aligned triplet of gas rich dwarfs with large scale velocity continuity. It lies in the central 8% of the volume that has ~ 10 times lower density than the mean density. At low spatial resolution, HI distribution and kinematics is similar to typical dwarf galaxies. However at higher resolutions, the the HI distribution is confined to several tidal tails and bridges (Chengalur et al., 2017).

UGC5288 has an extremely extended, low-density, HI disc. It has a well ordered, slightly warped disk. The optical morphology of the galaxy suggests a bar (van Zee, 2004). Majority of the HI is beyond optical disk, with its HI extending 5 times that of the optical disk.

DDO47 has an extended HI disk, where HI extends 4.5 times that of the optical disk. It has a non-interacting companion at a projected distance of 40.6 kpc within 10 km s^{-1} .

IC2520 has a tail in the north direction and a disturbed velocity field. We have also detected another galaxy at a distance of 29.5 kpc within 170 km s^{-1} .

MRK407 has a tidal tail in the west direction and it has a non interacting companion at a distance of 27.75 kpc within 74 km s^{-1} .

J0943+3326 is a metal poor ($\text{O}/\text{H} \sim 7.12$) galaxy (McQuinn et al., 2020). It has a non-interacting companion (UGC5186) at a distance of 31.6kpc and within 37 km s^{-1} (Begum et al., 2008).

2.5 Kinematics

The HI observations of void galaxies can be used to explore their kinematics and to study their angular momentum and dark matter distribution.

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Figure 2.12: Companions to J0723+3621, DDO47, J0943+3326, MRK407, IC2520, and UGC5340 respectively in the order of top to bottom. Synthesis beam and HI column density contours are the same as those of target galaxies.

2.5.1 Tilted ring model

The kinematics of gas rich disc galaxies have traditionally been modelled using the “Tilted Ring Model” (Rogstad et al., 1974) where the gas disc is divided into a number of annuli, each of which is assumed to be in circular motion. This modelling yields the “rotation curve”, i.e. the variation of the rotation velocity with radius (see §1.4.1 of chapter 1 for more details). Most of the earlier modelling software available for determining rotation curves (e.g., ROTCUR in the GIPSY package (van der Hulst et al., 1992)), works on the 2D velocity field (i.e. a “2-D” approach) determined from the 3D data cube (i.e with RA, DEC and velocity as axes). Velocity fields determined in this way could suffer from systematic problems, such as a flattening of the velocity gradient in the central part of the galaxy because of the finite resolution of the observations (the so called “beam smearing” problem). These problems become more pronounced as the number of resolution elements across the galaxy decreases and the inclination of the galaxy disc increases. Recently, there have been several software packages developed that determine the rotation curves by directly fitting the tilted ring model to the full 3D data cube (i.e. a “3-D” approach).

In this thesis, we use both of these approaches to derive rotation curves for our sample galaxies. We derive the rotation curves by fitting a tilted ring model to the intensity weighted first moment map or a velocity field determined by Gauss–Hermite polynomial profile fitting using the ‘ROTCUR’ task from the software package (van der Hulst et al., 1992). We also derive the rotation curves by fitting the tilted ring model to the HI data cube using the pipeline (v5.0.2, Kamphuis et al., 2015). We fit flat discs, where all parameters except the surface brightness and the rotational velocity of each ring have the same value at all radii.

2.5.2 Sample for kinematic studies

For the studies of dark matter distribution and angular momentum, we require a sample where rotation curves can be reliably derived. Therefore, we have an additional set of selection criteria for the sample. We have considered only galaxies that have well-behaved velocity fields, are well resolved across the major axis (more than ~ 6 beams). We exclude the galaxies that have disturbed velocity fields or have inclinations lower than 35° . 10 of 24 dwarf galaxies remain after imposition of these criteria. We also

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include the galaxy KK246 (Begum et al., 2008; Kreckel et al., 2011b), residing in the nearby Tully void, in our sample.

2.5.3 Derivation of rotation curves

We first used the FAT pipeline (Kamphuis et al., 2015) to fit tilted ring models to the HI data cubes for our sample galaxies. The FAT pipeline is a wrapper around TIRIFIC (Józsa et al., 2007) and it also uses SOFIA (The Source Finding Application is a HI source finding pipeline used for finding and parameterizing the galaxies in HI data cubes (Serra et al., 2015)) to obtain estimates of the initial parameters for the rings. The errors reported by FAT are empirical estimates determined by taking the maximum of the difference between the unsmoothed and the smoothed profile, the variation of the smoothed profiles in the Monte Carlo fitting process and a minimum default value. In case of the rotation curve, this minimum value is set as the maximum of 5 km s^{-1} or $0.5 \times dv / \sqrt{\sin(i)}$, where dv is the velocity resolution and i is the inclination (see Kamphuis et al. (2015) for more details on error determination).

We also used the task ROTCUR from the GIPSY software package (van der Hulst et al., 1992) to fit tilted ring models to the 2-D velocity fields. The initial estimates for parameters such as the inclination, position angle and systemic velocity were taken from the FAT output. We also used the DUCHAMP software package (designed to find and describe sources in 3-D spectral cubes; Whiting (2012)) to estimate the position angle and systemic velocity, the systematic velocity was also estimated from the synthetic global profile. We found that the systemic velocities estimated from FAT, DUCHAMP and the global profile match within $\pm 3 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. The inclinations obtained from FAT are generally within $\pm 10^\circ$ compared with optical inclinations (estimated assuming an intrinsic thickness $q_0=0.4$ (Roychowdhury et al., 2013)). The reasonableness of this choice of intrinsic thickness is confirmed by the fact that the inclinations obtained via fitting of the velocity fields match those obtained from the optical morphology. The centre of the galaxy was initially estimated as the centre of symmetry of the HI moment 0 map. In defining the radii and widths of the rings we sample the rotation curve at a rate of two points per synthesized beam width. None of the geometric or orientation parameters were found to have a significant variation with radius. The final rotation curve was derived after fixing all the parameters except for rotation velocity. For the GMRT data cubes, this process was repeated for the different resolution data sets, to

Figure 2.13: Rotation curves of galaxies, where rotation curves from FAT pipeline match with that of the ROTCUR software.

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Figure 2.14: Rotation curves of 3 galaxies, where rotation curves derived from FAT are not in agreement with those derived from Rotcur.

derive rotation curves at various resolutions. Finally, a hybrid rotation curve was made by combining the different rotation curves for a given galaxy. Rotation curves were also derived at all resolutions using the approaching and receding halves of the galaxy independently. The errors on the rotation curve were taken as the quadrature of the errors reported by the tilted ring model fitting routines and the difference between the rotation velocities of the approaching and receding sides of the galaxy.

The rotation curves derived using both the FAT and ROTCUR are shown figures 2.13 and 2.14. The rotation curve obtained using ROTCUR is shown with black circles and a black dotted line and the rotation curve from the FAT pipeline is shown with red diamonds and a red solid line. Fig. 2.13 shows the rotation curves of 8 galaxies, where the rotation curves derived with the FAT are generally in excellent agreement with that of the rotation curves derived with the 'ROTCUR'. The main difference is that, as expected, the inner parts of rotation curves derived using FAT are typically steeper than those derived using ROTCUR. To test whether the FAT model is a good fit to the observed data, and that the differences that we see in the curves arise because of the systematic differences between the 2D and 3D approaches, we derive moment maps from the best fit model data cube produced by FAT and derive rotation curves using ROTCUR. This comparison between data and models is discussed in detail in 3.4.4 of chapter 3. Fig. 2.14 shows the rotation curves of 3 galaxies (J0737+4724, UGC 3501 and DDO47), where the rotation curves derived using the FAT pipeline do not match to the rotation curves derived using the ROTCUR in the inner regions. This is probably because for all three galaxies the central HI density distribution is clumpy. FAT assumes a symmetric density distribution, and the clumpiness in the observed density made the central parts of the FAT rotation unreliable, as confirmed

by the large errors reported by FAT. While it is possible to model asymmetric density distributions using TIRIFC, we have not attempted that here.

We use the FAT rotation curves for construction of mass models since they are expected to be less affected by projection effects such as beam smearing. For studies of dark matter distribution, we exclude the 3 galaxies, where FAT rotation curves were unreliable in the central regions. We use the rotation curves derived for all the 11 galaxies for the estimation of angular momentum studies since the systematic difference that is seen in the inner regions of the rotation curve will have negligible effect on the total angular momentum (which is dominated by the outer parts of the disc).

2.6 Summary

We have presented HI imaging and kinematics of 24 void galaxies and their companions. This survey has led to the discovery of several interesting systems that show signs of interaction and gas accretion. Three of 24 galaxies are in triplets. These include, (i) J0723+36, a triplet of extremely gas-rich dwarf galaxies in approximately linear alignment, (ii) UGC3672, consists of an approximately linearly aligned triplet of gas-rich dwarfs, and (iii) UGC5340, a metal poor galaxy is a void triplet in which two massive components are already merged and the third component is connected to the primary galaxy by a low surface brightness HI bridge. In addition to these, [Beygu et al. \(2013\)](#) found a system of three interacting galaxies embedded in a common HI envelope inside a large void. These linearly aligned triplets are suggestive of ongoing growth of galaxies out of a filament. One of the 24 galaxies, UGC4722 is a merger remnant. It consists of an interacting pair of metal poor galaxies that are connected by young stars. Our sample also contains an extremely extended HI disc, i.e. UGC5288, which shows signs of accretion. We have detected six neighboring galaxies, all but one of the neighboring galaxy (i.e IC2520) appear to be companions to the target galaxy, i.e. they are within 100 kpc and 100 km s⁻¹.

We have selected a sub-sample of 11 galaxies for which rotation curves can be reliably derived. We derive the rotation curves by fitting the tilted ring model to the intensity weighted first moment map (2-D, ROTCUR) and by fitting the tilted ring model directly to the HI data cube (3-D, FAT). The FAT and ROTCUR derived rotation curves are in broad agreement for 8 of the 11 galaxies. The main difference is

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that the inner parts of the rotation curves derived using FAT are steeper than those derived using ROTCUR. For the remaining 3 galaxies, the rotation curves derived using the FAT pipeline are unreliable in the central regions.

We use these rotation curves to estimate the angular momentum and dark matter distribution of galaxies. We use the rotation curves derived for all the 11 galaxies for the estimation of angular momentum studies since the systematic difference that is seen in the inner regions of the rotation curve will have negligible effect on the total angular momentum (which is dominated by the outer parts of the disc). We use FAT rotation curves for studies of dark matter distribution since they are expected to be less affected by projection effects such as beam smearing, but also compare with dark matter distribution derived using ROTCUR rotation curves . Hence, we exclude 3 galaxies for construction of mass models since their FAT derived rotation curves were unreliable in the central regions. Mass modeling of the remaining 8 galaxies is presented in the next chapter, chapter 3.

3

Mass models of void dwarf galaxies

The following text is based on Sushma Kurapati, Jayaram N. Chengalur, Peter Kamphuis, Simon Pustilnik, 2020, MNRAS, 491, 4993.

3.1 Introduction

The standard Λ Cold Dark Matter (Λ CDM) paradigm has been remarkably successful at large scales, with predictions from Λ CDM numerical simulations providing an excellent match to observational data (e.g. [Planck Collaboration et al., 2014](#); [Springel et al., 2006](#); [Clowe et al., 2006](#); [Dawson et al., 2013](#); [Baur et al., 2016](#)). However, discrepancies between Λ CDM predictions and the observations remain at smaller scales, (see [Bullock and Boylan-Kolchin, 2017](#), for a review). One of the earliest noticed, as well as most studied, of these is the so called “cusp-core problem”, where observations of isolated dwarf and low surface brightness galaxies (i.e. galaxies for which observations are expected to be least affected by systematic errors arising from non circular motions and uncertainties in the stellar mass to light ratio) typically find that the dark matter halo has a constant density core towards the centre, while Λ CDM models predict a cuspy density profile (e.g. [de Blok, 2010](#); [Oh et al., 2011b](#); [Ogiya et al., 2014](#); [Ogiya and Mori, 2014](#); [Ogiya and Burkert, 2015](#)).

In detail, Λ CDM simulations which do not include baryonic physics predict that dark matter halos of all masses have a universal density profile with the density distri-

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bution in the inner regions following a power law $\rho \sim r^\alpha$ with slope $\alpha = -1$ (Navarro et al., 1996; Navarro and Steinmetz, 1997). Steeper slopes $\alpha = -1.5$ were found by Moore et al. (1998, 1999), and more recent simulations find that the inner slope shows some variation and mass dependence with $\alpha = -(0.8 - 1.4)$ (Ricotti, 2003; Ricotti et al., 2007; Del Popolo, 2010, 2012; Di Cintio et al., 2014). For smaller galaxies the slope is found to decrease towards the center reaching $\alpha = -0.8$ at ~ 100 pc from the centre (Stadel et al., 2009; Navarro et al., 2010; Del Popolo, 2011). In contrast however, observations of dwarf and low-surface brightness (LSB) galaxies indicate a flat ($\alpha \approx -0.2$) dark matter density core (e.g. Oh et al., 2015; de Blok et al., 2001; de Blok and Bosma, 2002a; Oh et al., 2011b). Some observational studies (Simon et al., 2005; Adams et al., 2014) find intermediate slopes, i.e. steeper than would be expected from a constant density core, but still significantly shallower than the slopes predicted by simulations.

Various solutions have been proposed to resolve the cusp-core problem; these broadly fall into three categories. The first set of solutions propose that the dark matter could be warm or weakly self interacting, this would erase the cusps that arise in pure Λ CDM (e.g. Spergel and Steinhardt, 2000; Rocha et al., 2013; Elbert et al., 2015; Kaplinghat et al., 2016; Schneider et al., 2017). The second category of solutions invokes baryonic processes to generate cores from an originally cuspy distribution. Basically, repeated gas outflows resulting from supernova explosions from star formation concentrated at the galaxy centre result in a re-distribution of the baryonic as well as dark matter (see e.g. Pontzen and Governato, 2012; Governato et al., 2012; Pontzen and Governato, 2014; Read et al., 2016a). However, some simulations find that the density profile of the dark matter is consistent with cuspy profiles even after including baryonic outflows (Marinacci et al., 2014; Ceverino and Klypin, 2009; Schaller et al., 2015). The third category of solutions suggest that there are residual systematic problems in determining and modelling the rotation curves of galaxies, and these problems could result in a mis-identification of cores as cusps (e.g. van den Bosch et al., 2000; Swaters et al., 2003; Hayashi et al., 2004; Oman et al., 2017; Pineda et al., 2017). These residual systematic effects include smoothing of the rotation curve because of the finite resolution of the observations (van den Bosch et al., 2000), incorrectly measured inclination angles (e.g. Rhee et al., 2004; Read et al., 2016b), improperly modelled pressure support (e.g. Pineda et al., 2017; Rhee et al., 2004; Valenzuela et al., 2007) or unmodelled non-circular motions (e.g. Oman et al., 2017; Rhee et al., 2004; Valenzuela et al.,

2007). All of these can lower the inner rotation velocities and mask the cuspy distributions. More recently, Pineda et al. (2017) studied systematic effects in observational studies using high-resolution hydrodynamic simulations of dwarf galaxies. They mimic realistic kinematic observations and fit the mock rotation curves with Navarro-Frenk-White (NFW) and isothermal haloes, and they find that the cored isothermal halos are favoured in spite of the fact that their simulations contain NFW halos.

Traditionally, the HI rotation curves used in mass modelling were derived from the 2-D velocity fields (e.g. Oh et al., 2015; de Blok and Bosma, 2002b; Oh et al., 2011b). Recently there have been several software packages developed that determine the rotation curves by directly modelling the full 3D data cube, including modelling of instrumental effects such as beam smearing. Rotation curves derived in this way would be expected not to suffer from the flattening associated with beam smearing, and as such better trace the underlying circular velocities. In this work, we derive the rotation curves by using both the 3D and 2D tilted ring fitting routines. We compare the properties of dark matter halos that were obtained using the rotation curves derived using both the approaches.

In addition, all the galaxies in our sample lie in voids. The dark matter distribution of void galaxies is also of interest by itself. There are at least two possible reasons why void galaxies may have different dark matter halo properties than galaxies in higher density regions. The first is that the large scale environment is expected to correlate with the properties of individual galaxy halos. Simulations find that, for halo masses $< 5 \times 10^{11} h^{-1} M_{\odot}$, halos in cluster regions are on average $\sim 30 - 40$ % more concentrated and have ~ 2 times higher central densities than halos in voids (Avila-Reese et al., 2005). Secondly, in models where the distribution of dark matter in central regions of the galaxy is driven by stellar feedback processes (e.g. Pontzen and Governato, 2012; Governato et al., 2012), void galaxies, with their typically higher star formation rates (Moorman et al., 2016) could be more affected by such baryonic processes as compared to galaxies in high density regions.

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Figure 3.1: HI data and kinematics for the galaxy KK246. Top left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $15.84'' \times 12.96''$ on the SDSS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy KK246. The HI contours start at a column density $1.1 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$, Top right: Position velocity diagram with the rotation curves overlaid on them. Bottom left: velocity field of data, and Bottom right: velocity field of the best fitting FAT model. Velocity contours run from 380 to 470 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 10 km s^{-1}

Figure 3.2: HI data and kinematics for the galaxy U4115. Top left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $14.76'' \times 14.04''$ on the SDSS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy UGC4115. The HI contours start at a column density $1.0 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. Top right: Position velocity diagram with the rotation curves overlaid on them. Bottom left: velocity field of data, and Bottom right: velocity field of the best fitting FAT model. velocity contours run from 290 to 390 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 10 km s^{-1}

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Figure 3.3: HI data and kinematics for the galaxy J0926+3343. Top left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $20.52'' \times 12.96''$ on the SDSS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy J0926+3343. The HI contours start at a column density $8.4 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$, Top right: Position velocity diagram with the rotation curves overlaid on them. Bottom left: velocity field of data, and Bottom right: velocity field of the best fitting FAT model. velocity contours run from 505 to 565 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 5 km s^{-1}

Figure 3.4: HI data and kinematics for the galaxy U5288. Top left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission at a resolution $18.72'' \times 16.92''$ on the DECaLS optical image of the galaxy UGC5288. The HI contours start at a column density $7.15 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$, Top right: Position velocity diagram with the rotation curves overlaid on them. Bottom left: velocity field of data, and Bottom right: velocity field of the best fitting FAT model. velocity contours run from 516 to 596 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 8 km s^{-1}

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Figure 3.5: HI data and kinematics for the galaxy U4148. Top left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $12.96'' \times 7.92''$ on the SDSS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy UGC4148. The HI contours start at a column density $2.2 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$, Top right: Position velocity diagram with the rotation curves overlaid on them. Bottom left: velocity field of data, and Bottom right: velocity field of the best fitting FAT model. velocity contours run from 700 to 820 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 10 km s^{-1}

Figure 3.6: HI data and kinematics for the galaxy J0630+23. Top left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $23.40'' \times 16.74''$ on the PanSTARRS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy J0630+23. The HI contours start at a column density $5.0 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. Top right: Position velocity diagram with the rotation curves overlaid on them. Bottom left: velocity field of data, and Bottom right: velocity field of the best fitting FAT model. velocity contours run from 1380 to 1510 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 10 km s^{-1}

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Figure 3.7: HI data and kinematics for the galaxy J0626+24. Top left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $16.09'' \times 13.53''$ on the PanSTARRS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy J0626+24. The HI contours start at a column density $1.0 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$, Top right: Position velocity diagram with the rotation curves overlaid on them. Bottom left: velocity field of data, and Bottom right: velocity field of the best fitting FAT model. velocity contours run from 1430 to 1560 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 10 km s^{-1}

Figure 3.8: HI data and kinematics for the galaxy J0929+1155. Top left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $17.64'' \times 16.56''$ on the PanSTARRS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy J0929+1155. The HI contours start at a column density $7.7 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. Top right: Position velocity diagram with the rotation curves overlaid on them. Bottom left: velocity field of data, and Bottom right: velocity field of the best fitting FAT model. velocity contours run from 1560 to 1680 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 10 km s^{-1}

3.2 Kinematic analysis

3.2.1 Rotation curves

The sample selection, the data reduction, and the derivation of rotation curves are discussed in detail in 2.2, 2.3, and 2.5 of chapter 2. We derive the rotation curves by using both the 3D and 2D tilted ring fitting routines. We use FAT (v5.0.2, Kamphuis et al., 2015) to fit a tilted ring model to the data cube (i.e. a “3-D” approach) and the ‘ROTCUR’ task from the GIPSY software package (van der Hulst et al., 1992) to fit a tilted ring model to the velocity field (i.e. a “2-D” approach). We fit flat discs, where all parameters except the surface brightness and the rotational velocity of each ring have the same value at all radii. Our data do not show obvious signatures of warps. The FAT and ROTCUR derived rotation curves (shown in Fig 2.13 of chapter 2) are in broad agreement for 8 of the 11 galaxies. The main difference is that the inner parts of the rotation curves derived using FAT are steeper than those derived using ROTCUR. This is likely due to the fact that FAT models the effect of the finite resolution and is hence expected to be less affected by effects such as “beam smearing”. For the remaining 3 galaxies (shown in Fig 2.14 of chapter 2), the rotation curves derived using the FAT pipeline were unreliable in the central regions probably due to their clumpy HI distribution. Hence, we exclude these 3 galaxies for the construction of the mass models. The optical and kinematic parameters (as derived from the FAT) for the selected 8 galaxies are listed in Table 3.1. The columns are as follows. column (1): galaxy name, (2): distance to the galaxy in Mpc, (3): absolute B-band magnitude (corrected for Galactic extinction using extinction values from NED), (4): HI mass ($\times 10^7 M_{\odot}$), and (5): inclination angle in degrees, (6): velocity dispersion in km s^{-1} and (7): maximum rotation velocity in km s^{-1} as derived from the FAT .

In Figures 3.1–3.4, we show (i) the integrated HI intensity map contours overlaid on the optical image, (ii) Position-velocity diagram taken along the major axis of the galaxy with the rotation curves overlaid on them. The dashed lines indicate the systemic velocity and kinematic center. The overplotted green diamonds represent the rotation curve derived by FAT (3D approach) and violet triangles represent the rotation curve derived by ‘ROTCUR’ (2D approach) (iii) the intensity weighted first moment of the galaxy, and (iv) velocity field of the best fitting FAT model.

3.2 Kinematic analysis

Figure 3.9: The rotation curves as derived by FAT before and after the correction for pressure support. The red diamonds and black circles indicate the derived rotation curve from the FAT and the rotation curve after correcting for the pressure support.

3. MASS MODELS OF VOID DWARF GALAXIES

Table 3.1: Parameters of galaxies selected for this study

Name	d (Mpc)	M_B	M_{HI} ($10^7 M_\odot$)	i^a	σ^b	V_{max}^b
KK246 ^c	6.85	-13.69	9.0	62	10.9	42.0
UGC4115	7.73	-14.75	31.9	55	13.6	56.5
J0926+3343	10.6	-12.90	5.2	69	11.5	31.5
UGC5288	11.4	-15.61	90.2	38	9.1	72.4
UGC4148	13.5	-15.18	78.4	83	8.4	63.9
J0630+23	22.9	-15.89	135.1	51	10.9	80.2
J0626+24	23.2	-15.64	63.8	62	10.2	80.3
J0929+1155	24.3	-14.69	36.6	72	9.1	62.3

^a The inclination angle (i) is in degrees,

^b Velocity dispersion (σ), maximum velocity (V_{max}) are in km s^{-1}

^c The M_B and d values for KK246 are from [Kreckel et al. \(2011a\)](#).

3.2.2 Correction for pressure support

The observed rotation velocities are usually smaller than the true circular velocities, as the random gas motions in the gaseous disk provide “pressure support” to the disk. This effect is particularly significant in dwarf galaxies whose velocity dispersions are comparable to the maximum rotation velocity. In order to construct the mass models, the observed rotation velocities have to be corrected for the pressure support (e.g. [Meurer et al., 1996](#); [Begum and Chengalur, 2004](#)). This correction is given by:

$$v_c^2 = v_o^2 - r \times \sigma^2 \left[\frac{d}{dr}(\ln \Sigma_{HI}) + \frac{d}{dr}(\ln \sigma^2) - \frac{d}{dr}(\ln 2h_z) \right] \quad (3.1)$$

where, v_c is the corrected velocity, v_o is the observed rotation velocity, Σ_{HI} is the HI surface density, σ is the velocity dispersion and h_z is the scale height of the disc. We assume that the scale height doesn’t vary with radius and that the velocity dispersion is constant across the galaxy (but have also checked that it doesn’t make a significant difference by assuming a linear gradient in both velocity dispersion and scale height - see below). Under the assumption of a constant scale height and velocity dispersion the pressure correction simplifies to:

$$v_c^2 = v_o^2 - r \times \sigma^2 \left[\frac{d}{dr}(\ln \Sigma_{HI}) \right] \quad (3.2)$$

We use parametric fits to the de-projected radial surface density profiles (themselves obtained using task ‘ELLINT’ in GIPSY software) to determine the pressure support correction. For most of the galaxies, either a Gaussian or double Gaussian profile fits best to the radial surface density distribution, An exponential profile fits best for the case of KK246. For the velocity dispersion, we use the values determined from the data cubes by the FAT pipeline.

In Figure 3.9, we show the rotation curves of all the galaxies as derived by FAT before and after the correction for pressure support. The red diamonds indicate the derived rotation curve from the FAT software and the black circles show the rotation curve after correcting for the pressure support. For all the galaxies, we find that the corrections are usually small in the inner regions, but are significant in the outer regions except for J0926+3343, which has the smallest angular diameter. We have also checked the corrections assuming a linear gradient in both scale height and velocity dispersion (6–12 km s⁻¹), and the result that the corrections are not significant at the inner radii is unchanged.

3.3 Mass models

The circular velocity reflects the gravitational potential of total matter content of galaxy which includes stars, gas and dark matter. We use the HI and optical de-projected radial surface brightness profiles and subtract the dynamical contribution of the atomic gas and stars in order to constrain the dark matter distribution. The derivation of the gas and stellar surface densities are described in §3.3.1 and §3.3.2. In §3.3.4, we discuss various different assumptions regarding the stellar mass to luminosity ratio, and the effect they have on the derived dark matter distribution. We assume that the contribution of the molecular gas is negligible since for faint dwarf galaxies such as those in our sample, the molecular fraction is believed to be low (e.g. Taylor et al., 1998; Schrubba et al., 2012; Cormier et al., 2014). The contribution of the ionized gas is also expected to be small and has been neglected. The HI gas and stars hence form the dominant baryonic component of the galaxy. In §3.3.3 below, we describe the different dark matter models that were used for the construction of mass models. Once the form of contribution of each of these components was determined, mass models were fit to the pressure support corrected rotation curves using ‘ROTMAS’ task in

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Figure 3.10: Left panels: Mass models for J0626+24, J0929+1155 and KK246. The open circles indicate the total observed velocities after the correction for pressure support. The blue filled circles indicate the velocity contribution of the dark matter halo (after subtracting the contribution of baryons). The red dashed line and the green solid line represent the best fit NFW model and the best fit ISO model. The blue dotted line and the brown dashed line represent the gas and stars respectively. The residual velocities from best-fit ISO and NFW model are shown by the green filled circles and the red open circles. Right panels: The mass density profiles of J0626+24, J0929+1155 and KK246. The black dotted line indicates the data points used for the estimation of inner density slope.

Figure 3.11: Left panels: Mass models for UGC4148, J0630+23 and UGC5288. The open circles indicate the total observed velocities after the correction for pressure support. The blue filled circles indicate the velocity contribution of the dark matter halo (after subtracting the contribution of baryons). The red dashed line and the green solid line represent the best fit NFW model and the best fit ISO model. The blue dotted line and the brown dashed line represent the gas and stars respectively. The residual velocities from best-fit ISO and NFW model are shown by the green filled circles and the red open circles. Right panels: The mass density profiles of UGC4148, J0630+23 and UGC5288. The black dotted line indicates the data points used for the estimation of inner density slope.

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Figure 3.12: Left panels: Mass models for UGC4115 and J0926+3343. For UGC4115, we didn't yield physical results when both c and R_{200} were allowed to vary. Hence, we fit the model by fixing the c value to the average concentration parameter for other galaxies (~ 5.5). The open circles indicate the total observed velocities after the correction for pressure support. The blue filled circles indicate the velocity contribution of the dark matter halo (after subtracting the contribution of baryons). The red dashed line and the green solid line represent the best fit NFW model and the best fit ISO model. The blue dotted line and the brown dashed line represent the gas and stars respectively. The residual velocities from best-fit ISO and NFW model are shown by the green filled circles and the red open circles. Right panels: The mass density profiles of UGC4115 and J0926+3343. The black dotted line indicates the data points used for the estimation of inner density slope.

GIPSY . The modelling procedure consists of a χ^2 minimization of

$$v_c^2 - \gamma v_*^2 - v_g^2 - v_h^2 = 0$$

where v_c is the rotation velocity after correcting for the pressure support, γ is the mass to luminosity ratio, v_* , v_g and v_h are the rotation velocities contributed by stars, gas and dark matter halo respectively.

3.3.1 Stellar Component

We use the g -band optical images to calculate the contribution of the stellar disk to the rotation curve. The optical g -band images were either taken from SDSS (Ahn et al., 2012) or from PanSTARRS (Flewelling et al., 2016) for those galaxies which lie outside the SDSS footprint. The de-projected luminosity profiles were derived using the task ‘ELLINT’ in ‘GIPSY ’ using the parameters obtained from the tilted ring fits. We fit an exponential to the extracted luminosity profile to obtain the scale length (h). We derive the g -band mass to luminosity ratio from the $g - i$ colors (taken from Perepelitsyna et al., 2014) and the stellar mass to light relations given in Zibetti et al. (2009). We use the derived mass to luminosity ratio to convert the luminosity profiles into stellar mass profiles. For the mass modelling, we assume a vertical $\text{sech}^2(z)$ scale height distribution, with the ratio of scale length to scale height (h/z_o) to be 5. We confirm however, that the choices of the vertical profile and the value of h/z_o do not affect the mass models significantly.

3.3.2 Gas Component

We use the total integrated HI intensity maps to derive the contribution of the gas to the observed rotation velocity. We apply the tilted ring parameters (see §2.5 in chapter 2) to derive the de-projected HI radial surface density profiles using task ‘ELLINT’ in GIPSY . The HI surface density profiles derived in this way match broadly with the profiles derived from FAT for most of the galaxies. We also confirm in §3.4 that our main results are not affected significantly if one uses the FAT derived surface brightness profiles instead of ‘ELLINT’ ones. We scale the derived HI surface density profiles by a factor of 1.35 to take the contribution of Helium and metals to the gas mass. As

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discussed above, we assume that the contribution of molecular gas and ionized gas to the total gas mass is negligible.

3.3.3 Dark matter halo

We use the two well-known models, viz. the Isothermal and the NFW models to parametrize the dark matter distribution. The parameters of these models are briefly summarized below.

3.3.3.1 Isothermal halo model

The density distribution of the observationally motivated pseudo-isothermal (ISO) halo model (e.g. [Begeman et al., 1991](#)) is:

$$\rho_{iso}(r) = \rho_0 [1 + (r/r_c)^2]^{-1} \quad (3.3)$$

where, ρ_0 is the core density and r_c the core radius of the halo. The corresponding circular velocity is:

$$V_{iso}(r) = \sqrt{4\pi\rho_0(r)r_c^2 \left[1 - \frac{r_c}{r} \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{r}{r_c}\right)\right]} \quad (3.4)$$

The inner inner slope ($\rho \sim r^\alpha$) of the mass density profile for the Isothermal halo model is $\alpha = 0$ (since for $r \ll r_c$, $\rho_{iso} \approx \rho_0$).

3.3.3.2 NFW halo model

The density profile of the NFW halo model ([Navarro et al., 1996](#)) is given by:

$$\rho_{NFW}(r) = \frac{\rho_i}{(r/r_s)(1+r/r_s)^2} \quad (3.5)$$

where r_s is a characteristic radius of the dark matter halo and ρ_i is the initial density of the universe at the time of collapse of the halo.

The corresponding circular velocity is:

$$V_{NFW}(r) = v_{200} \sqrt{\frac{\ln(1+cx) - cx/(1+cx)}{x[\ln(1+c) - c/(1+c)]}} \quad (3.6)$$

where $c = r_{200}/r_s$ is the concentration parameter and $x = r/r_{200}$; r_{200} being the radius at which the mean density of the halo is equal to 200 times the critical density and

v_{200} is the rotational velocity at r_{200} . v_{200} is related to the r_{200} as $v_{200} = hr_{200}$, where h is the dimensionless Hubble parameter. The inner slope of the density distribution is $\alpha \sim -1$ (at radii $r \ll r_s$, $\rho_{NFW} \approx \rho_i \left(\frac{r_s}{r}\right)$).

3.3.4 Constructing the mass models

As described above mass models for the galaxies were fit using three components i.e. the stellar disk, the gas disk and the dark matter halo. A number of different fits were performed. Firstly for the dark matter halo we fit both the Isothermal halo and NFW halo models. For each of these we allowed four different possibilities for the contributions from the baryonic components, viz. (1) *Constant γ_** : In this case, we use a fixed mass to light ratio as derived from the stellar population synthesis (SPS) models (2) *Maximum disc*: This model assumes that the observed rotation curve in the inner regions is almost entirely due to the stellar component. In this case, we scale the rotation curve due to the stellar component to the maximum value for which the dark matter density is non-negative at all radii. This model constrains the value of dark matter density to be minimum at all radii. (3) *Minimum disc*: In this case, we assume that the contribution of baryons to the observed rotation curve is zero. This assumption provides an upper limit to the dark matter density. (4) *Minimum disc + gas*: the stellar disk contribution to the rotation velocity is assumed to be zero, however the contribution of the gas disk is fully included. (5) *Free γ_** : In this model, we allow the mass-to-light ratio to be a free parameter. In some of the galaxies, this assumption did not yield physical results. The fit results of individual galaxies for various assumptions for γ_* are presented in Table 3.3.

3.4 Results

Fig 3.10–3.12 show the fit results for case(1), i.e. where the stellar mass to light ratio is fixed using the $g - i$ colors, using the rotation curves derived with FAT and the corresponding fit parameters are given in Table 3.2. We find that the NFW halos provide a better fit in most of the galaxies in terms of fit quality. However, the χ_{red}^2 is less than 1 in almost all cases, indicating that the errors provided by the FAT package are likely to be overestimated. Although both fits are formally acceptable, the residual velocities for NFW model (shown by red open circles) are generally smaller than the

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Table 3.2: Optical and dark matter properties

Galaxy	D (Mpc)	M_B	V_{rot} (km s^{-1})	γ_*	Isothermal			NFW		
					r_c (kpc)	ρ_0 ($M_\odot pc^{-3}$)	χ_r^2	c	r_{200} (kpc)	χ_r^2
KK246	6.85	-13.69	48.5	1.07	1.20±0.26	39.2±11.9	0.30	2.7±0.7	51.6±9.7	0.06
U4115 ^a	7.73	-14.75	62.9	0.29	1.87±0.20	30.5±3.6	0.09	..(5.5)	.. (37.2±2.9)	..(0.78)
J0926+3343	10.6	-12.90	38.3	0.06	0.34±0.19	163.4±143.3	0.52	1.9±6.1	59.9±160.6	0.15
U5288	11.4	-15.61	80.6	0.36	0.25±0.05	1340.9±507.1	0.71	11.4±1.7	41.3±1.7	1.21
U4148	13.5	-15.18	67.3	0.17	0.50±0.11	289.4±118.1	0.69	8.4±0.6	39.0±1.3	0.14
J0630+23	22.9	-15.89	86.0	0.24	1.92±0.24	41.7±8.0	0.34	3.4±0.8	71.4±9.9	0.39
J0626+24	23.2	-15.64	88.0	0.27	0.89±0.33	144.0±89.7	2.14	5.1±1.1	60.3±7.9	0.52
J0929+1155	24.3	-14.69	66.8	0.22	0.64±0.10	184.8±47.7	0.17	5.8±0.7	46.3±3.3	0.07

^a For UGC4115, we didn't yield physical results when both c and R_{200} were allowed to vary for the NFW halo model. Hence, we fix the c value to the average concentration parameter for other galaxies (~ 5.5) to fit the NFW halo model.

Table 3.3: Parameters of dark matter halos

Galaxy	Model	Isothermal					NFW				
		γ_*	r_c (kpc)	ρ_0 ($M_\odot \text{ pc}^{-3}$)	χ_r^2	γ_*	c	r_{200} (kpc)	χ_r^2		
KK246	Fixed γ_*	1.07	1.20±0.26	39.21±11.95	0.30	1.07	2.74±0.69	51.61±9.71	0.06		
	Minimum disc + gas	0.0	0.69±0.16	93.31±33.92	0.41	0.0	4.79±0.30	37.13±1.55	0.02		
	Minimum disc	0.0	0.66±0.14	107.17±36.68	0.42	0.0	5.11±0.23	37.63±1.13	0.01		
	Maximum disc	3.10	2.41±0.68	15.21±4.18	0.27		
U4115	Free γ_*	2.28	1.89±0.68	20.54±9.01	0.25		
	Constant γ_*	0.29	1.87±0.20	30.55±3.64	0.09	0.29		
	Minimum disc + gas	0.0	1.76±0.18	33.55±3.95	0.10	0.0		
	Minimum disc	0.0	1.71±0.14	41.12±3.82	0.08	0.0		
J0926+3343	Maximum disc	3.48	8.45±5.62	8.59±1.28	0.07	3.48		
	Free γ_*	2.75	4.48±2.83	11.71±5.09	0.07		
	Constant γ_*	0.06	0.34±0.19	163.38±143.27	0.52	0.06	1.89±6.07	59.89±160.65	0.15		
	Minimum disc + gas	0.0	0.35±0.19	163.76±142.79	0.52	0.0	1.90±5.60	59.94±158.44	0.15		
U5288	Minimum disc	0.0	0.41±0.24	148.97±134.17	0.64	0.0		
	Maximum disc	5.40	0.28±0.27	137.57±206.71	0.74		
	Free γ_*		
	Constant γ_*	0.36	0.25±0.05	1340.92±507.07	0.71	0.36	11.36±1.70	41.32±1.73	1.21		
U4148	Minimum disc + gas	0.0	0.25±0.05	1458.23±522.24	0.66	0.0	12.08±1.75	41.11±1.64	1.21		
	Minimum disc	0.0	0.28±0.06	1260.42±483.22	0.83	0.0	10.81±1.60	43.74±1.87	1.36		
	Maximum disc	5.40	2.26±0.64	20.21±9.23	1.22	5.40	2.49±0.78	57.61±7.91	0.88		
	Free γ_*		
J0630+23	Constant γ_*	0.17	0.50±0.11	289.43±118.12	0.69	0.17	8.42±0.65	39.05±1.26	0.14		
	Minimum disc + gas	0.0	0.51±0.11	288.84±117.34	0.69	0.0	8.45±0.65	39.14±1.26	0.14		
	Minimum disc	0.0	0.73±0.16	172.42±65.90	0.88	0.0	7.45±0.58	43.93±1.55	0.15		
	Maximum disc	17.0	0.14±0.08	1199.34±1270.0	0.95	17.0	4.38±2.45	29.25±6.52	1.01		
J0626+24	Free γ_*	2.8	0.45±0.13	315.64±149.47	0.76	0.51	8.36±0.82	38.86±1.84	0.16		
	Constant γ_*	0.24	1.92±0.24	41.73±8.02	0.34	0.24	3.42±0.76	71.4±9.97	0.39		
	Minimum disc + gas	0.0	1.85±0.23	45.07±8.51	0.35	0.0	3.61±0.78	70.41±9.44	0.42		
	Minimum disc	0.0	2.17±0.29	40.67±7.88	0.48	0.0	3.21±0.95	83.67±16.53	0.71		
J0929+1155	Maximum disc	2.64	3.24±0.61	15.47±3.74	0.36	2.64	1.07±1.13	118.94±74.78	0.34		
	Free γ_*	0.73	2.08±0.78	35.21±26.93	0.41	1.77	2.06±2.06	86.33±44.28	0.37		
	Constant γ_*	0.27	0.89±0.33	144.02±89.72	2.14	0.27	5.09±1.11	60.26±7.97	0.52		
	Minimum disc + gas	0.0	0.83±0.30	165.57	2.06	0.0	5.41±1.12	58.69±7.18	0.52		
J0929+1155	Minimum disc	0.0	1.03±0.34	127.57±69.41	2.12	0.0	5.15±0.86	64.46±6.71	0.35		
	Maximum disc	3.24	2.77±1.14	23.95±12.37	1.98	3.24	1.08±2.18	157.40±206.26	0.54		
	Free γ_*	1.07	4.14±3.03	66.67±25.79	0.65		
	Constant γ_*	0.22	0.64±0.10	184.76±47.67	0.17	0.22	5.78±0.70	46.34±3.26	0.07		
J0929+1155	Minimum disc + gas	0.0	0.65±0.10	184.82±47.63	0.17	0.0	5.78±0.69	46.59±3.26	0.07		
	Minimum disc	0.0	0.80±0.18	144.03±53.31	0.38	0.0	4.74±0.49	56.77±3.90	0.04		
	Maximum disc	17.6	0.38±0.19	192.49±172.12	0.73	17.6	6.96±4.15	24.67±6.07	0.72		
	Free γ_*	1.56	0.62±0.12	184.65±56.61	0.22		

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Table 3.4: Parameters of dark matter halos using FAT and ROTCUR derived rotation curves.

Galaxy	Model	Isothermal				NFW	
		r_c (kpc)	ρ_0 ($M_\odot \text{ pc}^{-3}$)	χ_r^2	c	r_{200} (kpc)	χ_r^2
KK246	FAT	1.20±0.26	39±12	0.30	2.7±0.7	52±10	0.06
	Rotcur	1.28±0.06	37±2	0.08	3.3±0.4	46±4	0.13
U4155	FAT	1.87±0.20	30±4	0.09
	Rotcur	2.06±0.10	29±1	0.17
J0926+3343	FAT	0.34±0.19	163±143	0.52	1.9±6.0	60±161	0.15
	Rotcur	2.23±1.08	21±5	0.46
U5288	FAT	0.25±0.05	1341±507	0.71	11.4±1.7	41±2	1.21
	Rotcur	0.58±0.07	314±68	1.90	10.4±1.3	44±2	4.32
U4148	FAT	0.50±0.11	289±118	0.69	8.4±0.6	39±1	0.14
	Rotcur	1.74±0.11	37±3	0.49	3.2±0.7	61±9	2.43
J0630+23	FAT	1.92±0.24	42±8	0.34	3.4±0.8	71±10	0.39
	Rotcur	2.97±0.38	22±3	0.21	1.5±1.0	125 ±60	0.29
J0626+24	FAT	0.89±0.33	144±90	2.14	5.1±1.1	60±8	0.52
	Rotcur	3.04±0.35	26±4	0.85	1.0±1.3	193±153	0.71
J0929+1155	FAT	0.64±0.10	185±48	0.17	5.8±0.7	46±3	0.07
	Rotcur	2.71±0.14	22±1	0.15

Table 3.5: Parameters of dark matter halos using 2D and 3D surface brightness profiles.

Galaxy	Model	Isothermal				NFW	
		r_c (kpc)	ρ_0 ($M_\odot \text{ pc}^{-3}$)	χ_r^2	c	r_{200} (kpc)	χ_r^2
KK246	2D SBR	1.20±0.26	39±12	0.30	2.7±0.7	52±10	0.06
	3D SBR	1.28±0.27	36±10	0.29	2.4±0.8	57±14	0.08
U4155	2D SBR	1.87±0.20	30±4	0.09
	3D SBR	1.83±0.16	34±3	0.07
J0926+3343	2D SBR	0.34±0.19	163±143	0.52	1.9±6.1	60±161	0.15
	3D SBR	0.41±0.28	131±134	0.65
U5288	2D SBR	0.25±0.05	1341±507	0.71	11.4±1.7	41±2	1.21
	3D SBR	0.26±0.05	1339±532	0.78	11.3±1.7	41±2	1.30
U4148	2D SBR	0.50±0.11	289±118	0.69	8.4±0.6	39±1	0.14
	3D SBR	0.49±0.11	304±123	0.66	8.5±0.6	39±1	0.14
J0630+23	2D SBR	1.92±0.24	42±8	0.34	3.4±0.8	71±10	0.39
	3D SBR	2.01±0.28	40±8	0.43	3.4±0.9	74±13	0.59
J0626+24	2D SBR	0.89±0.33	144±89	2.14	5.1±1.1	60±8	0.52
	3D SBR	0.98±0.34	128±74	2.03	5.1±0.9	62±7	0.37
J0929+1155	2D SBR	0.64±0.10	185±48	0.17	5.8±0.7	46±3	0.07
	3D SBR	0.70±0.12	168±50	0.23	5.4±0.6	50±3	0.06

Table 3.6: Inner density slopes of dark matter halos

Galaxy	R_{\min} (kpc)	R_{\max} ($H_{I_{\text{beam}}}$)	α (3D: minimum disc)	α (3D: DM only)	α (2D: Moment)	α (2D: Hermite)
KK246	0.15	20.3	-1.41 ± 0.12	-1.72 ± 0.37	-0.92 ± 0.13	-1.12 ± 0.03
U4115	0.25	32.7	-1.09 ± 0.16	-1.13 ± 0.20	0.04 ± 0.24	-0.35 ± 0.05
J0926+3343	0.21	5.9	-1.46 ± 0.38	-1.64 ± 0.37	-0.34 ± 0.21	-0.64 ± 0.6
U5288	0.23	23.4	-1.73 ± 0.15	-1.77 ± 0.19	-0.38 ± 0.3	-0.94 ± 0.1
U4148	0.13	21.4	-1.76 ± 0.23	-1.78 ± 0.23	-0.52 ± 0.02	-0.16 ± 0.14
J0630+23	0.33	18.3	-1.03 ± 0.14	-1.06 ± 0.15	-0.64 ± 0.49	-0.80 ± 0.46
J0626+24	0.34	19.5	-1.54 ± 0.08	-1.59 ± 0.08	-1.21 ± 0.02	-1.02 ± 0.40
J0929+1155	0.29	9.0	-1.16 ± 0.01	-1.17 ± 0.01	-0.07 ± 0.19	. . .

residual velocities for the isothermal model (shown by green filled circles) in the central regions. For 2 galaxies, viz. UGC4115 and UGC5288, the isothermal halo gave a better fit compared to the NFW halo. We note that the galaxy UGC5288 has a strong bar. For the galaxy UGC4115, we did not get physical results when both c and R_{200} were allowed to freely vary during the fitting process. For this galaxy we hence fix the value of c to the average concentration parameter for other galaxies (~ 5.5).

We compare the dark matter halo properties derived with FAT surface brightness profiles (‘3D’) and GIPSY surface brightness profiles (‘2D’) (shown in Table 3.5) and they mostly match within error bars. We also derive the dark matter halo parameters using the ROTCUR derived rotation curves and the corresponding fit parameters are shown in Table 3.4.

3.4.1 Dark matter density profiles

Apart from fitting mass models, one can also use the rotation curve to directly determine the inner slope of the density profile (e.g. Oh et al., 2011a). We assume a spherical halo potential (Trachternach et al., 2008) to convert the rotation curve to the dark matter density profile using the following equation:

$$\rho(R) = \frac{1}{4\pi G} \left[2 \frac{V}{R} \frac{\partial V}{\partial R} + \left(\frac{V}{R} \right)^2 \right] \quad (3.7)$$

where G is the gravitational constant and $V(R)$ is the rotation velocity after correcting for pressure support at a radius R . The right panels of Fig 3.10–3.12 show the

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Figure 3.13: The value of inner slope (α) of the dark matter density distribution versus the number of resolution elements across the major axis of the galaxy. The data points from this work are shown by blue circles. The red squares are from [Oh et al. \(2015\)](#). Left panel: slopes obtained using the rotation curves derived from FAT (3-D approach), right panel: slopes obtained using the rotation curves derived from ROTCUR (2-D approach).

Figure 3.14: The value of inner slope (α) of the dark matter density distribution versus the radius of the innermost point. The data points from this work are shown by blue circles. The red stars are from [de Blok et al. \(2001\)](#), the green pentagons are from [de Blok and Bosma \(2002a\)](#), the yellow diamonds are from [Swaters et al. \(2000\)](#) the cyan triangles are from [Verheijen \(1997\)](#). The black dotted lines are the theoretical slopes for the isothermal halo with core radii of 0.5 (left), 1 (middle) and 2(right) kpc. The red solid line is the NFW model (r^{-1}) and the green dashed line is the CDM $r^{-1.5}$ model with $c=8$ and $v_{200} = 100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ Left panel: slopes obtained using the rotation curves derived from FAT (3-D approach), right panel: slopes obtained using the rotation curves derived from ROTCUR (2-D approach).

derived dark matter density profiles of the individual galaxies. We plot both the dark matter densities derived from the total rotation curve (brown circles) and from the rotation curve after subtracting the contribution of baryons (green squares). The best-fit dark matter density profiles of isothermal halo and NFW halo models for a fixed mass to light ratio are also overplotted. As can be seen, the central dark matter density profiles are steeper than expected for the isothermal halo model, but are a good match to what would be expected from the NFW model.

In order to quantify the cuspieness of the dark matter distribution in the central regions of the galaxy, the logarithmic inner slope of the density profiles were measured following the method described in [de Blok et al. \(2001\)](#) (see also [Oh et al., 2015](#); [de Blok and Bosma, 2002b](#); [Oh et al., 2011b](#)). We first determine the “break radius” in the central regions of the galaxy. The break radius is defined as the radius at which the variation of the logarithmic slope of the density profile is maximum. The inner density slope (α) is then measured using a least-squares fit to the data points that lie within the break radius. The range over which the fit is performed is shown in the right panels of [Fig 3.10–3.12](#) by a black dotted line. The uncertainty in α is taken to be half of the difference between the slopes measured when one includes or excludes the first data point outside the break radius while doing the fit. This error estimate is probably more appropriate than that derived from the formal fit error. The inner density slopes were measured from both the observed rotation curve as well as the rotation curve obtained after subtracting the baryonic contribution. The former case corresponds to the “minimum disc assumption”, in the latter case the rotation velocity corresponds to the contribution of the dark matter alone. The measured slope α and the uncertainty in slope $\Delta\alpha$ of the galaxies for the dark matter only profiles are shown in the right panels of [Fig 3.10–3.12](#). We find that the mean values of the inner density slopes are $\alpha = -1.39 \pm 0.19$ and $\alpha = -1.48 \pm 0.23$ for the minimum disc assumption and the dark matter only profile respectively. The measured logarithmic inner density slopes for all the galaxies are shown in [table 3.6](#). These values are in better agreement with the logarithmic inner slope (~ -1) of the NFW cuspy profiles, and inconsistent with the slope of ~ 0 expected for the ISO halo. We also note that for all the galaxies, the radius within which we measure the inner density slope (r_d) is much less than the best fit characteristic radius (r_s) of the NFW halo, where r_d is typically within $\sim 10\%$ of r_s and within 30% of r_s for all the cases. But, for isothermal haloes, we find that

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r_d is typically comparable to the best fit core radius (r_c) of the isothermal halo and is higher than r_c in a few cases, which may lead to steeper DM density profiles (steeper than $\alpha \sim 0$).

3.4.2 Comparison with earlier studies

The steep inner slopes that we measure are in contradiction to several earlier measurements based on independent samples. For example, [de Blok et al. \(2001\)](#) measure α to be -0.2 ± 0.2 , while [Oh et al. \(2011b\)](#) find $\alpha = -0.29 \pm 0.07$ and [Oh et al. \(2015\)](#) get $\alpha = -0.42 \pm 0.21$ using the minimum disc assumption. Some earlier studies (e.g. [Verheijen, 1997](#)) have however found steeper slopes, i.e. $\alpha \sim -1.8$. Insufficient sampling of the dark matter density profiles in the inner region could lead to an artificial steepening of the slope ([de Blok et al., 2001](#)). This is because the logarithmic slope of the density profile becomes steeper towards the outer regions, steeper slopes would hence be obtained if data points from the outer region are included for the estimation of slope. To check whether this under sampling is the cause for the steeper slope that we measure, we compare the number of resolution elements across the galaxy for the galaxies in our sample and the literature. [Fig 3.13](#) (left panel) shows the plot of value of inner slope versus the number of resolution elements across the major axis of the galaxy. The blue circles indicate the galaxies from our sample and the red squares are the galaxies from earlier studies. As can be seen the galaxies in our sample have similar number of resolution elements as compared to the galaxies in the literature. This indicates that the obtained steeper slopes are not due to a different sampling in the inner regions of the dark matter halos. The other point of departure of this study is that we use rotation curves derived using a fit to the 3-D data cube, instead of a fit to the 2-D velocity field. To see what difference this makes, we show in [Fig 3.13](#) (right panel) the slopes measured for our sample using the 2-D velocity field and the GIPSY task ROTCUR. As can be seen the agreement between the slopes measured from our sample, and the slopes measured for earlier samples match quite well when we use rotation curves derived from the 2-D velocity field. [Fig. 3.14](#), which is a plot of the value of inner slope (α) versus the radius of the innermost point shows a similar result. [Fig. 3.14](#) (a), shows slopes for our galaxies based on FAT rotation curves, while in [Fig. 3.14](#) (b) shows the slopes measured using ROTCUR on the 2-D velocity fields. The data points from this work are shown by blue circles and other symbols are from

measurements taken from other studies (see the caption for details). The black dotted line shows the slope for the isothermal model, the red solid line and the green dashed lines show the Λ CDM r^{-1} (Navarro et al., 1996) and $r^{-1.5}$ (Moore et al., 1999) models respectively. The mean value of α for estimates from rotation curves derived from the 2-D velocity field, is $\alpha = -0.49 \pm 0.24$, which is consistent with values obtained in the literature.

3.4.3 Scaled density profiles

So far we have been dealing with each individual galaxy separately, and combining the results from parametric fits to the individual rotation curve. A complementary approach would be to try and suitably scale each rotation curve, so that they can be combined together, and then compare this composite curve with theoretical models. To do this, we follow (Oh et al., 2015, 2011b; Hayashi and Navarro, 2006) and scale the rotation velocities to $V_{0.3}$ and the radius to $R_{0.3}$, where $R_{0.3}$ is the radius at which the logarithmic slope of the rotation curve ($d \log V / d \log R$) becomes 0.3 and $V_{0.3}$ is the velocity at this radius. This scaling radius can generally be well determined for all the galaxies as it lies between the rising ($d \log V / d \log R = 1$) and the flat ($d \log V / d \log R = 0$) rotation curve. For our sample, we can determine $R_{0.3}$ for all the galaxies except for J0926+3343; in the case of J0926+3343 we take the outermost radius is taken as the scaling radius. In order to compare this composite rotation curve with the NFW model, we combine the theoretical NFW curves with V_{200} ranging from 10–110 km s⁻¹, concentration parameter obtained using the empirical relation between $c-V_{200}$ (de Blok et al., 2003; McGaugh et al., 2007) by also scaling them with respect to $R_{0.3}$ and $V_{0.3}$. Fig. 3.15 shows the plot of the scaled density versus the scaled radius. The black dotted line represents NFW halo with ($\alpha \sim -1$) with V_{200} 10–110 km s⁻¹ and the blue dashed line is the best-fit isothermal halo model. Once again we see a clear difference between the rotation curve derived from the 2-D and 3-D rotation curve. The left panel shows the density profile obtained using the FAT -derived rotation curve, which is consistent with the cuspy NFW profile. The right panel shows the density profile derived using the ROTCUR-derived rotation curve. This is not consistent with the NFW profile but is in good agreement with best-fit isothermal model in contrast to the FAT -derived rotation curve.

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Figure 3.15: Left panel: The density profiles derived using FAT (3-D approach) rotation curves, right panel: The density profiles derived using ROTCUR (2-D approach) rotation curves. The black dotted line represents NFW halo with ($\alpha \sim -1$) with V_{200} 10–110 km s $^{-1}$ and the blue dashed line is the best-fit isothermal halo model.

3.4.4 Further comparison of the 2D and 3D approaches

The difference between the rotation curves derived in the 2D and 3D method could, in principle arise from a FAT incorrectly modelling the data cube. To test this, we derive moment maps from the best fit model data cube produced by FAT and derive rotation curves as well as surface brightness profiles from them using the 2D routines in GIPSY. We show rotation curves as well as surface brightness profiles for all the galaxies in Fig. 3.16 and 3.17. For each of these quantities 3 sets of curves are shown, these are the curves derived by FAT (red squares) and GIPSY (black circles) when run on the original observed data, as well as the curves produced by the GIPSY tasks when run on the model produced by FAT (green diamonds). We find that in most cases, the rotation curves produced by GIPSY routines run on the original data very closely match those produced when the same routines are run on the FAT model, especially in the inner regions. This indicates that the FAT model is a good fit to the observed data, and that the differences that we see in the curves arise because of the systematic differences between the 2D and 3D approaches. There are significant differences in both the rotation curves as well as in the surface brightness profiles. The differences in the surface brightness profiles would lead to differences in the estimates of the contribution of the mass of the gas disk to the total rotation velocity as well as to differences in the estimated pressure support correction. We confirm that the differences to the pressure support correction are small in the inner regions (i.e. the regions that we use

Figure 3.16: Left panels: HI surface brightness as a function of radius and Right panels: Rotation velocity as a function of radius for the galaxies KK246, U4115, J0926+3343, and U5288. The profiles derived by fat and Rotcur are shown by red squares and black circles respectively. We use fat model and derive the profiles with 2D approach, which are shown by green diamonds.

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Figure 3.17: Left panels: HI surface brightness as a function of radius and Right panels: Rotation velocity as a function of radius for the galaxies U4148, J0630+23, J0626+24, and J0929+1155. The profiles derived by fat and Rotcur are shown by red squares and black circles respectively. We use fat model and derive the profiles with 2D approach, which are shown by green diamonds.

Figure 3.18: The value of inner slope (α) of the dark matter density distribution versus the radius of the innermost point. The slopes derived with the FAT rotation curves are shown by blue circles. The green and red circles indicate the slopes derived from the the Gauss-Hermite fit (and ROTCUR) and moment method (and ‘Rotcur’) respectively.

to determine the inner slope of the density profile). We also remind the reader that the inner slope is steeper than what one would expect from ISO halos even in the minimum disk approximation. This makes this result robust against variations produced by using different surface density profiles.

3.4.5 Comparison with Gauss-Hermite velocity fields

We also derive the velocity fields using Gauss-Hermite fits to the individual spectra using the task ‘XGAUFIT’ in GIPSY . The Gauss-Hermite polynomial includes an h_3 (skewness) term to the velocity profiles, and hence takes into account asymmetries in the profiles. We could not derive a reliable Hermite velocity field for the galaxy J0929+1155, the galaxy with the lowest signal to noise. The difference in slopes from the Hermite velocity field and the first moment map is significant for the galaxy UGC5288, which is a barred galaxy. As before we used the velocity fields to calculate the rotation curves using the task ROTCUR, these were then used to calculate the logarithmic slope of the density profile in exactly the same manner as detailed above. These slopes are listed

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Figure 3.19: Circular velocity at $r = 2$ kpc versus the maximum circular velocity, V_{max} for 8 void dwarf galaxies. The black solid line represents the correlation expected for the NFW halo.

in table 3.6, and the logarithmic slopes derived using the three different estimates of rotation curve (i.e. from the moment method and ROTCUR, the Gauss-Hermite fit and ROTCUR, and FAT) are shown in Fig. 3.18. As can be seen slopes derived with Hermite velocity fields are somewhat steeper than the slopes derived with the first moment maps, but not as steep as the FAT derived curves. The average slope obtained using the Gauss Hermite fits is -0.71 ± 0.33 . If we exclude the galaxy J0929+1155, the average slope obtained using moment maps and FAT is -0.56 ± 0.25 and -1.41 ± 0.21 respectively.

3.4.6 Comparison with simulated galaxies

The role of systematic effects in observational studies to the cusp-core problem was investigated by Pineda et al. (2017) using hydrodynamical simulations of dwarf galaxies. They mimic realistic kinematic observations and fit mock rotation curves. Their model galaxies also suggest that the minimum disc approximation would cause one to infer that the DM profile is flatter than it actually is, which is in contrast with the widely accepted claim. Our results are in agreement with this, we find a flatter inner density slope with the minimum disc assumption ($\alpha = -1.39 \pm 0.19$) than for the dark matter

only profile where we find a relatively steeper slope ($\alpha = -1.48 \pm 0.23$), although it matches within the error bars. They also find that it is extremely challenging to fully correct for the pressure support even with the data available from the highest quality cusp-core studies and that even small errors of a few km s^{-1} can cause dark matter cusps to be disguised as cores. In our particular case, we note that the pressure correction terms are small in the central part of the galaxy, and different assumptions do not make a significant difference to the final rotation curve (see §3.2.2).

Oman et al. (2015) find that the ‘cusp-core problem’ is better characterized as an ‘inner mass deficit’ problem, where they compare the inner circular velocities of observed galaxies with those of Λ CDM galaxies of same maximum velocity (V_{max}). Following their prescription in Fig 3.19, we plot the circular velocity at 2 kpc against the maximum measured rotation speed V_{max} . We interpolate linearly between nearby data points to get the velocity at exactly 2 kpc. The black solid line represents the correlation expected for the NFW halo. Dwarf galaxies in our sample are in good agreement with the NFW haloes.

Oman et al. (2017) measure HI rotation curves using ^{3D}BAROLO tilted ring modelling tool for the galaxies simulated from the APOSTLE Λ CDM hydrodynamical simulations. Their results suggest that non-circular motions in the gas lead to underestimate the circular velocities in the central regions, which can be misinterpreted as evidence for cores in the dark matter. They suggest that the failure of tilted ring models when applied to galaxies with non-negligible non-circular motions could be a possible resolution to the cusp-core problem. In our case, we find no clear evidence for non-circular motions, except in the case of UGC 5288, where there appears to be a strong bar and we indeed find that NFW halo is not a good fit for this galaxy.

3.4.7 Environmental dependence of DM halo properties

One of the aims of this study was to check if the void galaxies have different DM halo properties as compared to the galaxies outside voids. Figure 3.20 shows the concentration parameters versus the V_{200} (km s^{-1}). The black circles in the left panel and right panel represent the NFW halo parameters derived for the void dwarf galaxies using FAT and ROTCUR respectively. We were able to obtain physical values for the concentration parameters only for 6 rotation curves derived with FAT and 4 rotation curves derived with ROTCUR. The magenta squares (Oh et al., 2011a), red diamonds (Oh

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Figure 3.20: The concentration parameters versus the V_{200} in km s^{-1} . left panel: The parameters for the galaxies in our sample are using the rotation curves derived from FAT (3-D approach), right panel: The parameters for the galaxies in our sample are using the rotation curves derived from ROTCUR (2-D approach).

et al., 2015), blue triangles (de Blok et al., 2001) represent the NFW halo parameters of galaxies outside voids.

As can be seen from the plot, the data for the void dwarfs from our sample and other dwarfs from the literature overlap. We perform a 2D two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) test to compare the distribution of dwarf galaxies in the voids and dwarf galaxies in the average density regions quantitatively. We do not include de Blok et al. (2001) sample for the comparison as their galaxies lie outside the rotational velocity range of our galaxies. Since four galaxies (DDO43, DDO46, DDO52, and F564-V3) from the comparison sample happen to lie in voids (Pustilnik et al., 2018), we include them in the void galaxy sample. This test gives a probability of 0.11 for the void galaxies and the galaxies from average density regions being drawn from the same distribution. This p-value indicates that there is no clear statistical evidence for the two samples (i.e. dwarfs from voids and average density regions) being drawn from different populations. However, we require a larger sample to draw stronger conclusions.

3.5 Summary and Conclusions

We have derived rotation curves of 8 galaxies that lie in Lynx-Cancer void using 3-D and 2-D tilted ring fitting routines. We construct mass models and we find that both the isothermal and NFW halos are a good description of dark matter distribution of

galaxies in terms of fit-quality (i.e. χ_{red}^2). We convert the rotation curves derived using 2-D and 3-D approaches into density profiles. This allows us to examine the central dark matter density profiles and to distinguish between the cores and cusps at the center of galaxies. We find that the dark matter halo density profiles derived using 3-D approach are consistent with that predicted from Λ CDM simulations and the measured inner slopes ($\alpha = -1.39 \pm 0.19$) are more steep than the values of the slopes from the literature ($\alpha = -0.2 \pm 0.2$ in [de Blok et al. \(2001\)](#), $\alpha = -0.29 \pm 0.07$ in [Oh et al. \(2011b\)](#) and $\alpha = -0.42 \pm 0.21$ in [Oh et al. \(2015\)](#)). Since mass models for the galaxies in most of the earlier literature were constructed using the 2-D approaches, we use the rotation curves derived using 2D approach to estimate the inner density slope (α) values. The value of $\alpha \sim -0.5-0.7$ we get using the 2D approach is consistent with the slopes obtained in literature. This suggests that the fundamental differences in 3-D and 2-D tilted ring fitting routines affect the slope of the central dark matter density profiles. Since our sample size is modest, it is important to check the results using larger samples to obtain statistically significant conclusion.

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4

Angular momentum of dwarf galaxies

The following text is based on Sushma Kurapati, Jayaram N. Chengalur, Simon Pustilnik, Peter Kamphuis, 2018, MNRAS, 479, 228

4.1 Introduction

Two fundamental physical parameters of galaxies that are strongly correlated with their morphology and other secondary parameters are their mass (M) and specific angular momentum (j). For example, [Fall \(1983\)](#) showed that spiral and elliptical galaxies occupy distinct regions in the $j_s - M_s$ plane (where the subscript indicates quantities pertaining to the stellar component of the galaxies). For both spirals and ellipticals $j_s \approx qM_s^{2/3}$, but at a given M_s the specific stellar angular momentum of spirals is approximately 5 times larger than that of ellipticals. More recently, [Posti et al. \(2018, 2019\)](#) find a unbroken power-law $j_s \propto M_\odot^\alpha$ with $\alpha \sim 0.55 \pm 0.02$ for all the galaxies in the stellar mass range of $10^7 - 10^{11.5} M_\odot$. [Obreschkow and Glazebrook \(2014\)](#) considered the gas (atomic and molecular) contribution to angular momentum in addition to the stellar contribution in a sample of spiral galaxies, and they found a tight correlation between j_b , M_b , and bulge fraction (β). Across the entire sample, they found that $j_b \propto M_b^{2/3}$ (where the subscript denotes the quantities relating to the total cold baryonic component, i.e. stars + atomic gas + molecular gas), however at a fixed bulge fraction they found that $j_b \propto M_b$.

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Both scalings, viz. $j \propto M^{2/3}$ as well as $j \propto M$ have theoretical underpinnings. The traditional understanding was that galaxies acquire their angular momentum via the tidal torquing of collapsing proto-halos by neighbouring mass concentrations. In such models the bulk of the angular momentum gain happens around the turn around time of the proto-halo and the angular momentum remains roughly constant after that epoch. The angular momentum of the final collapsed halo is generally quantified by its ‘spin parameter’ $\lambda_h = J_h |E_h|^{1/2} / (GM_h^{5/2})$ (where J_h is the total angular momentum of the halo, E_h the total energy, and M_h the total mass). Both analytical calculations (Peebles (1969)), as well as numerical simulations (e.g. Bett et al. (2007); Rodríguez-Puebla et al. (2016)) find that the spin parameter is roughly independent of the total mass of the halo. This leads to a scaling relation between the halo specific angular momentum $j_h (= J_h/M_h)$ and the halo mass, viz. $j_h \propto M_h^{2/3}$. If one assumes that the baryonic matter and dark matter have similar distributions at early times and that galaxies form by cooling and angular momentum conserving collapse of the baryonic component (Fall (1983); Mo et al. (1998)) then a similar scaling relation would be expected for the baryonic component of galaxies, viz. $j_b \propto M_b^{2/3}$. On the other hand, if one focuses only on the baryonic components, and assumes that the bulk of the mass is contained in a gaseous disc which is just marginally stable against gravitational collapse (see e.g. Zasov, 1974; Zasov and Zaitseva, 2017), then one can show that $j_{\text{gas}} \propto M_{\text{gas}}$ (where the subscript indicates quantities relating to the gas disc).

In the models where the galaxy’s specific angular momentum is set by tidal torquing, one would expect that the angular momentum too would have an environmental dependence, as the tidal torque depends on the environment. Indeed numerical simulations show that the spin does depend on the tidal field and that on the average, haloes spin faster in stronger tidal fields (e.g. Shi et al., 2015). Cosmological simulations also find that the halo spin directions tend to correlate with the large scale structure, with low mass halo spins tending to be oriented parallel to the parent structure, while higher mass haloes have spins that are perpendicular to the parent structure (e.g. Aragón-Calvo et al., 2007). However, observational studies of galaxy spin filament alignment show mixed results. For example, Chen et al. (2019) find that bright and early-forming galaxies align more strongly with the directions of nearby filaments than faint and late-forming galaxies, while Krolewski et al. (2019) find no evidence for alignment. Welker et al. (2020) and Blue Bird et al. (2020) found mass-dependent spin alignments of galaxy

discs with respect to filaments in agreement with simulations. One possible reason for this mass dependence is that late time mass accretion is most significant for massive haloes, and tends to happen along the slowest collapsing direction (i.e. perpendicular to the parent structure, see e.g. Wang and Kang (2017)). The relationship between the spin and the morphology also appears to be mass dependent, with simulations suggesting that halo spin is the most important parameter setting the morphology of dwarf galaxies (Rodriguez-Gomez et al., 2017).

In this chapter, we study the angular momentum of dwarf irregular galaxies, and in particular compare the baryonic specific angular momentum of dwarf galaxies residing in voids with that of dwarfs lying outside voids. Dwarf galaxies are particularly interesting to study the environmental dependence of angular momentum as they are more sensitive to their environment as compared to larger spirals. As discussed earlier in §2.1, dwarf galaxies in voids are systematically more gas rich and have a higher sSFR than their average density counterparts (Moorman et al., 2016; Pustilnik and Martin, 2016). Simulations also show that the fainter dwarf galaxies in voids ($M_r > -16$) are typically bluer, have higher rates of star formation and specific star formation and lower mean stellar ages as compared to the dwarf galaxies in average density environments, while luminous dwarfs do not show similar trends (Kreckel et al., 2011b). Further, as mentioned above, simulations also suggest that the halo spin is the most important parameter in setting the morphology of dwarf galaxies, this makes it an interesting parameter to measure. Finally, since dwarf irregular galaxies are also generally gas rich, this means that measurements of the baryonic specific angular momentum and baryonic mass of dwarfs are less sensitive to the assumed stellar mass to light ratio as compared to brighter galaxies. Apart from comparing dwarf galaxies inside voids with those outside, we also compare the observed j_b vs M_b trends for dwarf galaxies with theoretical models such as those described above.

The rest of this chapter is organized as follows. In §4.2, we describe the measurements of angular momentum and mass. In §4.3, we present the $j_b - M_b$ relation for void dwarf galaxies and compare it with the relation for dwarf galaxies outside voids, as well as bulgeless spiral galaxies. In §4.4, we discuss and interpret our results in the context of various theoretical models and finally we conclude with a summary of the key results in §4.5.

4.2 Measurement of angular momentum and mass

The sample selection, the data reduction, and the derivation of rotation curves are discussed in detail in §2.2, §2.3, and §2.5 of chapter 2. In summary, we select 11 galaxies from the Lynx Cancer void for which the rotation curves can be reliably derived. The parameters for these 11 galaxies are listed in Table 5.3. The columns are as follows. column (1): galaxy name, (2): distance to the galaxy in Mpc, (3): absolute B-band magnitude (corrected for Galactic extinction), (4): HI mass ($\times 10^7 M_{\odot}$), (5): date of observation and (6): telescope used for the HI observations.

We derive the rotation curves by using both the 3D and 2D tilted ring fitting routines. We use FAT (v5.0.2, Kamphuis et al., 2015) to fit a tilted ring model to the data cube (i.e. a “3-D” approach) and the ‘ROTCUR’ task from the GIPSY software package (van der Hulst et al., 1992) to fit a tilted ring model to the velocity field (i.e. a “2-D” approach). The FAT and ROTCUR derived rotation curves are shown in Fig 2.13 and 2.14 of chapter 2. The rotation curves are generally in excellent agreement for 8 of the 11 galaxies. For 3 of the 11 galaxies (J0737+4724, UGC 3501 and DDO47), the rotation curves derived using the FAT pipeline did not match to the rotation curves derived using the ROTCUR in the inner regions. This is probably because for all three galaxies the HI density distribution is clumpy, which seems to have affected the inner part of the FAT curves and hence they are unreliable, confirmed by the large errors. However, the systematic difference that is seen in the inner regions of the rotation curve will have negligible effect on the total angular momentum since it is dominated by the outer parts of the disc. The specific angular momentum estimated using the ROTCUR and FAT derived rotation curves match within error bars.

For all of our sample galaxies, the HI mass was calculated using the standard formula, $M_{HI} = 2.36 \times 10^5 D^2 \int S dv M_{\odot}$, where D is the distance in Mpc, S is the flux density in Jy and dv is in km s^{-1} (Roberts, 1962). Integrated fluxes for the galaxies observed at the GMRT were measured using the lowest resolution ($\sim 40''$) data. The HI flux was measured both from the integrated global profile, as well as directly from the data cube using the SOFIA software. These two are in excellent agreement (within $\sim 10\%$); the value quoted here is from SOFIA. The quoted uncertainties on gas mass are based on the errors on the distance measurements (typically 10%) as well as the error on flux

4.2 Measurement of angular momentum and mass

Table 4.1: Parameters of galaxies selected for this study

Name	d (Mpc)	M_B	M_{HI} ($10^7 M_\odot$)	Obs.Date	Telescope
KK246	6.850	-13.69	9.0	09.07.2010	VLA
DDO47	8.040	-14.78	52.3	28.09.1984	VLA
UGC4115	7.730	-14.75	31.9	08.07.2004	VLA
UGC3501	10.07	-13.32	8.6	22.11.2014	GMRT
J0737+4724	10.40	-12.50	1.8	24.11.2011	GMRT
J0926+3343	10.63	-12.90	5.2	21.08.2015	GMRT
UGC5288	11.41	-15.61	90.2	20.01.1999	VLA
UGC4148	13.55	-15.18	78.4	01.10.2015	GMRT
J0630+23	22.92	-15.89	135.1	12.09.2015	GMRT
J0626+24	23.21	-15.64	63.8	03.05.2015	GMRT
J0929+1155	24.29	-14.69	36.6	23.04.2015	GMRT

Notes: All the galaxies except KK246 are from Lynx-Cancer void. All the parameters are taken from [Pustilnik and Tepliakova \(2011\)](#) and from [Kreckel et al. \(2011a\)](#) for the galaxies in Lynx-Cancer void and KK246 respectively.

densities. The error on the flux density is dominated by the calibration uncertainties, which for the GMRT are typically $\sim 10\%$.

The specific angular momentum j can be estimated by evaluating

$$j \equiv \frac{J}{M} = \frac{\int_0^R dr 2\pi r^2 \Sigma(r) v(r) \cos[\delta i(r)]}{\int_0^R dr 2\pi r \Sigma(r)} \quad (4.1)$$

where, $\Sigma(r)$ is the azimuthally averaged surface density, $v(r)$ is the circular velocity at radius r , $\delta i(r)$ is the difference in inclination with respect to the central disc inclination and R is the radius of the gas disc. This integral needs to be evaluated separately for the stellar and the gaseous components of the galaxy. The HI and optical deprojected radial surface brightness profiles were derived by fitting elliptical annuli to the HI moment 0 map and g-band optical images respectively, by using the ELLINT task in the GIPSY package. The g-band optical images were taken from the SDSS ([Ahn et al., 2012](#)) or from PanSTARRS ([Flewelling et al., 2016](#)) for those galaxies which lie outside the SDSS footprint. The stellar masses for these galaxies were calculated using the g-band luminosities and the g-i colors, which were taken from [Perepelitsyna et al. \(2014\)](#)¹, and using the stellar mass to light relations given in [Zibetti et al. \(2009\)](#).

¹We note that there are errors in calculations of stellar masses in [Perepelitsyna et al. \(2014\)](#),

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Table 4.2: Measured values of mass and specific angular momentum of 11 galaxies in this study

ID	Galaxy	M_* ($\log_{10} M_{\odot}$)	M_{gas} ($\log_{10} M_{\odot}$)	M_{bar} ($\log_{10} M_{\odot}$)	j_* (\log_{10} kpc km/s)	j_{gas} (\log_{10} kpc km/s)	j_{bar} (\log_{10} kpc km/s)
1	KK246	$7.70^{+0.114}_{-0.155}$	$8.11^{+0.119}_{-0.165}$	$8.25^{+0.094}_{-0.121}$	$1.10^{+0.081}_{-0.100}$	$1.96^{+0.062}_{-0.073}$	$1.84^{+0.062}_{-0.073}$
2	DDO47	$7.55^{+0.114}_{-0.155}$	$8.85^{+0.119}_{-0.165}$	$8.87^{+0.114}_{-0.156}$	$2.06^{+0.062}_{-0.072}$	$2.43^{+0.061}_{-0.071}$	$2.42^{+0.061}_{-0.071}$
3	UGC4115	$7.57^{+0.114}_{-0.155}$	$8.71^{+0.119}_{-0.165}$	$8.74^{+0.112}_{-0.152}$	$1.74^{+0.073}_{-0.088}$	$2.11^{+0.064}_{-0.075}$	$2.09^{+0.064}_{-0.075}$
4	UGC3501	$7.09^{+0.121}_{-0.168}$	$8.07^{+0.119}_{-0.165}$	$8.11^{+0.110}_{-0.147}$	$1.36^{+0.062}_{-0.073}$	$1.45^{+0.063}_{-0.073}$	$1.44^{+0.063}_{-0.073}$
5	J0737+4724	$6.07^{+0.114}_{-0.155}$	$7.38^{+0.119}_{-0.165}$	$7.41^{+0.115}_{-0.156}$	$0.92^{+0.063}_{-0.074}$	$1.22^{+0.063}_{-0.074}$	$1.21^{+0.063}_{-0.074}$
6	J0926+3343	$6.09^{+0.114}_{-0.155}$	$7.85^{+0.119}_{-0.165}$	$7.86^{+0.118}_{-0.162}$	$1.33^{+0.080}_{-0.098}$	$1.52^{+0.073}_{-0.088}$	$1.52^{+0.073}_{-0.088}$
7	UGC5288	$8.14^{+0.114}_{-0.155}$	$9.08^{+0.119}_{-0.165}$	$9.13^{+0.109}_{-0.146}$	$2.16^{+0.062}_{-0.072}$	$2.73^{+0.061}_{-0.071}$	$2.70^{+0.061}_{-0.071}$
8	UGC4148	$7.46^{+0.114}_{-0.155}$	$9.10^{+0.119}_{-0.165}$	$9.11^{+0.117}_{-0.161}$	$2.24^{+0.062}_{-0.072}$	$2.53^{+0.061}_{-0.071}$	$2.53^{+0.061}_{-0.071}$
9	J0630+23	$8.22^{+0.115}_{-0.157}$	$9.29^{+0.119}_{-0.165}$	$9.33^{+0.111}_{-0.150}$	$2.22^{+0.063}_{-0.073}$	$2.67^{+0.061}_{-0.071}$	$2.65^{+0.061}_{-0.071}$
10	J0626+24	$7.73^{+0.115}_{-0.157}$	$8.95^{+0.119}_{-0.165}$	$8.97^{+0.114}_{-0.154}$	$2.37^{+0.062}_{-0.072}$	$2.41^{+0.062}_{-0.072}$	$2.41^{+0.062}_{-0.072}$
11	J0929+1155	$7.43^{+0.114}_{-0.155}$	$8.68^{+0.119}_{-0.165}$	$8.70^{+0.114}_{-0.155}$	$2.23^{+0.063}_{-0.073}$	$2.32^{+0.062}_{-0.073}$	$2.32^{+0.062}_{-0.073}$

Errors in the stellar mass were computed using the errors in the distance as well as the photometric errors. The total gas density profile was computed by scaling the HI surface density by a factor of 1.35 to account for the contribution from Helium. No correction was made for the molecular gas since for faint dwarf galaxies such as those in our sample, the molecular fraction is believed to be low (e.g. [Taylor et al., 1998](#); [Schruba et al., 2012](#); [Cormier et al., 2014](#)). The contribution of the ionized gas is also expected to be small and has been neglected. Thus, the total baryon density profiles were computed as $\Sigma_b = \Sigma_* + 1.35 \Sigma_{HI}$. The specific angular momentum of gas, stars and baryons was computed by numerically evaluating the integral in Equation (1). For all quantities, the integral converges within the error bars. The rotation velocity of the stars was taken to be the same as that of the gas. This assumption has no significant effect on our results since the total angular momentum of the stellar component is very small ($< 10\%$) compared to that of the gas. Table 4.2 lists the measurements of total mass and specific angular momentum of stars, gas, and baryons along with error bars on these quantities. The columns are as follows. Column (1) galaxy ID; (2) name of the galaxy; (3) stellar mass ; (4) gas mass; (5) total baryonic mass; (6) stellar specific angular momentum; (7) gas specific angular momentum and (8) baryonic specific angular momentum.

4.3 Results

4.3.1 Comparison of j in void dwarfs & other dwarfs

We show in Fig. 4.1 the j_b - M_b relation for the 11 void dwarf galaxies (black open circles). One of the aims of this study was to check if void galaxies have a different specific angular momentum compared to galaxies outside voids. Hence, we also show in Fig. 4.1 data for a comparison sample of 14 dIrr galaxies drawn from the studies by [Butler et al. \(2017\)](#) (red squares) as well as for 5 gas rich dwarf galaxies taken from [Chowdhury and Chengalur \(2017, hereafter CC17\)](#) (green diamonds). Since two galaxies (DDO 154 and DDO 133) were common in both the samples, they were excluded from the [Butler et al. \(2017\)](#) sample. This gives us a total of 17 galaxies in the comparison sample. These two samples contain galaxies with similar morphological type (mostly dwarf irregulars)

where the galactic extinctions were not taken into account. An updated version of stellar masses in [Perepelitsyna et al. \(2014\)](#) is now given in arXiv:1408.0613v3.

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Figure 4.1: Log j_b -log M_b relation of 11 dwarf galaxies residing in Lynx-Cancer void from this work (black open circles), 12 dwarf galaxies from [Butler et al. \(2017\)](#) (red squares) and 5 dwarf galaxies from [Chowdhury and Chengalur \(2017\)](#) (green diamonds). The blue dotted line indicates the $\beta = 0$ plane of j_b - M_b relation obtained for the massive spiral galaxies by [Obreschkow and Glazebrook \(2014\)](#) and was recomputed by [Chowdhury and Chengalur \(2017\)](#). The black solid line is the best fit line for the dwarf galaxies using the linear regression. The galaxies from [Butler et al. \(2017\)](#) that were identified as being discrepant are marked with a circle around the red squares.

and M_B as the galaxies in our sample. While, as noted above, our sample galaxies were selected from void environments, the large scale environment was not a specific selection criteria for the two comparison samples. However, some of the galaxies from the comparison samples lie in low density regions. In the sample of [Chowdhury and Chengalur \(2017\)](#), the galaxy AndIV is an isolated galaxy and lies in a low density region ([Karachentsev et al., 2016](#)). In the sample of [Butler et al. \(2017\)](#), DDO52 belongs to Lynx-Cancer void. As can be seen from the plot, the data for the void dwarfs from our sample and other dwarfs from the literature overlap. A Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) test gives a probability of 0.54 for the galaxies in our sample and the literature being drawn from the same distribution. If the two galaxies from the comparison sample that happen to lie in low density regions (viz. AndIV and DDO52) are included in the void galaxy sample, the KS test gives a probability of ~ 0.30 that the two samples are drawn from the same population. This large p-value indicates that there is no clear statistical evidence for the two samples (dwarfs from voids and average density regions) being drawn from different populations. Hence, when we determine the j_b - M_b relation below, we combine the data for all the galaxies. This gives us a total sample size of 28 (11 galaxies from our sample, 12 galaxies from [Butler et al. \(2017\)](#) and 5 galaxies from [Chowdhury and Chengalur \(2017\)](#)). We note that one of the selection criteria for all of these galaxy samples was the availability of good quality HI rotation curves, i.e. they are gas rich. We return to the issue of having selected gas rich dwarfs in Section 4.4.2.

4.3.2 j_b - M_b relation for dwarf galaxies

Another useful comparison is with the sample of spiral galaxies from the THINGS survey. [Obreschkow and Glazebrook \(2014\)](#) studied the relation between specific angular momentum (j_b), baryonic mass (M_b) and bulge fraction (β) for the galaxies in this sample, and found that these three parameters correlate. The dwarf galaxies in our sample are bulge-less, and for Fig. 4.1 we would like a parametrization of the relationship between j_b and M_b for $\beta = 0$. Such a parameterization has been provided by [Chowdhury and Chengalur \(2017\)](#) (based on the data in [Obreschkow and Glazebrook \(2014\)](#), and with errors estimated via bootstrapping re-sampling), viz.

$$\log_{10}\left(\frac{j_b}{10^3 \text{ kpc km/s}}\right) = c_1 \log_{10}\left(\frac{M_B}{10^{10} M_\odot}\right) + c_2 \quad (4.2)$$

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with $(c_1, c_2) = (0.94 \pm 0.05, -0.13 \pm 0.04)$ respectively. This is shown in Fig. 4.1 as the dotted blue line. As can be seen, all of the dwarf galaxies lie systematically above the relationship seen for bulgeless spiral galaxies, a fact noted earlier by [Butler et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Chowdhury and Chengalur \(2017\)](#). Since the dwarf galaxies both inside and outside of voids appear to follow the same trend in the j_b - M_b plane, we combine both the void and non-void samples in order to determine the best fit j_b - M_b for dwarf irregular galaxies.

We use two fitting procedures to estimate the best fit linear regression between j_b and M_b for the combined sample. The LTS algorithm ([Cappellari et al., 2013](#)) does an iterative fit allowing for errors on both axes (but assuming that they are uncorrelated). In each iteration data points identified as discrepant in the previous iteration are dropped. This algorithm identifies four galaxies from the sample of [Butler et al. \(2017\)](#), viz. UGC8508, DDO210, DDO50 and NGC2366 as being discrepant. As can be seen from Fig. 4.1, UGC8508 is a significant outlier. We could not identify any underlying physical reason for this. All the discrepant galaxies are indicated by a circle around the red squares in Fig 4.1. After excluding these galaxies, the final fit values that the LTS algorithm gives are $(c_1, c_2) = (0.83 \pm 0.06, 0.31 \pm 0.09)$. We then use the BCES algorithm ([Akritas and Bershady, 1996](#)) as implemented in the python code developed by R. Nemmen (see e.g. [Nemmen et al., 2012](#)) which accounts for errors in both j_b and M_b , as well as the fact that these errors are correlated. The galaxies identified by the LTS algorithm as discrepant have been dropped when doing this fit. The BCES algorithm fit values are $(c_1, c_2) = (0.89 \pm 0.05, 0.40 \pm 0.08)$. We adopt these fit values for the rest of the paper; this best fit line is also shown by the solid black line in Fig. 4.1. Including the three discrepant galaxies, but excluding UGC 8508, gives best fit parameter values which agree with the values above within 2σ . It is interesting that the slope (i.e. the c_1 parameter) for the dwarf galaxies matches the slope measured for larger spirals within the 1σ error bars. However, the intercept obtained for the dwarf galaxies is significantly ($\sim 6\sigma$, using the combined error bars) different, with the dwarf galaxies having a higher specific angular momentum than that expected from the relationship for spiral galaxies.

4.4 Discussion

In theoretical models of galaxy formation, the angular momentum acquired in proto-galaxies is presented in terms of the “spin parameter” ($\lambda = J |E|^{1/2} / GM^{5/2}$), which is a combination of the total angular momentum J , the total energy E and the total mass M . This parametrisation is popular since the value of λ (unlike j) is expected to be independent of mass. Consistent with early theoretical calculations, simulations of structure formation find that the spin parameter of galaxy halos exhibits a log-normal distribution with average $\langle \lambda \rangle \approx 0.04$. The distribution of spin parameter has been studied as a function of mass, redshift, and environment, and is found to be nearly independent of mass and redshift, but with a slight dependence on environment (e.g. [Shi et al., 2015](#)). The fact that λ is independent of mass also means that the specific angular momentum scales with mass as $j \propto M^\alpha$, with $\alpha \sim 2/3$, ([Peebles, 1969, 1971](#)). These theoretical and numerical results are strictly speaking for the dark matter haloes. Observations can only directly probe the baryonic matter. If one assumes that the baryons and the dark matter initially have the same specific angular momentum and that the specific angular momentum is roughly conserved as the baryons collapse to form the visible galaxy ([Fall and Efstathiou, 1980](#)), then for the baryonic material too, one would observe the same scaling between specific angular momentum and total baryonic mass, viz. $j_b \propto M_b^{2/3}$. In a pioneering study done more than three decades ago, [Fall \(1983\)](#) showed that for both spiral and elliptical galaxies $j_b \propto M_b^\alpha$ with $\alpha \approx 2/3$. The constant of proportionality is larger for spiral galaxies than for ellipticals by a factor ≈ 5 , a result confirmed in [Romanowsky and Fall \(2012\)](#). These authors also show that the differences between ellipticals and spirals cannot be explained by assuming that they arise in proto-galaxies with different spin parameters, instead there must be formation and evolutionary processes that affect the final specific angular momentum of the baryons.

While halos may acquire their initial angular momentum via tidal torquing, there are a number of evolutionary processes that could affect the specific angular momentum of the galaxies we observe today. Bulge dominated objects produced by mergers of discs could have greatly reduced specific angular momentum compared to their progenitors. This is consistent with the results of [Fall \(1983\)](#) who find that the specific angular momentum of ellipticals is significantly smaller than that of spirals. Feedback from star

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Figure 4.2: (a). The $\text{Log } j_b$ - $\text{Log } M_b$ plane and (b) $\text{Log } j_{\text{gas}}$ - $\text{Log } M_{\text{gas}}$ plane showing data for 11 dwarf galaxies residing in Lynx-Cancer void (black open circles) as well as dwarf galaxies for which we have taken the data from the literature. The black solid line indicates the best fit linear relation to the entire sample. The green dotted line is the best-fit stability model (Eqn 4.6) for a rising rotation curve. The best fit stability model corresponds to $\sigma/Q_c \sim 2.8 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and $\sim 2.2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ for the fit to the baryons and the gas respectively. The dotted line is from [Obreschkow and Glazebrook \(2014\)](#) and shows the $j \propto M^{2/3}$ relation expected from the tidal torquing model. See the text for more details.

formation or AGN could prevent the catastrophic collapse of baryonic matter into a low specific angular momentum bulge in the centre of the halo. Indeed one of the major problems in the early simulations of galaxy formation that did not include such feedback was that the simulated galaxies had unrealistically small specific angular momentum (e.g. [Navarro and Steinmetz, 1997](#)). Conversely, this problem is greatly diminished in models which include feedback (see e.g. [Okamoto et al. \(2005\)](#); [Governato et al. \(2007\)](#)). If the baryonic specific angular momentum depends critically on feedback processes, rather than on the initial angular momentum of the dark halo, then it is possible that there is some kind of regulatory mechanism that results in the observed relationship between the baryonic specific angular momentum and the baryonic mass. Below we look at one specific model where it is assumed that the galaxy consists of a marginally stable gas disc.

4.4.1 disc stability models

[Zasov \(1974\)](#) showed that the HI mass (M_{HI}) scales with the maximum rotational velocity (V_m) and the radius at which it is achieved (R_m), i.e. $M_{\text{HI}} \propto V_m R_m$ (the product $V_m R_m$ can be taken as an approximate proxy to the specific angular momentum), and argued that this scaling can be understood as a consequence of a critical gas density required for the onset of star formation. This critical density is assumed to be the one set by the Toomre stability criteria [Toomre \(1964\)](#). [Zasov and Zaitseva \(2017\)](#) present analytic equations for the relationship between the specific angular momentum, mass, and the Toomre stability parameter. We summarize these briefly below. For a gas disc with radius R_0 and the circular velocity V_0 at R_0 , and for which the column density is everywhere equal to the critical density, the gas mass is given by

$$M_{\text{gas}} = 2^{3/2}(1+n)^{-1/2} \frac{\sigma}{Q_c G} V_0 R_0 \quad (4.3)$$

where $n = 0$ for a flat rotation curve, and 1 for a rising one and Q_c is the numerical value of the threshold parameter at which the disc instability sets in, in units of the Toomre parameter $Q = \sigma \kappa / (\pi G \Sigma_g)$, where κ is the epicyclic frequency, σ is the velocity dispersion and Σ_g the gas column density ([Zasov and Zaitseva \(2017\)](#))¹. Similarly the total angular momentum is given by

¹We note that there is a typographical error in [Zasov and Zaitseva \(2017\)](#), where the factor G is missing

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$$J = 2^{1/2}(1+n)^{-1/2} \frac{\sigma}{Q_c G} V_0^2 R_0^2 \quad (4.4)$$

This gives us the relation between the specific angular momentum and mass if the gas is in a marginally stable state, viz.

$$\log(j) = \log(M) + \log \left(2^{-5/2} (1+n)^{1/2} \frac{Q_c G}{\sigma} \right) \quad (4.5)$$

We note that the slope of the relation is independent of the shape of the rotation curve (flat or rising) although the intercept is not. Hence, if the gas is marginally stable, we expect that the specific angular momentum scales with mass as $j \propto M^\alpha$, with $\alpha \sim 1$. This is in contrast with the expected scaling relation for the specific angular momentum and mass of the dark matter halo ($\alpha \approx 2/3$; (Peebles, 1969, 1971)) and also the observed scaling relation between the baryonic specific angular momentum and mass of the spiral galaxies and elliptical galaxies ($\alpha \approx 2/3$; Fall (1983)), but is similar to the scaling relation obtained for galaxies at a fixed bulge fraction ($\alpha \sim 0.94 \pm 0.05$; Obreschkow and Glazebrook (2014)) and also for the dwarf galaxies ($\alpha \sim 0.89 \pm 0.05$; see §4.3.2).

For the case of a linearly rising rotation curve, we can write Eqn. 4.5 as

$$\log(j) = \log(M) + \log \left(\frac{Q_c G}{4\sigma} \right) \quad (4.6)$$

Since dwarf galaxies are gas dominated, Eqn. 4.6 should approximately hold for the total baryonic content. Fig 4.2 shows the location of 11 dwarf galaxies residing in Lynx-Cancer void (from this work; black open circles) and dwarf galaxies from the literature in the (a) baryonic j-M plane and (b) gas j-M plane. The stability relation (Eqn. 4.6) is shown as a green dashed line; it can be seen that it does indeed provide a reasonable fit to the data. For the best fit relation shown in Fig. 4.2 we assume $n=1$ (since dwarf irregular galaxies typically have rising rotation curves) and fit for σ/Q_c . As can be seen from Eqn 4.6, if we assume $n=0$ the derived σ/Q_c will change by a factor of $\sqrt{2}$. The σ/Q_c that we get (for $n=1$) is $\sim 2.8 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. This value can be compared with the canonical values of σ and the Q_c . The observed velocity dispersion in gas discs is $\sim 6 - 10 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (see e.g. Shostak and van der Kruit, 1984; Tamburro et al., 2009; Ianjamasimanana et al., 2015). If we assume that Q_c lies in the range 2 – 4 (which is a typical value suggested by observations, see e.g. Zasov and Zaitseva (2017)

and references therein), then the obtained best-fit values of σ/Q_c lie well within the range suggested by other observations. Finally, we note that this stability model has also been proposed by [Obreschkow et al. \(2016\)](#) who present observational support for the prediction of the stability model that the atomic gas fraction (f_{atm}) of galaxies to varies as $f_{\text{atm}} \propto j\sigma/(GM)$ (where σ is the gas velocity dispersion).

In the case of the gas j - M measurements, the best fit σ/Q_c (for $n=1$) is ~ 2.2 km s^{-1} . This fit was done with the slope fixed to 1, as required by Eqn. 4.6. If we fit also for the slope, the best fit relationship between the gas specific angular momentum (j_{gas}) and mass (M_{gas}) is:

$$\log_{10}\left(\frac{j_{\text{gas}}}{10^3 \text{ kpc km/s}}\right) = (0.80 \pm 0.08) \log_{10}\left(\frac{M_{\text{gas}}}{10^{10} M_{\odot}}\right) + (0.37 \pm 0.12) \quad (4.7)$$

We revisit this $j_{\text{gas}} - M_{\text{gas}}$ relation for a diverse sample of galaxies in chapter 5 and discuss it in the context of marginally stable disc models.

4.4.2 Comparison with theoretical expectations

One of the clear conclusions of this chapter is that dwarf galaxies have a higher baryon specific angular momentum compared to an extrapolation of the trends seen for higher mass bulge-less spirals. Similarly, [Butler et al. \(2017\)](#) found that dwarf galaxies also have systematically higher j_b as compared to the $j_b \propto M_b^{2/3}$ relation observed for samples which include all spirals independent of bulge fraction. [El-Badry et al. \(2017\)](#) study the angular momentum content of isolated galaxies in the FIRE simulations spanning $M_{\star} = 10^6 - 10^{11} M_{\odot}$. They find that the simulation produces fewer high-angular momentum, low mass galaxies than are represented in observational studies. They suggest that this is due to (1) the standard practice of assuming that the stellar disc has the same rotational velocity as the gas, which leads to an overestimation of angular momentum, and (2) the bias in observational studies towards well behaved, rotating systems. For our sample galaxies, we note that the first issue is unlikely to be a problem since the contribution of stellar specific angular momentum to the total specific angular momentum is very small ($< 10\%$). We also note that none of the galaxies in the FIRE simulations have as high a specific angular momentum as that of the observed galaxies. Thus while it is possible that the relationship that we observe defines the upper envelope of the $j_b - M_b$ relation, it does appear that even those simulations that include feedback do not produce galaxies with as high a specific angular momentum as found in observations.

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The simple tidal torquing model predicts that for the dark matter $j_H \propto \lambda M_H^{2/3}$. We show in Fig. 4.2 the corresponding baryonic relation derived for spiral galaxies by (Obreschkow and Glazebrook, 2014):

$$\frac{j_b}{10^3 \text{ kpc km/s}} = 1.96 \lambda f_j f_M^{-2/3} \left[\frac{M_b}{10^{10} M_\odot} \right]^{2/3} \quad (4.8)$$

where $f_M = M_b/M_H$, is the baryon fraction and $f_j = j_b/j_H$ is the specific angular momentum fraction. The derivation by Obreschkow and Glazebrook (2014) assumes $f_j = 1$ (Fall and Efstathiou, 1980; Stewart et al., 2013), spin parameter $\lambda \approx 0.04$ (Macciò et al., 2008) and $f_M \approx 0.05$ (as typical for large spiral galaxies (McGaugh et al., 2010; Behroozi et al., 2013)). As can be seen from Fig. 4.2, the relationship predicted by the tidal torquing model is flatter than what we observe for dwarf galaxies. Of course, as we noted above, this relationship is, strictly speaking, for the total mass, while the observed relationship is for the baryonic components. It seems likely therefore that, as discussed above, baryonic processes that unfold as the galaxy evolves are crucial in determining the final specific angular momentum. In this context, the fact that stability models (as discussed in §4.4.1) predict a j - M relationship quite similar to what is observed is particularly interesting. In the scenario where the specific angular momentum is regulated by stability criteria, the larger specific angular momentum of dwarfs may be partly because dwarf galaxy rotation curves are linear over a larger part of the disc. (Recall as discussed above, in the stability model the intercept is 0.29 for a flat rotation curve and 0.44 for a rising one). We note however that our own sample contains a mix of rising as well as flat rotation curves. On the other hand, dwarf galaxies also have significantly thicker gas discs than spirals (Roychowdhury et al. (2013, 2010)). Gas column densities that would be unstable by the Toomre criteria ($Q=1$) for thin discs would be stable in thick ones (see e.g. Wang et al. (2010)). As such, if the gas column density is being set by the stability criteria, one would expect that this would lower the specific angular momentum for dwarfs as compared to spirals. It hence appears likely that there is something else at play here, apart from disc stability. We explore one such mechanism, viz. preferential loss of low angular momentum gas, in section (§4.4.5) below.

Figure 4.3: Location of 11 dwarf galaxies residing in Lynx-Cancer void from this work (black open circles), 12 dwarf galaxies from [Butler et al. \(2017\)](#) (red squares), dwarf galaxies from [Chowdhury and Chengalur \(2017\)](#) (green diamonds), 17 dwarf galaxies with reliable rotation curves ($q=1$) from [Elson \(2017\)](#) (blue stars) and 19 dwarf galaxies with uncertain rotation curves ($q=2$) from [Elson \(2017\)](#) (purple plus symbols) in the plot of j_b vs M_b . The black solid line is the linear regression for dwarf galaxies from this work, the blue dotted line indicates the $\beta = 0$ plane of j_b - M_b relation obtained for bulgeless spiral galaxies by [Chowdhury and Chengalur \(2017\)](#); [Obreschkow and Glazebrook \(2014\)](#) and the red dashed line is the best fit relation obtained by [Elson \(2017\)](#).

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4.4.3 Comparison with other samples

In this section, we compare the $j_b - M_b$ relation from this work to the relation obtained for dwarf galaxies in earlier studies. As discussed above, our results are in good agreement with those of [Butler et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Chowdhury and Chengalur \(2017\)](#). Recently [Elson \(2017\)](#) used a sample of 37 galaxies from the Westerbork HI survey of Spiral and Irregular Galaxies project (WHISP; ([Swaters et al., 2002](#))) with rotation curve data from [Swaters et al. \(2009\)](#) to derive the $j_b - M_b$ relation. [Swaters et al. \(2009\)](#) used data with 30" resolution to derive the rotation curves and they divided their derived rotation curves into four categories. A reliable rotation curve was given a quality index $q=1$, uncertain and highly uncertain rotation curves are indicated by $q=2$ and $q=3$ respectively. A case for which no rotation curve could be derived is indicated by $q=4$. [Elson \(2017\)](#) use both reliable rotation curves ($q=1$) and uncertain rotation curves ($q=2$) for their study of $j_b - M_b$ relation for low mass galaxies. Fig. 4.3 shows the location of dwarf galaxies from this work and dwarf galaxies from the literature in the plot of j_b versus M_b . The black solid line is the linear regression for dwarf galaxies from this work, the blue dotted line indicates the $\beta = 0$ plane of $j_b - M_b$ relation obtained for the massive spiral galaxies by [Chowdhury and Chengalur \(2017\)](#); [Obreschkow and Glazebrook \(2014\)](#) and the red dashed line is the best fit relation obtained by [Elson \(2017\)](#). [Elson \(2017\)](#) obtained a slope, $\alpha \sim 0.62$, which differs from the steeper relation obtained in this work ($\alpha \sim 0.89$). However, if we consider only the galaxies with reliable rotation curves ($q=1$), and with masses lower than $10^{9.1} M_\odot$ (see Sec. 4.4.4 below for a justification of this cut-off), then the galaxies seem to be consistent with the relation obtained by us. The galaxies with uncertain rotation curves ($q=2$) have a large scatter and deviate from the distribution of remaining dwarf galaxies. As discussed below, combining our sample with other samples, we find a break in the $j_b - M_b$ relation at a mass of $10^{9.1} M_\odot$. Most of our sample galaxies are below this mass limit. The best fit slope we find using [Elson \(2017\)](#) sample, after excluding galaxies with uncertain rotation curves as well as galaxies with masses $> 10^{9.1} M_\odot$ is 0.86 ± 0.04 . This agrees within error bars with the value that we find for our sample.

4.4.4 Dependence of the j_b - M_b relation on other galaxy parameters

In order to understand if there is any correlation between the deviation of the specific angular momentum of dwarf galaxies from the $j_b - M_b$ relation of bulgeless spiral galaxies with other parameters such as baryonic mass and environment, we calculate the difference in j_b and $j_{b,\text{exp}}$. where, j_b is the observed specific angular momentum for a dwarf galaxy and $j_{b,\text{exp}}$ is the expected specific angular momentum for a given mass and zero bulge fraction from the relation derived for spiral galaxies obtained by [Chowdhury and Chengalur \(2017\)](#); [Obreschkow and Glazebrook \(2014\)](#). Let $d_{j,b}$ be defined as $\log(j_b) - \log(j_{b,\text{exp}})$.

Fig. 4.4 (a) shows the plot of $d_{j,b}$ versus baryon mass. We include the dwarf galaxies from this work and dwarf galaxies from the literature. As discussed above, we include only the galaxies with reliable rotation curves ($q=1$) from [Elson \(2017\)](#). A break appears around $M_b \sim 10^{9.1} M_\odot$. Dwarf galaxies with masses lower than $10^{9.1} M_\odot$ have significantly higher baryonic specific angular momentum than expected from the relation for bulgeless spiral galaxies. As the mass of the galaxy increases beyond $10^{9.1} M_\odot$, the baryonic specific angular momentum decreases and they tend to follow the relation obtained for the bulgeless spirals. It is interesting to note that the mass at which the break is seen is similar to the limiting mass $M_* \sim 2 \times 10^9 M_\odot$, below which low-mass galaxies start to be systematically thicker ([Sánchez-Janssen et al., 2010](#)).

We also check if there is any correlation between the scatter in $j_b - M_b$ relation with the environment. We use the tidal index (TI) as a parameter to describe the environment of a galaxy. Tidal index quantifies the local density environment and is determined by the distance and the mass of significant neighbour. We use TI5 as a parameter which is determined by the five most important neighbours. TI5 is a more robust indicator of galaxy environment as compared to TI1, which is determined by the galaxy's immediate significant neighbour. Negative tidal indices indicate that the galaxy is in an isolated environment while large positive indices indicate that the galaxy is in a dense environment. The TI values were primarily taken from the Local Volume (LV) catalogue ([Karachentsev et al., 2014](#)); for some of the galaxies with significant changes in the estimated distance, they were recomputed and corrected using the updated information in the extragalactic database, HyperLeda. Fig. 4.4 (b) shows the plot of $d_{j,b}$ versus tidal index. There is some indication that galaxies with higher tidal

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indices also have lower specific angular momentum, however, the trend is not as clear as it is in the case of the mass (Fig.4.4 (a)). Further, for our sample, the galaxies with larger tidal index, also tend to be the ones with higher baryonic mass. We have indicated all the galaxies with masses higher than $10^{9.1} M_{\odot}$ by a circle around their respective symbols. In Fig. 4.4 (b), we do not see any trend for specific angular momentum to decrease with higher tidal index if we ignore the high-mass galaxies ($> 10^{9.1} M_{\odot}$).

4.4.5 Preferential loss of low angular momentum gas via stellar feedback

One possibility discussed by [Chowdhury and Chengalur \(2017\)](#) is that the specific angular momentum in the dwarfs has been increased by preferential loss of low angular momentum gas. This is a natural consequence of stellar feedback, in situations where the star formation is concentrated near the galaxy center (i.e. a region of low specific angular momentum) and the mass loss happens preferentially along the minor axis of the galaxy (see e.g. [Brook et al., 2011](#)). Such situations arise naturally in dwarf galaxies, and result in stellar feedback processes preferentially removing low angular momentum gas from the central parts of dwarfs, thus increasing the specific angular momentum of the remaining gas. Mechanical energy input from stellar feedback would also increase the thickness of the disc. While this qualitatively looks like an attractive explanation, it would be interesting to check if we can confirm that the amount of star formation in these galaxies is sufficient to produce the observed increase in the specific angular momentum. This is a particular concern for the extremely gas rich galaxies in our sample, since they have a small fractional stellar mass, and it is unclear that the star formation would be sufficient to change the specific angular momentum by the observed factor.

To estimate the expected increase in the specific angular momentum because of preferential loss of low specific angular momentum gas, we firstly assume that the $j_b - M_b$ curves for the bulgeless spirals and dwarfs are approximately parallel (since the measured slopes agree with error bars). If we call the factor by which the dwarfs specific momentum is larger than that of the spirals as β , then the offset between the lines in Fig. 4.1 corresponds to $\log_{10}(\beta) = 0.53 \pm 0.09$, which corresponds to $\beta = 3.4 \pm 0.21$. For the purpose of making an approximate estimate of the required mass loss, we assume,

Figure 4.4: (a) $d_{j,b}$ versus baryon mass and (b) $d_{j,b}$ versus tidal index. 11 dwarf galaxies residing in Lynx-Cancer void from this work (black open circles), and the dwarf galaxies from the literature (symbols are the same as in previous figures). 5 massive spiral galaxies with bulge fraction, $\beta < 0.05$ from [Obreschkow and Glazebrook \(2014\)](#) are shown by cyan pentagons. The galaxies with masses higher than $10^{9.1} M_{\odot}$ are indicated by a circle around their respective symbols.

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that to zeroth order the discs are marginally stable, so that their mass and angular momentum are given by Eqn. 4.3 and 4.4 respectively. If we assume that outflows remove all of the material within a fractional radius α , (i.e. all of the material between the galaxy centre and αR_0 is lost), then from these same equations one can work out that the mass will decrease by the factor $(1 - \alpha)$ and the offset in $j_b - M_b$ plane will increase by the factor $\log_{10}((1 + \alpha)/(1 - \alpha))$. This allows us to solve for α , yielding $\alpha = 0.55 \pm 0.07$, or that about half of the original baryonic mass needs to be lost. From the simulations including stellar feedback (e.g. Brook et al., 2011), the mass loading factor (i.e. the ratio of the mass loss rate to the star formation rate) is ~ 2.3 . This is also the ratio between the total mass lost and the total stellar mass. From the data in Table 4.2 the average M_*/M_b is ~ 0.08 , which for a mass loading factor of 2.3 corresponds to a total fractional mass loss of 0.16, significantly smaller than the value of $\alpha = 0.55 \pm 0.07$ required to explain the offset in the $j_b - M_b$ plane. We note that the assumption that all of the material internal to αR_0 is lost is an overestimate, and hence our calculation of the increase in the specific angular momentum is also an overestimate. Thus the conclusion that the observed star formation is insufficient to increase the specific angular momentum by the observed amount appears robust. On the other hand, the mass loading factor includes only mass that escapes from the galaxy altogether. In principle, it is sufficient that the mass is converted into a form (e.g. ionized gas) that drops out from our baryon budget. While this is a possible solution, there is no clear observational evidence that the ionized medium contains a significant fraction of the baryonic mass in dwarf galaxies.

Given that there appears to be problems with increasing the specific angular momentum entirely by preferential loss of low angular momentum gas, it is worth considering what other possible mechanisms could be relevant. One such, suggested earlier by Chowdhury and Chengalur (2017) in the context of the high specific angular momentum of dwarfs, is the cold accretion of high angular momentum gas (see also e.g. Danovich et al. (2015)). This mechanism, if operative, would of course result in increasing the specific angular momentum of dwarf discs (discussed in more detail in next chapter). One could speculate that it would result in an increased disc thickness because of increased turbulence caused by the accretion, but it is unclear as to why cold accretion should be more relevant for dwarfs as compared to bulgeless spirals. We return to this discussion in chapter 5, where we study the relation between gas specific

angular momentum and gas mass of a diverse sample of galaxies to develop holistic understanding of role of angular momentum in galaxy formation and evolution.

4.5 Summary and Conclusions

In summary, we have measured the specific angular momentum of 11 void dwarf galaxies and find them to be larger than would be expected from an extrapolation of the trends seen for bulgeless spirals. We compare the specific angular momentum of dwarf galaxies that lie in voids with that of dwarfs that lie outside voids and find that they have similar specific angular momentum (§4.3.1). As such, our data does not show any correlation between the specific angular momentum and the large scale environment. We hence derive the relation between the baryonic specific angular momentum and mass for dwarf galaxies by combining our data with that for other dwarfs for which data is available in the literature (§4.3.2). We find that the dwarf galaxies with masses lower than $\sim 10^{9.1} M_{\odot}$ have significantly higher baryonic specific angular momentum than expected from the relation for bulgeless spiral galaxies (§4.4.4). Interestingly this threshold is very similar to the mass threshold below which the galaxy discs start to become systematically thicker (Sánchez-Janssen et al., 2010). This finding gives qualitative support to earlier suggestions that both of these processes may arise because of a common physical mechanism, such as feedback from star formation. Stellar feedback processes preferentially remove low angular momentum gas from the central parts of dwarfs (thus increasing the specific angular momentum of the remaining gas) and the input mechanical energy also leads to an increase in the velocity dispersion and to a thickening of the discs. In detail, however, we find that the observed amount of star formation in our sample galaxies is insufficient to produce the observed increase in the specific angular momentum (§4.4.2). We suggest that other mechanisms, such as for example, cold mode accretion of high specific angular momentum gas, may also be playing a role (we return to this in the next chapter).

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5

The HI angular momentum-mass relation

This chapter is based on Sushma Kurapati, Jayaram N. Chengalur, Marc A.W. Verheijen, MNRAS (submitted).

5.1 Introduction

Studies of the correlations between global parameters of galaxies (e.g. rotation velocity vs. luminosity, or star formation rate vs. stellar mass) provide critical observational tests of galaxy formation and evolution models. One specific parameter which is receiving increasing attention is angular momentum. This is in part because that it is only now that, thanks to large IFU surveys as well as large HI surveys, measurements of angular momentum are becoming available for a sizeable number of galaxies (e.g. [Walter et al., 2008](#); [Hunter et al., 2012](#); [Sánchez et al., 2012](#); [Bryant et al., 2015](#); [Bundy et al., 2015](#); [Stott et al., 2016](#)). Further, our theoretical understanding of how galaxies acquire angular momentum is also rapidly evolving as numerical models become more sophisticated and better able to capture the details of the physics of the baryonic component of galaxies.

As discussed earlier in §4.1, tidal torquing models predict that the specific angular momentum of the dark matter halos scales with the mass as $j_H \propto M_H^{2/3}$ ([Peebles, 1969](#)) and a similar scaling is expected for baryonic components if we assume that the baryonic matter and dark matter have similar distributions at early times and that the

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angular momentum is conserved during galaxy evolution. It has been found that such a scaling relation is indeed obtained for the stellar component of galaxies (e.g. [Fall, 1983](#); [Romanowsky and Fall, 2012](#); [Posti et al., 2018](#); [Fall and Romanowsky, 2018](#)), while the $j_b - M_b$ relation is more nuanced than a simple $j_b \propto M_b^{2/3}$ scaling. For e.g. [Obreschkow and Glazebrook \(2014\)](#) find $j_b \propto M_b$ at a fixed bulge fraction, while they find $j_b \propto M_b^{2/3}$ across the entire sample (see [4.1](#) for more details). In the previous chapter, we find that gas rich dwarf galaxies appear to have an excess specific angular momentum compared to that expected from the scaling relation for bulgeless spirals (see [§4.3.2](#) of chapter 4; [Butler et al. \(2017\)](#); [Chowdhury and Chengalur \(2017\)](#)). We also find that the elevation in specific angular momentum occurs for the galaxies with masses lower than $10^{9.1} M_\odot$ (see [§4.4.4](#) of chapter 4).

These observations can be explained if we assume that the baryonic-specific angular momentum depends on the evolutionary processes, rather than on the initial angular momentum of the dark halo. The recent numerical simulations of galaxy formation (e.g. [Desmond et al., 2017](#); [Jiang et al., 2019](#)) show that the collapsed baryonic component of galaxies does not arise solely from the cooling and contraction of the initial hot baryonic component of the proto-halo. Both mergers as well as ‘cold’ flows of baryonic material along filaments that penetrate deep into the halo (e.g. [Kereš et al., 2005, 2009](#); [Brooks et al., 2009](#)) could result in a significant change in the final baryonic mass as well as the final angular momentum. The effect on the angular momentum depends on whether the merger was ‘wet’ (i.e. with a gaseous progenitor) or dry (i.e. with a gas poor progenitor) as well as the relative orientation of the spin of the incoming material vis a vis that of the galaxy (see e.g. [Naab et al., 2014](#); [Lagos et al., 2018](#)). Additionally, the final baryonic mass as well as angular momentum is affected by the energy input from stellar winds and supernovae which could cause an outflow of material from the galaxy. The strength of the outflows depends on whether the supernovae explosions are clustered or not. Since clustering of supernovae typically happens only near the centres of galaxies (i.e. in regions where the material has low specific angular momentum, (sAM)) outflows lead to a preferential loss of low specific angular momentum material. This results in an increase in the specific angular momentum of the remaining material in the galaxy ([Brook et al., 2011](#); [Dutton, 2009](#); [Sharma et al., 2012](#)). As a consequence of these processes the angular momentum of the galaxy is not fixed during its formation phase, but rather is affected by the entire

evolutionary path of the galaxy. Both the morphology as well as the angular momentum appear to be driven more by evolutionary processes and a galaxy’s merger history than the original spin parameter of the dark matter halo (see e.g. [Jiang et al., 2019](#); [Stewart et al., 2017](#); [Zjupa and Springel, 2017](#); [Renzini, 2020](#)). For e.g. simulations show that accretion of low sAM or counter rotating gas leads to a central compact galaxy (“blue nugget”), with a spheroidal stellar distribution, and possibly an outer counter-rotating disc, while accretion of co-rotating material typically leads to a disc type galaxy with gas density stable against rapid gravitational collapse (see e.g. [Jiang et al., 2019](#); [Zolotov et al., 2015](#); [Kretschmer et al., 2020](#)).

Here we use interferometric HI observations to study the relation between the baryonic specific angular momentum and mass, as well as that between the HI specific angular momentum (j_{gas}) and HI mass (M_{gas}) for a diverse sample of gas rich galaxies including HI-bearing ultra-diffuse galaxies (HUDs), normal dwarf galaxies, spiral galaxies, and early-type galaxies. We discuss the results in terms of the range of simulations discussed above. This chapter is organized as follows. In §5.2, we describe the sample and observations. In § 5.3, we determine the gas angular momentum and gas mass relation and finally, we summarize the main results in § 5.5.

5.2 Sample

Our sample consists of a wide variety of galaxies including dwarf galaxies, HI bearing ultra diffuse galaxies, spiral galaxies, as well as early-type galaxies. The dwarf galaxy sample is drawn from previous works on the specific angular momentum of dwarf galaxies, viz., void dwarf galaxies from [Kurapati et al. \(2018\)](#), field dwarf galaxies from [Butler et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Chowdhury and Chengalur \(2017\)](#). The HI bearing ultra-diffuse galaxies (HUDs) were selected from the restrictive sample of [Leisman et al. \(2017\)](#), with half light radii $r_{g,\text{eff}} > 1.5$ kpc, $\mu_{g,0} > 24$ mag arcsec⁻², and $M_g > -16.8$ mag, i.e. extreme stellar sizes as expected from their stellar magnitudes. We used new Giant Metrewave Radio Telescope (GMRT) observations to obtain HI morphologies and kinematics of 2 HUDs as part of a pilot study for a larger survey. The total intensity maps and velocity fields for these two galaxies are shown in Figure 5.1. We derive the rotation curve for these galaxies using Fully Automated TiRiFiC (FAT; [Kamphuis et al., 2015](#)) by fitting a tilted ring model to the data cube. The data reduction and the procedure used for

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the derivation of rotation curves is discussed in detail in 2.3 and 2.5 of chapter 2. The derived rotation curves for ultra-diffuse galaxies are shown in Figure 5.2.

Spiral galaxies are taken from the samples of Verheijen and Sancisi (2001) and Obreschkow and Glazebrook (2014). Verheijen and Sancisi (2001) presented results from a synthesis imaging survey of 43 galaxies in the nearby Ursa Major region using the Westerbork Synthesis Radio Telescope (WSRT). We require a sample of galaxies where rotation curves can be reliably derived. Hence, we consider only those galaxies from this sample that are well resolved across the major axis and exclude the galaxies that are in interacting pairs or that have disturbed velocity fields. Only 16 of 43 galaxies remain after the imposition of these criteria. We use K' band luminosity profiles (as measured in Verheijen (2001)) to calculate the stellar mass profiles since the uncertainties in the derivation of the mass to light ratio are much less in the mid-infrared compared to the optical. We assume a constant K' band mass to light ratio of 0.24 to calculate the stellar surface density profiles (Ponomareva et al., 2018). We use the rotation curves and the radial HI surface density profiles from Verheijen (2001) to calculate the baryonic and gas specific angular momentum.

The early-type galaxies were selected from the ATLAS^{3D} HI survey of a volume-limited, complete sample of 166 nearby early-type galaxies (ETGs) brighter than $M_K = -21.5$ (Serra et al., 2012). In constructing the sub-sample we first restrict the selection to galaxies with morphologies later than $T > -4.0$. Serra et al. (2012) divided the galaxies with detected HI into four morphological classes, viz. (i) large discs - most of the HI rotates regularly and is distributed in a disc or ring larger than the stellar body of the galaxy, (ii) small discs - most of the HI rotates regularly and is distributed in a small disc confined within the stellar body of the galaxy, (iii) unsettled - most of the HI exhibits an unsettled morphology (e.g. tails or stream of gas) and kinematics, and (iv) clouds - the HI is found in small, scattered clouds around the galaxy. In order to calculate the angular momentum accurately, we require a sample where reliable rotation curves can be derived. Hence, we have considered only the galaxies from the first class, i.e. those with large discs that have regular velocity fields. We show their total intensity maps and velocity fields in Figures 5.3, 5.4, 5.5 and 5.6. We derived the rotation curve for these galaxies using FAT on the final ATLAS^{3D} data products, i.e. HI cubes with a typical angular resolution of ~ 35 arcsecs. Our final sample consists of those galaxies for which reliable rotation curves could be obtained by FAT. We use

^{3D}Barolo (Di Teodoro and Fraternali, 2015, ; determines the rotation curve by fitting a tilted ring model to the 3-D data cube) to derive the rotation curve for one of the galaxy (NGC 3941), since the FAT derived rotation curve was unreliable. The derived rotation curves for the final sample of early-type galaxies are shown in Fig 5.7. Two of the early-type galaxies (NGC3626 and NGC3941) have companions, which were excluded for the measurements of mass and specific angular momentum.

We calculate the specific angular momentum of all the galaxies by using the equation 4.1 of chapter 4. In Tables 5.1 and 5.2, we present the measurements of stellar, gas, and baryonic mass and specific angular momentum of UMa spiral galaxies and ultra-diffuse galaxies respectively: The columns are as follows. Column (1) name of the galaxy; (2) stellar mass ; (3) gas mass; (4) total baryonic mass; (5) stellar specific angular momentum; (6) gas specific angular momentum and (7) baryonic specific angular momentum. In Table 5.3 we show the properties and the measurements of the gas mass and gas specific angular momentum of the early-type galaxies. The columns are as follows. Column (1) name of the galaxy; (2) morphology ; (3) distance in Mpc (4) gas mass; (5) gas specific angular momentum and (6) Notes on galaxies.

5.3 Results

5.3.1 Specific angular momentum of the HI disc

As discussed in the introduction, recent simulations indicate that the angular momentum of galaxies is governed more by evolutionary processes and the physics of the baryonic material than by the the initial spin of the dark matter halo. Numerical simulations also support the picture that star formation occurs in marginally stable gas discs, where inflows provide both the gas required for the star formation, as well as energy to keep the discs marginally stable against gravitational instability (e.g. Dekel et al. (2013)). Models of disc galaxies where the discs are critically stable also appear to provide a reasonable description of the specific angular momentum-mass relation of the gas discs of local galaxies (see e.g. §4.4.1 of chapter 4; Romeo (2020); Zasov (1974); Zasov and Zaitseva (2017)). Observational constraints on models where the gas mass and angular momentum of HI discs are set by the requirement that the disc be critically stable have been presented by for e.g. Zasov and Zaitseva (2017); Obreschkow et al. (2016). It would hence be interesting to look at how well such models fit the HI

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Figure 5.1: Top left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $42.12'' \times 37.76''$ on the SDSS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy AGC121790. The HI contours start at a column density $8 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Top Right: velocity field for the ultra-diffuse galaxy AGC121790. Velocity contours run from 2906 to 2966 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 6 km s^{-1} . Bottom left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $13.32'' \times 9.72''$ on the DECaLS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy AGC749401. The HI contours start at a column density $9 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Bottom right: velocity field for the ultra-diffuse galaxy AGC749401. Velocity contours run from 2710 to 2763 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 6 km s^{-1} .

Figure 5.2: Rotation curves of ultra-diffuse galaxies.

Figure 5.3: Top left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $59.04'' \times 32.36''$ on the DECaLS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy NGC3626. The HI contours start at a column density $1.1 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Top Right: velocity field for the galaxy NGC3626. Velocity contours run from 1280 to 1660 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 20 km s^{-1} . Bottom left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $79.2'' \times 30.2''$ on the SDSS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy NGC4262. The HI contours start at a column density $9.1 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Bottom right: velocity field for the galaxy NGC4262. Velocity contours run from 1175 to 1525 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 25 km s^{-1} .

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Figure 5.4: Top left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $42.84'' \times 33.41''$ on the DECaLS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy NGC4278. The HI contours start at a column density $1.5 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Top Right: velocity field for the galaxy NGC4278. Velocity contours run from 400 to 825 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 25 km s^{-1} . Bottom left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $38.16'' \times 36.00''$ on the SDSS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy NGC5582. The HI contours start at a column density $1.5 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Bottom right: velocity field for the galaxy NGC5582. Velocity contours run from 1225 to 1600 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 25 km s^{-1} .

Figure 5.5: Top left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $38.16'' \times 36.97''$ on the PanSTARRS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy NGC6798. The HI contours start at a column density $1.5 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner, Top Right: velocity field for the galaxy NGC6798. Velocity contours run from 2200 to 2500 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 15 km s^{-1} . Bottom left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $38.88'' \times 35.96''$ on the PanSTARRS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy NGC3941. The HI contours start at a column density $1.5 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Bottom right: velocity field for the galaxy NGC3941. Velocity contours run from 800 to 1025 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 25 km s^{-1} .

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Figure 5.6: Top left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $51.48'' \times 33.12''$ on the DECaLS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy UGC6176. The HI contours start at a column density $1.3 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Top Right: velocity field for the galaxy UGC6176. Velocity contours run from 2575 to 2775 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 25 km s^{-1} . Bottom left: An overlay of the integrated HI emission (contours) at a resolution $39.96'' \times 35.63''$ on the PanSTARRS optical image (grey scale) of the galaxy UGC9519. The HI contours start at a column density $1.5 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and are rising in multiples of $\sqrt{2}$. The beam size is also shown in the bottom-left corner. Bottom right: velocity field for the galaxy UGC9519. Velocity contours run from 1560 to 1680 km s^{-1} with a spacing of 20 km s^{-1} .

Figure 5.7: Rotation curves of early-type galaxies. Error bars on NGC4278 are taken to be the velocity resolution of the data cube (13 km s^{-1} , which is greater than median of FAT errors of all galaxies) since FAT errors were unreliable.

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Table 5.1: Measured values of specific angular momentum and mass (stars, gas, and baryons) for UMa spiral galaxies in this study

Galaxy	dist (Mpc)	M_s ($\log_{10} M_\odot$)	M_{gas} ($\log_{10} M_\odot$)	M_b ($\log_{10} M_\odot$)	j_s (\log_{10} kpc km/s)	j_{gas} (\log_{10} kpc km/s)	j_b (\log_{10} kpc km/s)
NGC3877	15.27	10.6 ± 0.13	9.14 ± 0.137	10.62 ± 0.126	2.87 ± 0.065	3.04 ± 0.065	2.88 ± 0.065
NGC3917	17.14	10.13 ± 0.13	9.34 ± 0.137	10.19 ± 0.114	2.75 ± 0.065	3.07 ± 0.065	2.81 ± 0.065
NGC3953	18.82	10.73 ± 0.13	9.62 ± 0.137	10.76 ± 0.121	3.14 ± 0.065	3.46 ± 0.065	3.17 ± 0.065
NGC3972	20.04	10.10 ± 0.13	9.31 ± 0.137	10.16 ± 0.114	2.70 ± 0.065	2.98 ± 0.065	2.75 ± 0.065
NGC3992	27.04	10.91 ± 0.13	10.23 ± 0.137	11.0 ± 0.110	3.36 ± 0.065	3.84 ± 0.065	3.49 ± 0.065
NGC4013	19.23	10.81 ± 0.13	9.65 ± 0.137	10.84 ± 0.122	2.93 ± 0.065	3.42 ± 0.065	2.99 ± 0.065
NGC4100	20.04	10.62 ± 0.13	9.74 ± 0.137	10.67 ± 0.116	3.01 ± 0.065	3.39 ± 0.065	3.07 ± 0.065
NGC4157	16.29	10.87 ± 0.13	9.96 ± 0.137	10.92 ± 0.117	2.92 ± 0.065	3.40 ± 0.065	3.01 ± 0.065
NGC4183	17.21	10.12 ± 0.13	9.65 ± 0.137	10.25 ± 0.103	2.76 ± 0.065	3.06 ± 0.065	2.85 ± 0.065
NGC4217	18.19	10.75 ± 0.13	9.53 ± 0.137	10.78 ± 0.123	2.97 ± 0.065	3.27 ± 0.065	2.99 ± 0.065
UGC6399	22.08	9.48 ± 0.13	9.19 ± 0.137	9.66 ± 0.098	2.54 ± 0.066	2.79 ± 0.066	2.64 ± 0.066
UGC6446	18.03	8.83 ± 0.13	9.62 ± 0.137	9.69 ± 0.120	2.29 ± 0.066	2.88 ± 0.066	2.83 ± 0.066
UGC6667	18.45	9.80 ± 0.13	9.06 ± 0.137	9.87 ± 0.112	2.67 ± 0.065	2.70 ± 0.065	2.67 ± 0.065
UGC6917	20.41	9.42 ± 0.13	9.54 ± 0.137	9.78 ± 0.096	2.67 ± 0.065	2.99 ± 0.065	2.88 ± 0.065
UGC6983	21.28	9.29 ± 0.13	9.74 ± 0.137	9.87 ± 0.107	2.62 ± 0.065	3.08 ± 0.065	3.00 ± 0.065
UGC7089	11.50	9.06 ± 0.13	8.80 ± 0.137	9.25 ± 0.097	2.19 ± 0.066	2.54 ± 0.066	2.34 ± 0.066

Table 5.2: Measured values of specific angular momentum and mass (stars, gas, and baryons) for ultra-diffuse galaxies in this study

Galaxy	dist (Mpc)	M_s ($\log_{10} M_\odot$)	M_{gas} ($\log_{10} M_\odot$)	M_b ($\log_{10} M_\odot$)	j_s (\log_{10} kpc km/s)	j_{gas} (\log_{10} kpc km/s)	j_b (\log_{10} kpc km/s)
AGC749401	41.8	7.31 ± 0.13	8.66 ± 0.137	8.68 ± 0.126	2.12 ± 0.065	2.39 ± 0.065	2.39 ± 0.065
AGC121790	37.5	6.40 ± 0.13	8.89 ± 0.137	8.89 ± 0.126	2.00 ± 0.065	2.46 ± 0.065	2.46 ± 0.065

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Figure 5.8: $\log j_{\text{gas}} - \log M_{\text{gas}}$ of 2 HUDs (magenta triangles) from this work, 11 dwarfs residing in Lynx-Cancer void (black circles) from [Kurapati et al. \(2018\)](#), 17 field dwarfs (red diamonds from [Butler et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Chowdhury and Chengalur \(2017\)](#)), 16 spirals residing in the UMa cluster (plus symbols) from this work, and 15 spirals from OG14. The green line indicates the best fit for the $j_{\text{gas}} - M_{\text{gas}}$ relation using the linear regression. The blue line represents the stability criterion ($j_{\text{HI}} \times 11 \text{ km s}^{-1} / (G M_{\text{HI}}) \sim 1$) from [Romeo \(2020\)](#)

Table 5.3: Measured values of gas mass and gas specific angular momentum of 6 S0 and 2 elliptical galaxies in this study

Galaxy	Morphology	dist (Mpc)	M_{gas} ($\log_{10} M_{\odot}$)	j_{gas} ($\log_{10} \text{kpc km s}^{-1}$)	Notes
NGC3626	S0	19.5	9.19 ± 0.137	3.60 ± 0.067	C
NGC4262	S0	15.4	8.84 ± 0.137	3.27 ± 0.066	R
NGC4278	E	15.6	8.90 ± 0.137	3.64 ± 0.070	M, L
NGC5582	E	27.7	9.78 ± 0.137	3.85 ± 0.066	R
NGC3941	S0	11.9	8.86 ± 0.137	3.15 ± 0.067	C, R
NGC6798	S0	37.5	9.64 ± 0.137	3.67 ± 0.074	C
UGC6176	S0	40.1	9.21 ± 0.137	3.21 ± 0.066	W
UGC9519	S0	27.6	9.40 ± 0.137	3.02 ± 0.068	M

Notes on HI morphology and kinematics:

C = HI counter-rotating relative to the stellar kinematics; L= lopsided HI morphology;

M= HI misaligned relative to the stellar kinematics; R= ring; W= warp

specific angular momentum (j_{gas}) and the HI mass (M_{gas}) for our heterogeneous sample of galaxies.

We show in Fig. 5.8 the HI specific angular momentum and HI gas mass relation for our sample galaxies. Interestingly, the galaxies show a smooth $j_{\text{gas}} - M_{\text{gas}}$ relation across the entire mass range in contrast to $j_{\text{b}} - M_{\text{b}}$ relation (see §4.4.4 of chapter 4). We estimate the best fitting linear regression between j_{gas} and M_{gas} by using the BCES algorithm (Akritas and Bershady, 1996) that accounts for errors on both j_{gas} and M_{gas} as well as for the fact that these errors are correlated. The best-fit $j_{\text{gas}} - M_{\text{gas}}$ relation is given by, $j_{\text{gas}} = qM_{\text{gas}}^{\alpha}$ with $\alpha = 0.87 \pm 0.05$ and $\log_{10} q = -5.20 \pm 0.41$. We do not include early-type galaxies to fit the $j_{\text{gas}} - M_{\text{gas}}$ relation since these galaxies are peculiar in that the gas is counter-rotating or misaligned with the stellar kinematics. We discuss these galaxies further below. The existence of such a relation between the HI mass and the HI specific angular momentum (suggested earlier also by for e.g. Zasov (1974)) is interesting in itself, and we return to this in Sec. 5.4. We also note that the slope that we find for the $j_{\text{gas}} - M_{\text{gas}}$ relation is significantly different from that seen for the $j_{\text{s}} - M_{\text{s}}$ relation (i.e. 0.55 ± 0.02) by Posti et al. (2019). We return to a discussion of this in Sec. 5.4. Here we focus on how the relation that we find compares with expectations from the critically stable disc model (see also §4.4.1 of chapter 4).

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The commonly used criterion for stability is the Toomre Q parameter. Strictly speaking, the Toomre criterion is for a thin single component disc, while at least some of the galaxies that we are analysing have significant stellar masses as well as a non negligible disc thickness. Issues associated with applying the Toomre-Q criterion to such galaxies have been discussed in detail in [Zasov and Zaitseva \(2017\)](#) and [Romeo \(2020\)](#). [Romeo \(2020\)](#) in particular takes a phenomenological approach, and suggests that the different components (molecular, atomic, stellar) of galaxy discs follow scaling laws derived from the relation

$$\frac{j_i \hat{\sigma}_i}{GM_i} \approx 1$$

where $\hat{\sigma}_i = \bar{\sigma}_i/A_i$, with $\bar{\sigma}_i$ being the disc averaged velocity dispersion of component i (HI, H₂, or stars), and A_i is the mass averaged Toomre-Q parameter. The value of $\hat{\sigma}_i$ is not derived from fundamental principals, but is instead determined by a fit to observational data. [Romeo \(2020\)](#) uses data from [Leroy et al. \(2008\)](#) (which overlaps with the [Obreschkow and Glazebrook \(2014\)](#) sample) to determine the value for $\hat{\sigma}_i$. For the HI component the derived value is 11 km/s. We show this empirical relation, $\log(j) = \log(M) - 6.41$ (with $\hat{\sigma}_i = 11$ km/s) in [Fig. 5.8](#). As can be seen, it provides a good fit to the data, the majority of which is independent from the sample used by [Romeo \(2020\)](#). This further supports the idea that the structure of the HI discs in galaxies settles to a critical density, as would happen in models where the star formation rate (and hence mass outflow rate) is driven by the mass inflow rate.

As discussed in the introduction, simulations also show that spheroidal stellar distributions with extended counter-rotating gas discs could arise in systems where there has been a recent accretion of gas whose spin is not aligned with that of the parent galaxy (e.g. [Kretschmer et al., 2020](#)). In the context of such models it would be interesting to examine the position of extremely gas rich early-type galaxies in the $j_{\text{gas}} - M_{\text{gas}}$ plane. As can be seen from [Table 1](#), for many of the galaxies in our sample the gas is counter-rotating or misaligned with the stellar kinematics, consistent with results from simulations. [Figure 5.9](#) shows the location of early-type galaxies, as well as all our other sample galaxies in the $j_{\text{gas}} - M_{\text{gas}}$ plane. The green solid line indicates the best fit line using the linear regression for all the galaxies except the early-type galaxies and green dotted lines indicate 3σ intrinsic scatter. As can be seen, most of the early-type galaxies lie above the 3σ scatter, i.e. their HI discs have significantly higher

Figure 5.9: The location of early-type galaxies with large regular HI discs (blue open triangles) and the other galaxies (symbols are the same as in previous figures) in the $j_{\text{gas}}\text{--}M_{\text{gas}}$ plane. The green solid line indicates the best fit line using the linear regression for all the galaxies except early-type galaxies. The green dotted lines indicate 3σ scatter around the relation. The HI discs in gas rich early-type galaxies have high specific angular momentum compared to other galaxies with similar HI mass.

specific angular momentum as compared to other galaxies with the same HI mass. A Kolmogorov–Smirnov (KS) test gives a probability of 7×10^{-4} for the early-type galaxies being drawn from the same distribution as the other galaxies. Our observations hence support the picture in which these gas rich S0 galaxies have acquired the gas via a recent inflow of high, but misaligned sAM gas. The elevated specific angular momentum is consistent with the decreased star formation efficiency of early-type galaxies since higher angular momentum stabilizes the gas against Jeans instabilities and subsequent star formation (Toomre, 1964; Obreschkow et al., 2016).

5.3.2 Baryonic Specific Angular Momentum

Several earlier studies (see §4.3 of chapter 4; Obreschkow and Glazebrook (2014)) had studied the correlation between the specific angular momentum and mass of the bary-

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Figure 5.10: The $\log j_b$ - $\log M_b$ plane. The black solid line is the best fit line for the dwarf galaxies from Kurapati et al. (2018). The symbols are the same as in previous figure. The cyan dotted line indicates the $\beta = 0$ plane, the magenta dotted line indicates $\beta = 0.1$ plane, and the yellow dotted line indicates $\beta = 0.2$ plane of j_b - M_b relation obtained for the massive spiral galaxies by OG14.

onic (i.e. gas + stars) component of galaxies. In chapter 4, we have investigated the relation considering the baryonic mass for a sample of gas rich dwarf galaxies in a range of environments, using the bulgeless spiral relation found by [Obreschkow and Glazebrook \(2014\)](#) for comparison. We found that the baryonic specific angular momentum of dwarfs was higher as compared to the extrapolation of the trend seen for higher mass bulge-less spirals. The increase in specific angular momentum was found to set in at a mass threshold of $10^{9.1} M_{\odot}$ (see §4.4.4 of chapter 4).

Fig. 5.10 shows the relation between the baryonic specific angular momentum and the baryonic mass for the galaxies in the chapter 4 (including void dwarf galaxies and galaxies from literature) along with the data from the UMa sample of spiral galaxies. We do not use the early-type galaxies for this analysis since, as discussed above for these galaxies the gas does not in general co-rotate with the stars. The added data points from UMa connect the dwarf galaxies and spiral galaxies from [Obreschkow and Glazebrook \(2014\)](#) and further strengthen the conclusion that there is a break in the relation around a baryonic mass of $10^{9.1} M_{\odot}$. We note that in the case of the UMa galaxies, we have not included the contribution of molecular gas, since these measurements are not available. Since the molecular gas can be assumed to be co-rotating with the HI and generally is more compact than the HI disc, the addition of this contribution would result in an increase in the baryonic mass, as well as a decrease in the average specific angular momentum. This would only increase their deviation from the relation for gas rich dwarfs, leaving the conclusion that there is a break in the $j_b - M_b$ relation around $10^{9.1} M_{\odot}$ unchanged.

In chapter 4, we had examined a number of possible reasons for the excess specific angular momentum of the gas rich dwarfs, as well as the break in the relation at $10^{9.1} M_{\odot}$. One possible explanation is that feedback due to star formation preferentially removes low specific angular momentum gas (since star formation tends to be concentrated in the central regions of galaxies). Since outflowing gas is more easily lost from dwarf galaxies as compared to larger spirals, this could lead to the remaining gas in dwarfs having a larger specific angular momentum than spirals. However, in chapter 4, we show that the observed star formation in the sample dwarfs is not sufficient to explain the observed excess specific angular momentum (see §4.4.5). Instead, we suggested that other evolutionary processes, including inflow of high angular momentum gas, or gas rich mergers of prograde progenitors (as expected to occur along filaments

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e.g. [Beygu et al. \(2013\)](#); [Chengalur et al. \(2017\)](#)) could be responsible for the excess specific angular momentum of gas rich dwarfs. The observations of the high specific angular momentum of the recently acquired gas discs of early type galaxies reinforces the importance of late stage inflows/ mergers in determining the specific angular momentum.

In this context, it is worth noting that cold flows are expected to be more important in the build up of the baryonic component of low mass galaxies (e.g. [Brooks et al. \(2009\)](#)). In a recent paper, [Dekel et al. \(2019\)](#) find that there is a mass threshold for disc formation at a stellar mass of $\sim 10^9 M_{\odot}$; for lower mass galaxies disc formation is disrupted by spin flips by frequent mergers. Above this threshold, wet compactions lead to long lived extended gas rings. This would suggest that low mass galaxies have lower specific angular momentum, i.e. a trend reverse to what we observe. One resolution to this apparent contradiction is that our sample is specifically of gas rich dwarfs; this selection criterion could favour low mass galaxies which have undergone fewer mergers; or that the mergers tended to be with gas rich progenitors on prograde orbits. We return to a discussion of the possible reasons for the break seen in the $j_b - M_b$ relation in the next section.

We also draw attention to one more feature in [Fig. 5.10](#), the location of the ultra-diffuse dwarfs. Ultra-diffuse dwarf galaxies (UDGs) are a recently discovered population of very low surface brightness galaxies, which have stellar masses of dwarfs, but have sizes as large as L_* galaxies ([van Dokkum et al., 2015](#)). The majority of the UDGs are red and appear more common in clusters. However, galaxies with similar optical properties to the cluster UDGs have also been identified in less dense environments. HI-bearing ultra-diffuse galaxies (HUDs), which have similarly diffuse optical discs as those of UDGs were recently discovered in the HI survey of [Leisman et al. \(2017\)](#). However, HUDs are bluer and have significant reservoirs of HI as compared to the UDGs in clusters. Several formation scenarios have been proposed to explain the formation of the UDGs. Some authors propose a scenario in which UDGs are failed Milky Way like galaxies which lost their gas after forming the first stars ([van Dokkum et al., 2015](#)) and others argue that they are genuinely dwarf galaxies residing in high spin parameter halos ([Amorisco and Loeb, 2016](#)). These formation scenarios can be tested by measuring the angular momentum of UDGs and comparing them to the normal dwarf galaxies. [Figure 5.10](#) shows the baryonic specific angular momentum versus the

baryonic mass of HI-bearing UDGs (magenta triangles) and normal dwarf galaxies of similar masses. We find that the specific angular momentum of HI-bearing UDGs is similar to other normal dwarf galaxies at a given mass. This is in contrast with the formation scenarios that predict that UDGs are genuinely dwarf galaxies residing in high spin haloes. We note that our result is in contradiction with a recent analysis by Mancera Piña et al. (2020), who find that ultra diffuse galaxies have higher-than-average *stellar* specific angular momentum, but have circular velocities much lower than galaxies with similar baryonic mass. They assume flat rotation curves and exponential light curves and approximate the stellar specific angular momentum to be the product of circular velocity and the stellar disc scale length since they lack the resolution to integrate angular momentum over the entire disc. This, along with the very small size of our sample, make it important to confirm these results with high resolution observations of a larger sample. Nonetheless, we note that our results here are consistent with the current understanding that the final angular momentum of galaxies is independent of the initial spin parameter of the parent dark matter halo.

5.4 Discussion

As we saw above both the $j_{\text{gas}} - M_{\text{gas}}$ relation as well as the $j_s - M_{\odot}$ relation (Posti et al. (2018)) follow an unbroken power law over the mass range of $10^7 - 10^{10.5} M_{\odot}$. However their slopes are very different, viz. with slopes of 0.87 ± 0.05 (this work) and 0.55 ± 0.02 (Posti et al., 2018) respectively. In contrast to these relations, the $j_b - M_b$ relation is *not* smooth and has a break at $10^{9.1} M_{\odot}$, with dwarf galaxies having higher baryonic specific angular momentum compared to the bulge-less spiral galaxies. We confirm that this break arises because a shift in the relative contributions of the stellar and gas angular momenta to the total baryonic angular momentum. We estimate the expected baryonic specific angular momentum for our sample of galaxies (excluding early-type galaxies, which as discussed above are discrepant) from their stellar mass, gas mass, and the nominal power laws for the $j_{\text{gas}} - M_{\text{gas}}$ and $j_s - M_s$ relations. That is, the expected j_b is given by $j_{b,\text{exp}} = (j_s M_s + j_{\text{gas}} M_{\text{gas}}) / (M_s + M_{\text{gas}})$ where we calculate the j_s and j_{gas} values from the observed stellar and gas mass and the power laws, $j_{\text{gas}} \propto M_{\text{gas}}^{0.87}$ and $j_s \propto M_s^{0.55}$ to calculate the $j_{b,\text{exp}}$. Figure 5.11 shows the observed j_b and the expected j_b from the $j_{\text{gas}} - M_{\text{gas}}$ and the $j_s - M_s$ relations. As can be seen the observed j_b matches the the

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Figure 5.11: The observed j_b versus the expected j_b from the $j_{\text{gas}} - M_{\text{gas}}$ and $j_s - M_{\odot}$ relations. The symbols are the same as in previous figure. Black dotted line shows the $j_b = j_{\text{exp}}$ line.

expected j_b . This supports the idea that the break in the $j_b - M_b$ relation that we see is a consequence of the changing contribution of the stars and gas to the total angular momentum. It also suggests that the high gas fractions of dwarfs and the relatively high $j_{\text{gas}} - M_{\text{gas}}$ slope is primarily responsible for the high baryonic specific angular momentum of dwarf galaxies as compared to the bulge-less spiral galaxies.

How do the power law relations between the specific angular momentum and the mass fit in with the other known scaling relations? To address this question we consider a simple model galaxy where the stars and gas have exponential surface brightness profiles with scale lengths r_s and r_{gas} as well as a flat rotation curve with $V(r) = V_c$. This gives $j \propto V_c r$. From this expression we calculate the expected slope (α_s) for the $j_s - M_\odot$ relation by using the stellar mass size relation, $r_s \propto M_s^{0.28}$ (Bell and de Jong, 2001) and the stellar TF relation, $V_c \propto M_s^{0.31}$ (Bloom et al., 2017), which gives $\alpha_s \sim 0.28 + 0.31 = 0.59$ which compares well with the observed slope of $\sim 0.55 \pm 0.02$. For the gas rich galaxies we use the baryonic TF relation, $V_c \propto M_b^{0.33}$ (Ponomareva et al., 2018) and assume that the baryons are dominated by gas for the dwarf galaxies, which gives $V_c \propto M_{\text{gas}}^{0.33}$. This in combination with the gas mass-size relation $r_{\text{gas}} \propto M_{\text{gas}}^{0.51}$ (Wang et al., 2016) gives the slope (α_{gas}) for the $j_{\text{gas}} - M_{\text{gas}}$ relation, $\alpha_{\text{gas}} \sim 0.51 + 0.33 = 0.84$, in excellent agreement with what we observe. For less gas rich galaxies, if we combine the stellar TF relation $V_c \propto M_s^{0.31}$ from Bloom et al. (2017) and the gas fraction relation $M_{\text{gas}} / M_s = M_s^{-0.53}$ from Romeo (2020), we find $V_c \propto M_{\text{gas}}^{0.66}$ and $\alpha_{\text{gas}} \sim 0.66 + 0.51 = 1.17$ in reasonable agreement with what we observe.

The $j_{\text{gas}} - M_{\text{gas}}$ as well as the $j_s - M_s$ relation are relatively tight compared to the other scaling relations (e.g. stellar size mass relation). The observed vertical scatter for the $j_{\text{gas}} - M_{\text{gas}}$ relation is 0.18 and the intrinsic scatter is 0.16. These values are comparable to the scatter in the baryonic TF relation (e.g. Ponomareva et al., 2018; Lelli et al., 2016; Ponomareva et al., 2017). This supports earlier suggestions of Obreschkow and Glazebrook (2014); Zanisi et al. (2020) that the specific angular momentum-mass relationship is a fundamental relation.

5.5 Summary and Conclusions

We have examined the relation between the HI mass and the HI specific angular momentum for a sample of galaxies with well measured rotation curves that spans

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a range of morphology. We find that the relation is well fit by an unbroken power law over the mass range $10^7 - 10^{10.5} M_{\odot}$. The scatter in this relation is small, and this supports earlier suggestions that the relationship between the angular momentum and mass is a fundamental scaling relation for galaxies. The slope of the power law 0.87 ± 0.05 is also significantly different from that expected from tidal torquing models which predict $j \propto M^{2/3}$, as well as the observed slope of 0.55 ± 0.02 for the stellar component of disc galaxies. Our sample includes two HI bearing ultra-diffuse galaxies, and we find that they lie along the relationship defined by the other galaxies in our sample. The only discrepant galaxies are early-type galaxies with large well rotating discs. These are found to have excess angular momentum compared to that predicted by the relation. In all of these galaxies, the HI disc also appears to be kinematically distinct from the stellar disc, indicating that it represents recently acquired material. Overall, our observations support the suggestions from recent numerical simulations that the kinematics of the baryonic component of galaxies is more affected by cold flows and late stage mergers than by the spin parameter of the parent dark matter halo. Earlier analysis in chapter 4 had indicated a break in the baryonic $j_b - M_b$ relation at a mass of $\sim 10^{9.1} M_{\odot}$. Data from the current sample confirms this break. We show that the break arises because of the change in gas to stellar mass ratio with mass as well as the different slopes of the $j_s - M_s$ and $j_{\text{gas}} - M_{\text{gas}}$ relations.

6

Summary and future work

In this thesis, we used high resolution HI kinematics to derive the rotation curves of galaxies and thereby estimate their angular momentum and dark matter distribution. We investigate the systematics involved in the derivation of rotation curves and their effect on inferred dark matter density profiles. We also study the baryonic/gas specific angular momentum of galaxies residing in different environments and j - M correlation of a diverse sample of galaxies to develop a holistic understanding of the role of angular momentum in galaxy formation and evolution. Here, we summarize some of the key results of the thesis and discuss future plans.

6.1 Summary of results

We have presented HI imaging and kinematics of 24 galaxies residing in the Lynx-Cancer void. This survey has led to discovery of several interesting systems that show signs of interaction and gas accretion. Out of these 24 galaxies, three are in triplets, one is a merger remnant, and one has an extremely extended HI disk. We have detected six neighboring galaxies, all but one of the neighboring galaxies appear to be companions to the target galaxy.

We have selected a sub-sample of 11 galaxies for which rotation curves can be reliably derived. We derive the rotation curves by fitting the tilted ring model to the intensity weighted first moment map (2-D, ROTCUR) and by fitting the tilted ring model directly to the HI data cube (3-D, FAT). The FAT and ROTCUR derived rotation curves are in broad agreement for 8 of the 11 galaxies. The main difference is that the

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inner parts of the rotation curves derived using fat are steeper than those derived using ROTCUR. For the remaining 3 galaxies, the rotation curves derived using the FAT pipeline were unreliable in the central regions. We use FAT rotation curves for studies of dark matter distribution since they are expected to be less affected by projection effects such as beam smearing, but also compare with dark matter distribution derived using 2D rotation curves. Hence, we exclude 3 galaxies for construction of mass models since their FAT derived rotation curves were unreliable in the central regions.

6.1.1 Dark matter distribution

We construct mass models of eight gas rich dwarf galaxies that lie in the Lynx–Cancer void and we find that both the isothermal and NFW halos are a good description of dark matter distribution of galaxies in terms of fit-quality (i.e. χ_{red}^2). From NFW fits to the dark matter halo profile, we find that the concentration parameters of haloes of void dwarf galaxies are similar to those of dwarf galaxies in normal density regions. We convert the rotation curves derived using 2-D and 3-D approaches into density profiles. This allows us to examine the central dark matter density profiles and to distinguish between the cores and cusps at the center of galaxies. We find that the dark matter halo density profiles derived using 3-D approach are consistent with Λ CDM profiles and the measured inner slopes ($\alpha = -1.39 \pm 0.19$) are more steep than the values of the slopes from the literature ($\alpha = -0.2 \pm 0.2$ in [de Blok et al. \(2001\)](#), $\alpha = -0.29 \pm 0.07$ in [Oh et al. \(2011b\)](#) and $\alpha = -0.42 \pm 0.21$ in [Oh et al. \(2015\)](#)). Since the mass models for the galaxies in the literature were constructed using the 2-D approaches, we use the rotation curves derived using 2D approach to estimate the inner density slope (α) values. The value of $\alpha \sim -0.5-0.7$ we get using the 2D approach is consistent with the slopes obtained in literature. This suggests that the fundamental differences in 3-D and 2-D tilted ring fitting routines affect the slope of the central dark matter density profiles. Since our sample size is modest, it is important to check the results using larger samples. We plan to confirm the results with a larger sample of highly resolved dwarf galaxies by using various tilted ring fitting routines such as 3DBarolo (3D), FAT (3D), and classical Rotcur (2D) and further investigate the residual systematic problems in determining and modelling the rotation curves of galaxies.

6.1.2 Angular momentum

We present measurements of the baryonic mass and specific angular momentum of 11 void dwarf galaxies. We find that the locus of void dwarf galaxies in the j_b - M_b plane is the same as that of dwarf galaxies in average density environments. However, all gas-rich dwarf galaxies (i.e. regardless of environment) have significantly higher baryonic specific angular momentum than expected from the relation obtained for larger spiral galaxies. We find that this elevation in specific angular momentum occurs for dwarf galaxies with masses lower than $10^{9.1} M_\odot$. As the baryonic mass of the galaxy increases beyond $10^{9.1} M_\odot$, the baryonic specific angular momentum decreases and they tend to follow the relation obtained for the massive galaxies with zero bulge fraction. Interestingly, the mass threshold that we find, viz, $10^{9.1} M_\odot$ is very similar to the mass threshold below which galaxy discs start to become systematically thicker. We examine the possibility that both these effects, viz. the thickening of discs and the increase in specific angular momentum are results of feedback from star formation. Such feedback would preferentially remove the low angular momentum gas from the central parts of dwarfs (thus increasing the specific angular momentum of the system) and also inject mechanical energy into the system, leading to thicker discs. We find however, that the observed amount of observed star formation in our sample galaxies is insufficient to produce the observed increase in the specific angular momentum. It hence appears that other, as of yet not identified mechanisms, play a role in producing the observed enhancement in specific angular momentum. We speculate that cold accretion may be one possible mechanism.

We study the relationship between the HI specific angular momentum (j_{gas}) and the HI mass (M_{gas}) for a sample of galaxies with well measured HI rotation curves that spans a range of morphology. We find that the relation is well described by an unbroken power law $j_{\text{gas}} \propto M_{\text{gas}}^\alpha$ over the entire mass range ($10^7 - 10^{10.5} M_\odot$), with $\alpha = 0.87 \pm 0.05$. This is in reasonable agreement with models which assume that evolutionary processes maintain HI discs in a marginally stable state. The slope we observe is also significantly different from both the $j \propto M^{2/3}$ relation expected from tidal torquing models and the observed slope (0.55 ± 0.02) of the specific angular momentum-mass relation for the stellar component of disc galaxies. Further, we show that the break in j_b - M_b arises because of the change in gas to stellar mass ratio with

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mass as well as the different slopes of the $j_s - M_s$ and $j_{\text{gas}} - M_{\text{gas}}$ relations. Our sample includes two HI-bearing ultra diffuse galaxies, and we find that their angular momentum follows the same relation as other galaxies. The only discrepant galaxies in our sample are early-type galaxies with large rotating HI discs, these are found to have significantly higher angular momentum than expected from the power law relation. The HI discs of all these early-type galaxies are misaligned or counter-rotating with respect to the stellar discs, consistent with the gas being recently acquired. Overall our observations support simulations which suggest that late stage wet mergers, as well as cold flows play a dominant role in determining the kinematics of the baryonic component of galaxies.

6.2 Future work

6.2.1 HI deficient and HI excess galaxies

The baryonic specific angular momentum of a galaxy evolves during the galaxy evolution since different internal and external processes can redistribute the angular momentum of baryons. These processes include accretion, outflows, inflows, stripping, and merging. For example, in the case of mergers, 'wet' (i.e. with gas rich precursors) mergers could lead to an increase in the baryonic spin parameter, while 'dry' mergers typically lead to a decrease in the baryonic spin parameter (e.g. Lagos et al. (2018)). The effect of these processes can be better understood by studying both HI excess and HI deficient galaxies.

Measuring the gas angular momentum of HI deficient galaxies residing in different environments will enable us to understand how different physical processes affect the locations of galaxies in the $j_{\text{gas}}-M_{\text{gas}}$ plane. For example, if the galaxy has lost its gas during ram pressure stripping, j_{gas} is expected to decrease since the high angular momentum gas from outskirts is lost. If the gas is lost from the central regions of the galaxy during outflows, one would expect the j_{gas} to increase and it may remain constant if the gas is lost uniformly throughout the galaxy in the case of starvation. We expect processes such as ram pressure, stripping, merging, and starvation to dominate in cluster environments and gas accretion is more common in isolated environments. We plan to identify a sample of HI deficient galaxies in isolated environments, groups, and clusters and study the deviation from $j_{\text{gas}}-M_{\text{gas}}$ relation as a function of the tidal

index. Similarly, studying the j_{gas} of HI excess galaxies with little star formation will allow us to understand the effect of gas accretion on angular momentum. Various signatures in the HI morphologies (e.g. truncated disc, hole in the centre, low surface brightness disc, counter rotating or misaligned HI disc with the stellar kinematics) can be mapped to the increase / decrease in j_{gas} .

6.2.2 Quantification of HI morphology

Asymmetries in the HI gas distribution and kinematics of galaxies are thought to be indicators for both gas accretion and gas removal processes. For example, truncated HI discs, one sided HI tails, lopsided HI morphologies can be associated with ram pressure stripping. We expect gas accretion to be more common in the lowest density environments and the removal of gas in the highest density environments. We can quantify the HI morphology (e.g. Concentration, Asymmetry, Smoothness, Gini and M_{20}) to check the environmental dependence of gas accretion and gas removal processes (e.g. Holwerda et al. 2011; Giese et al. 2016). We have presented HI imaging of 24 void galaxies in this thesis. In addition, we have obtained GMRT observations for 6 dwarf galaxies in Virgo cluster and 6 dwarf galaxies in UMa region. We plan to quantify the HI morphologies of these galaxies and thereby study various environmental processes as a function of environment (e.g. voids, groups, clusters, etc) and of their position within the void/cluster.

6.2.3 Ultra diffuse galaxies

The ultra diffuse galaxies (UDGs) have stellar masses of dwarfs but have effective radii of Milky Way sized objects. The majority of the UDGs are red and are more common in clusters. However, galaxies with extreme ratios of stellar mass to stellar scale length were also discovered in HI surveys of isolated environments (e.g. Leisman et al. 2017). These galaxies are called HI-bearing ultra diffuse galaxies (HUDs), which are bluer compared to the UDGs in the clusters. In this thesis, we have presented the measurements of j_b of 2 HUDs, which have similar j_b as that of other dwarfs. This result is in contrast with formation scenarios that predict that UDGs are genuinely dwarf galaxies residing in high spin haloes. However, the sample is too small to make statistically significant conclusions. Thus, we have recently obtained GMRT observations for 16 HUDs residing in isolated environments. These observations can be used to measure

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their HI column densities and dynamic masses along with their j_b measurements. The HI column densities of UDGs will give us important insights on whether they have sufficient column densities to form stars. Measurements of the dynamical mass of the halo should allow us to find out whether UDGs reside in Milky Way sized halos or if they are genuinely dwarf galaxies. Further, we plan to search for HI in cluster UDGs and obtain interferometric images for the detected ones. We plan to compare all the parameters (e.g. dynamic mass, angular momentum, etc) for both the red UDGs residing in clusters and isolated HUDs to test whether the formation of UDGs is linked to the cluster environments or that they formed outside the clusters and are later aggregated to them.

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